

D3.2 Interim Evaluation report of pilots 1
WP3 – Piloting at the City Labs
31/08/2019

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	780783	Acronym	FAMILIES_SHARE
Full Title	D3.2 Interim Evaluation report of pilots 1		
Topic	H2020 CAPS Topic: ICT---11---2017		
Funding scheme	IA Innovation Action		
Start Date	1/1/2018	Duration	34 months
Project URL	www.families-share.eu		
EU Project Officer	Loretta Anania		
Project Coordinator	Agostino Cortesi, UNIVE		
Deliverable	D3.2 Interim Evaluation report of pilots 1		
Work Package	WP3 Piloting at the City Labs		
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M20	Actual 30/11/2018
Nature	R – Report	Dissemination Level	P - Public
Lead Beneficiary	UNIVE		
Responsible Author	Maria Sangiuliano, Marzia Cescon, Natasha Sega	Email	maria.sangiuliano@smartvenice.org
	Smart Venice	Phone	+39 3401792661
Contributor(s):	FBK (Chapter 1), all partners		
Keywords	Social-digital innovation & platform evaluation, acceptance, usability		

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0	18 th June 2019	Draft	Release of ToC. Feedback on ToC	SV, FBK, all partners
1.1	14 th August 2019	Draft	Release of the first draft to WP3 partners and feedbacks collection (1st level check)	FBK, UNIVE, VILABS
1.2	26 th August 2019	Draft	Improved draft version to all partners for comments and approval of the deliverable (2nd level check)	All Partners

1.3	28 th August 2019	Draft	Collection of feedbacks from reviewers for refinement	FBK, UNIVE, Vilabs
2.0	31 th August 2019	Final	Release of the final version	SV

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© **Families_Share, 2018**
 This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Sommario

<i>Executive summary</i>	7
<i>Introduction</i>	9
Document structure and intended audience	9
<i>Part I. Evaluating the first prototype</i>	10
1.1 Research Methodology	10
1.2 Technical features of the 1st prototype	10
1.3 Results from the heuristic evaluation	13
1.4 Results from the usability tests	16
1.4.1 Data collected	18
1.5 Further platform improvement and second release	20
<i>Part II. Digital social innovation pilots in the City Labs</i>	27
2.1 Overall approach and research methodology	27
2.1.1. City Labs reporting approach	28
2.1.2. Evaluation methodology	29
2.2 Overview of the main City Labs features, engaged participants and stakeholders	31
2.2.1 Overview of the main City Labs features	31
2.2.2 Parents and stakeholders involvement in the preparatory phase	34
2.2.3 Parents and stakeholder involvement in the piloting phase	38
2.3 Bologna City Lab	40
2.3.1 Background and previous steps at the Bologna City Lab	40
2.3.2 Preparatory activities	41
2.3.3 Pilots	42
2.3.4 Results from evaluation in Bologna	43
2.4 Trento City Lab	44
2.4.1 Background and previous steps at the Trento City Lab	44
2.4.2 Preparatory activities	46
2.4.3 Pilots	48
2.4.4 Results from evaluation in Trento	50
2.5 Venice City Lab	53
2.5.1 Background and previous steps at the Venice City Lab	53
2.5.2 Preparatory activities	54
2.5.3 Pilots	58
2.5.4 Results from evaluation in Venice	61
2.6 Hungarian City Lab	62
2.6.1 Background and previous steps at the Hungarian City Lab	62
2.6.2 Preparatory activities	64

2.6.3 Pilots	65
2.6.4 Results from evaluation in Hungary	66
2.7 Kortrijk City Lab	66
2.7.1 Background and previous steps at the Kortrijk City Lab	66
2.7.2 Preparatory activities	68
2.7.3 Pilots	70
2.7.4 Results from evaluation in Kortrijk	71
2.8 Thessaloniki City Lab	71
2.8.1 Background and previous steps at the Thessaloniki City Lab	71
2.8.2 Preparatory activities	72
2.8.3 Pilots	74
2.8.4 Results from evaluation in Thessaloniki	75
2.9 Hamburg City Lab	77
2.9.1 Background and previous steps at the Hamburg City Lab	77
2.9.2 Preparatory activities	77
2.9.2 Cancellation of the Hamburg City Lab: reasons and reflections	78
<i>Part III. Evaluating the Families Share app</i>	79
3.1 Participants to the study	79
3.2 Log in data analytics and improvement of the platform app based on users feedback during the pilot	80
3.3 Perceived Usability and Technology Acceptance	85
3.3.1 Overall results	86
3.3.2 Perceived usability in the City Labs	87
3.4 Perceived Usefulness	89
3.4.1 Overall results	89
3.4.2 Perceived usefulness in the City Labs	90
3.5 Attitudes, social diffusion and intention to use	92
3.5.1 Overall results	92
3.5.2 Attitudes, social diffusion and intention to use in the City Labs	94
3.6 Trust and privacy	96
3.6.1 Overall Results	96
3.6.2 Trust and privacy in the City Labs	98
<i>Part IV. Main strengths and challenges encountered in the digital-social innovation experiment and emerging models</i>	99
4.1 The core strengths	100
4.2 Main challenges	100
4.2.1 Entrusting oneself and other parents as care givers and educators: parents resistances and concerns	100
4.2.2 Informal vs formal care: (gendered) paradoxes and tensions of bringing childcare out of the services' market	100
4.2.3 Regulatory issues	102
4.2.4 Families with different backgrounds	102
4.2.5 Various type of stakeholders resistances	102

4.2.6 Organizational hurdles: families last minute withdrawals	103
4.2.7 Groups of children with different ages	103
4.2.8 Children sickness	103
4.2.9 Safety and insurance issues	103
4.2.10 Technical issues of the platform	104
4.2.11 Embedding and aligning social and digital innovation	104
4.3 Emerging models	105
<i>Part V. Scenarios of future use and requested additional features</i>	107
5.1 Requested additional features	107
5.2 Reflecting on scenarios of future use	109
<i>References</i>	112
<i>ANNEXES</i>	114
Annex 1. Heuristic Evaluation	114
Annex 2. Usability testing	115
Annex 3. City Labs Periodic report	116
Annex 4. Interviews	121
Annex 5. Focus group	123
Annex 6. Survey	124
Annex 7. Privacy and data protection	126

Executive summary

The Families Share project has undergone its first pilot experiment whereas a socially innovative model of time sharing for childcare based on volunteering, self-management and mutual help from parents (co-playing) supported by an on line platform/app to facilitate organization of activities, has been proposed in 8 cities (Venice, Bologna, Trento, Kortrijk, Thessaloniki, Hamburg, Budapest, Győr), and tested in 6 of them (Venice, Bologna, Trento, Kortrijk, Thessaloniki, Győr).

The Families Share app has been released in several versions, it has been subject to two rounds of initial evaluations followed by improvement's cycles, before the actual piloting: a heuristic evaluation was held with experts from partners, and a usability test (early March 2019) run with 46 participating parents and, following those, the platform was made ready for 'in situation' use in May 2019 (see details of results and their impact on the design process in Chapter 1).

Positive results have been achieved for a first test in very different contexts: from February to July 2019, each City Lab has held many meetings and gatherings where representatives from 54 stakeholders have taken part, mostly schools, city representatives and NGOs. During the same periods, 384 parents have attended meetings and preparatory events, 285 of those have also experimented co-playing activities between June and July, with different adapted versions of shared childcare as a social innovation component of the project, and 95 users have registered on the Platform.

Two major typologies of co-playing activities have emerged: co-playing weeks and afterschool/afternoon activities; variations are definitely influenced by a series of highly contextual macro and micro factors in each one of the involved cities and neighborhoods. On one side, for summer co-playing weeks, a more straightforward choice prioritizing the goal of offering a solution to childcare during holiday periods in the requires more volunteering efforts from parents. On the other hand, for the afterschool activities a more gradual approach was putting the need for building trust and communities of parents up front. While in Kortrijk, Venice, and Trento to a lesser extent with its specificities as a work place based pilot, parents have been more intensively and directly conducting childcare activities in great part contributing to organizing them, the other City Labs have used a more gradual approach with respect to experimenting the proposed socially innovative behaviours.

The gap between the number of co-playing parents and the number of registered users on the platform is explained by the fact that in the city with the highest number of co-playing parents (Kortrijk) the platform was not used. Indeed, as it is reported and argued along Chapter 2 the 'platform has been used 'in situation' as a tool for organizing the co-playing activities in Venice and Trento only, while in Győr, Thessaloniki and Bologna it has been tested by parents during the activities or right after their conclusion. The project has been implemented by almost all the City Labs in such a way that the proposed social innovation has been tested while at the same time co-designing a digital tool with the same groups of participants. Only for the Belgian City Lab this was not the case, and the 2 dimensions of innovation were not aligned: in that case, a fully accepted social innovation already ongoing since almost 5 years, facilitated by a series of supporting tools, has created an habit from parents. This has been an obstacle to the acceptance of the digital innovation component, especially as the release of ready to use version of the platform came at a point in time when they had already organized their summer co-playing weeks (May 2019). To this respect, the Families Share experience so far confirms that **promoting acceptance of a digital tool and a socially innovative behaviors at the same time, can reinforce each other**, while, **vice-versa, misalignment can generate resistance from participants/users**.

Nevertheless, the feedback from the 75 parents participating to the evaluation of both the shared childcare activities and platform were encouraging: as reported in Chapter 3, the social innovation component is extremely appreciated and valued by all participants across all the 6 cities. The main strong point and added value perceived by parents and City Lab managers is definitely the **trust-based community building opportunity** that the Families Share social innovation model brings about, and the fact that it is a **high quality and affordable childcare solution**.

Many parents across different City Labs have expressed their intention to repeat the experience already during the upcoming new school year in autumn/winter, and their positive experience will be thoroughly communicated, with WP5 support, at the local levels to expand the City Lab communities.

Evaluation of the app/platform was also overall positive: it was considered quite easy to use and useful by the majority of parents (60%). Considering technology acceptance (a broader construct with respect to usability), results of the survey show that almost 50% of the respondents in the City Labs considered the platform useful and easy to use, and they have a positive attitude toward the application and a positive intention to use the app in the future. The results suggest that while the app is mostly perceived as usable and useful, users would need a stronger motivation for sustaining adoption and continuous usage of the platform.

The evaluation has allowed to identify the most relevant encountered challenges (Chapter 4) in the Families Share piloting process, and to identify emerging models and a series of additional requested/desired features as well as reflections on future scenarios of use (Chapter 5). Findings will be used by partners to carefully monitor the dynamics of appropriation of the proposed digital and social innovations, in view of finalizing the co-design process and further refining the platform and its upcoming new and last release, as well as to organize the new pilot activities in 2020.

Introduction

This document reports on the activities conducted in WP3 as part of Task 3.3 (“Pilot experiencing of socially innovative childcare sharing models and testing of the Families_Share platform”). The main goal of these activities was to support and evaluate the whole process of piloting the Families Share model and platform within the different City Labs. Indeed, in order to activate and evaluate the digital social innovation experience as well as enhance the quality of the digital tool, two pilot iterations were foreseen according to the Grant Agreement. The present document reports on the first pilot iteration and provides useful elements to be further explored and taken into account in view of the second pilot iteration (M24-32).

Document structure and intended audience

This document comprises 5 parts:

- *Part I. Evaluating the first prototype.* In this part, the technical features of the 1st platform pre-release and the results gathered through **heuristic evaluation** and face-to-face **usability tests** are summarized, following the evaluation guidelines described in D3.1. (Methodology of pilot testing and evaluation, and Guidelines for Community Managers).
- *Part II. Digital social innovation pilots in the City Labs.* Objective of Part II of the report presents the results of the first real world experimentations carried out in each City Lab, as well as all the processes and dynamics taking place in the preparatory and piloting phases. Both the social and the digital experience is described, in order to point out strengths and weaknesses both of the social model and the digital platform, and make the necessary adjustments in view of the second piloting phase (M24-M32).
- *Part III. Evaluating the Families Share app.* In Part III, the results of the evaluation activities of the Families Share app and model carried out after the completion of the pilot activities at the different City Labs are described.
- *Part IV. Main strengths and challenges encountered in the digital-social innovation experiment and emerging models.* The present Part presents the main strengths and challenges encountered during the first piloting by the City Labs as well as the models that seem to emerge in the piloting and acceptance of the social innovation model in its different versions and the digital platform use, and their interrelation in the different contexts.
- *Part V. Scenarios of future use and requested additional features.* The last part explores the future developments of the Families Share platform and model. Its aim is to identify possible future scenarios of Families Share platform and different use of shared childcare models in the various contexts, and the additional features that would be needed in order to implement such scenarios.

Part I. Evaluating the first prototype

1.1 Research Methodology

The first version of the Families Share platform was released in February 2019 (M13), and was developed according to the needs analysis performed in WP1, and according to the requirements described in D1.2. We summarize in this section, the technical features of the 1st platform pre-release and the results gathered through **heuristic evaluation** and face-to-face **usability tests**, following the evaluation guidelines described in D3.1. (Methodology of pilot testing and evaluation, and Guidelines for Community Managers). These evaluation activities had the main goal to address the main usability issues before the start of the piloting activities in the 6 City Labs. According to the iterative design lifecycle adopted in Families Share, feedback from users and stakeholders have been collected also during the real-work pilots of the Families Share co-play activities through face-to-face semi-structured **interviews** and **focus groups**, **surveys** (in collaboration with WP4 “impact assessment”) and the study of users’ interaction from the platforms’ **log analysis**.

In the present document, the platform/app evaluation is split across sections 1 and 3, while section 2 focuses on the social innovation component and the specific contexts of each City Lab. Thus, section 1.2 describes the results of the heuristic evaluation of the pre-release version of the Families-Share platform and section 1.3 presents the usability tests conducted with representative users (10 participants for each City Labs). Part 3 describes the results from the evaluation conducted after the piloting activities that provided indications on users’ acceptance of the digital platform.

Figure 1. Evaluation activities structure

1.2 Technical features of the 1st prototype

In the following graphic representations we summarise the main features of the 1st release of the Families_Share platform (See D2.2. for a more detailed presentation of the features).

The platform can be accessed from a web application (working on a web browser, including browsers on iOS) and from a mobile application for Android OS.

<p>Register and provide information</p> <p>Users can register to the platform creating a new combination of username and password or using Google credentials.</p>	<p>Create a personal profile</p> <p>Users can create a personal profile for sharing contact information with other parents</p>
---	---

Log In

Email

Password

CONFIRM

Forgot Password?

OR LOG IN WITH

GOOGLE

By logging in you agree with our Terms of Service and Privacy Policy

Don't have an account? [Sign Up](#)

Edit profile

SAVE

Name
Lucia Bianchi

Phone number
+48 12345678

Label
Mobile

Address
Church Street, 45

City

State

Email address
lucia.bianchi@email.com

Create a child profile

Users can create profiles for their children adding information that can be useful for other parents when conducting the co-playing activities (e.g. allergies, special needs, etc.)

Gabriele Bianchi

March 13th, 2008
10 years old

Boy

Lucia Bianchi
Mother

ADD PARENT

Additional info

ADD

Create and join groups

Users can create or join new groups of parents. Access for new members is moderated by the group administrators.

Create group

- Provide a name and description

New group

A new group of parents

CONTINUE CANCEL
- Set the visibility
- Provide the location
- Invite people

<p>Search and join an existing group</p> <p>Users can search for existing groups of parents and request to participate.</p>	
<p>Join an activity</p> <p>Users can participate in the activities as volunteer or register their child(ren)</p>	<p>Communicate with other parents</p> <p>The application includes basic features for supporting communication among parents.</p>

Figure 2. Main features of the 1st release

Figure 3. Other screenshots

1.3 Results from the heuristic evaluation

Following the evaluation guidelines described in D3.1, an heuristic evaluation activity was performed with the goal of identifying the main usability issues of the pre-release that should be fixed before the real-world experimentation.

In heuristic evaluations, only experts are involved. We decided to perform the evaluation activity during the Project meeting held in Hamburg in January on the 22th and the 23th 2019 in order to engage in a

collaborative evaluation two types of experts: HCI experts working in the project with a background on usability and UX as well as use-case scenario experts, that are City Labs representatives. This solution was chosen in order to have multiple perspectives and gain insights from the different contexts in which the Families Share platform will be used. Evaluators were asked to examine the mobile app interface and to report issues and criticalities. At the end of all evaluation sessions, each collected usability problem was analyzed and similar problems were combined in order to reduce redundancy. The result was a report with indications for the developers to fix critical usability issues and to improve the user experience of the Families Share application.

Picture 1. Hamburg Project meeting

During the evaluation task, partners of the consortium were split into small groups composed by 4-5 participants. The groups had to inspect the app following a scenario and a given set of tasks. Usability issues as well as criticalities of the app in relation to the specific needs of each CityLab were reported as written reports by groups on a shared digital file (see Picture 1).

The results of the evaluation will be recorded from each evaluator in a digital document as a google form (see Picture 2).

In this file, evaluators had to report:

- the description of the problem encountered
- the priority level (1 = non critical, 5 very critical)
- the type of issue encountered: usability problem or a problem related to functionalities

After the project meeting the HCI experts worked with the development team in order to refine the understanding of the criticalities emerged during the group work, and define the heuristic violated, according to Nielsen & Mohlic heuristics (1990; see also D3.1. for the description of the heuristic evaluation method and the detailed description of the heuristics). The file was then used by the development team to address the issues encountered and prepare the release to be used in the City Labs for the usability testing.

ID	Name	Description	Priority	Type	Heuristic	Status
8		Scroll down not working on iOS (cannot see the whole menu)	4 Critical	Usability	User freedom	Verify
24		Default tab when you are in a group should be "activities"	4 Critical	Functionality	Opinion vary	Closed
27		Issue with password (every time log-in, must reset the password)	4 Critical	Usability	Flexibility	Closed
28	Agostino	Create a group: cannot set the visibility	4 Critical	Functionality		Closed
29	Agostino	Need to accept to be part of the group	4 Critical	Functionality		Closed
43	Manolis	Times change when I create an activity/timeslot. It appears to be a timezone issue. We need to always make sure we store the information wrt the same timezone in each community/citylab. This could be a community setting	4 Critical	Usability		In progress
53		Start up guide : should be changed by group administrators - provide links	2 Medium	Functionality		Need further
56	Marzia	"Group members" screen: icon for option should be different from the mail icon	4 Critical	Usability	Consistency	Closed
67		Add multiple choices in location for Venice app (Venezia Centro Storico, Venezia	4 Critical	Functionality		In progress
9		Confirmation button looks disabled on "group" (same appearance disable / not selected)	3 Serious	Usability	Consistency	Closed
12		Stepper go back with click	3 Serious	Usability	Consistency	Closed
18		Family: the person should accept the invitation	3 Serious	Functionality		Closed
20	Marie	When you invite a new group member, I would like to see a list of all people (like a contact list on the phone) - leave it as an option?	3 Serious	Functionality		Closed
21		Profile: remove the "visibility of profile" option: information about profile should be visible only by group member	3 Serious	Functionality		Need further
23		ADD Parent: a textbox open but ADD is not allowed (web interface)	3 Serious	Usability	Visibility	Closed
25		Get accepted to the group without accepting the invitation	3 Serious	Usability	User freedom	Closed

Figure 4. Results from the pre-release app evaluation at the Hamburg project meeting. The entire table can be accessed on https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1BjpBek7oUfILTGz9yNM4tTf_o_rhDg1S6LXHIL2-xo0/edit

The evaluation resulted in a total of 78 issues, 51 of them were classified as usability issues (e.g. "When sending a message, pressing Back would bring to the home screen" or "In the child profile screen the delete parent button is missing") while 27 were considered as additional functionalities to be added to the application (e.g. "When an activity has met all the constraints, members should be notified" or "It should be possible to invite people to download the app through WhatsApp, Telegram or email"). Most issues were rated with medium priority, while usability problems with serious and high level were identified and addressed on a priority basis (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Priority level and type of found observed in the heuristic evaluation.

The following graph (Figure 6) shows the number of usability problems by heuristics. Issues related to the "cognitive load" category includes problems related to the amount of mental resources that is required to operate the app. "user freedom" includes issue with undo and redo actions, while "real world matching" comprises the match between the application and the real world, such as information presented in a natural and logical order or the use of familiar words, phrases and concepts. "consistency" includes issue in the platform conventions and "visibility" the use of appropriate feedback and information on the system's status. Issues labeled in the "error prevention" category include the use of

design elements and patterns for preventing problems from occurring, “*aesthetic*” the adoption of minimalist design, “*flexibility*” the accessibility of the system to inexperienced and experienced users as well. Lastly, the use of “*help and documentation*” support, and of meaningful error messages that clearly state how to recover for error or unintended actions (“Error recovery”).

Figure 6. Usability issues found in the heuristic evaluation.

Data collected during the expert inspection are shared among the team and an overall order of priority is defined. Results are further elaborated with the development team to find solutions to the criticalities identified (as part of Tasks 2.1 - Platform front-end and 2.2 - Platform back-end).

1.4 Results from the usability tests

Usability testing was conducted with City Labs engaged parents to understand users' actual behaviors with the mobile app and to gather information regarding usability issues (e.g. difficult-to-complete tasks, confusing language, etc.). All participating users were made familiar with the project's goals, and the social innovation component based on shared childcare that the app/platform is built to support and promote: attention was paid by researchers to prevent the possibility that the usability testing was influenced by a lack of understanding of the innovative practices the technological artifacts is meant to sustain.

The usability tests investigated efficiency, effectiveness and perceived difficulty (see Table 1) in using the Families_Share mobile app and web app, following the methodology described in D3.1.

Aspects	Indicators	Description
Efficiency	Measured as the level of ease or struggle to accomplish a task.	Measured by observer through a 5-point Likert scale 1 = Completed without struggles 5= Not completed, lot of struggles

	Measured as task completion time	Measure time to complete each task
Effectiveness	Quality of solution	How did the task have been performed? Describe the interaction path the user followed to complete the task
	Error/criticalities experienced	Describe the main issues encountered in terms of: i) understandability of information/navigation flow/ UI elements, ii) trust & privacy issues,
Perceived difficulty	Perceived user difficulty (SEQ)	Overall, how easy did you find this task? 7 point Likert scale 1= very easy 7= very difficult

Table 1. Usability evaluation aspects investigated in the usability tests. For a detailed description please refer to D3.1 (Section 3.3 - 3.3. Individual face-to-face usability testing)

During the testing, participants were asked to complete specific tasks on the application, while facilitators observed the interaction with the system and tried to understand their problem asking people to “think aloud”. In a thinking aloud usability test, participants were asked to use the system while continuously thinking aloud, i.e. verbalizing their thoughts as they perform tasks on the user interface (Nielsen 1993). In this way, participants were asked to explicit their mental process during the completion of tasks.

Since the test was performed before the real-world experimentation, scenarios were created to help users in understanding the context of use of the application and the motivations behind it.

A scenario was created including a brief description that gave the context behind the activities presented in the test. Below the scenario (with Eline or Mark as protagonist) used (each CityLab adapted the name and context based on their specificities):

Scenario / Eline version

Eline, mother of Lisa (7 years old), is looking for childcare for the next summer period in August. At the local primary school, she hears at the school gate that also other parents are looking for alternatives for arranging childcare during summer. Mark, father of Ben (7), mentions that his family is using the Families_Share application for arranging childcare during the holiday periods. Together with other parents, they decide to use the Families_Share app to organize childcare activities. The app support group of parents to create groups and to organize activities. Group members can give their availability for specific activities, in order to cover the period needed.

Scenario / Mark version

Mark, father of Lisa (7 years old), is looking for childcare for the next summer period in August. At the local primary school, he hears at the school gate that also other parents are looking for alternatives for arranging childcare during summer. Eline, mother of Ben (7), mentions that his family is using the Families_Share application for arranging childcare during the holiday periods. Together with other parents, they decide to use the Families_Share app to organize childcare activities. The app support group of parents to create groups and to organize activities. Group members can give their availability for specific activities, in order to cover the period needed.

Nine tasks were included in the first version of the usability test protocol. Eight additional tasks were added to include also some other activities involving group administrators:

Number	Optional	New Tasks	User Role
--------	----------	-----------	-----------

Task 1		Register a new profile	Regular user
Task 2		Edit your address in your personal profile	Regular user
Task 3		Create a profile for your child	Regular user
Task 4		Join the group “XXX”	Regular user
Task 5		Invite a friend to download the app	Regular user
Task 6		Write a message to the group	Regular user
Task 7		Insert your and your child's availability for the activity XXX (activity already created by another user)	Regular user
Taks 8		Create a new activity named XXX	Regular user
Task 9		Create a new group named XXXX	Regular user
Task 10	●	Edit name, photo, address and email in your personal profile	Regular user
Task 11	●	Edit a child profile > add special information, birthday, gender	Regular user
Task 12	●	Search a group and remove your availability to an activity	Regular user
Task 13	●	Invite a friend to join in a group	Administrator
Task 14	●	Accept the join request of a new user in the group	Administrator
Task 15	●	Add a parent in a child's profile	Regular user
Task 16	●	Edit the name, description and the profile photo of the group	Administrator
Task 17	●	Using the pending activities icon: See details of an activity and accept it	Administrator
Task 18	●	Add a user as an administrator	Administrator

Table 2. List of tasks

1.4.1 Data collected

46 participants from 6 City Labs took part in the usability study. The total sample consisted of 35 female participants (76%) and 24 male participants (24%), with different declared/self-perceived degrees of familiarity with technology (from beginner technology users to expert ones, with the majority of participants being average or advanced users).

CityLab	Participants
Venice IT	8
Bologna IT	10
Trento IT	10
Kortrijk BE	4

Females	35
Males	11

Familiarity with technology	
Beginner	6

Hamburg DE	4	Average user	18
Thessaloniki GR	10	Advanced	15
Total	46	Expert	7

Table 3. Characteristics of the participants involved in the Families_Share usability tests.

Figure 7. Gender and technology familiarity distribution of usability testing participants.

Table 4 shows the main quantitative outcomes in terms of time and observed/reported difficulty.

Task	Description	Reported difficulty (SEQ)	Observed difficulty	Average Time
Task 7	Share your availabilities	4.53	3.28	223.74
Task 2	Edit profile	3.17	2.22	115.95
Task 8	Create a new activity	2.69	2.38	181.87
Task 3	Add a child profile	2.62	2.09	118.88
Task 1	Sign-in	2.26	1.98	142.26
Task 6	Send a message	2.1	1.65	63.59
Task 4	Join a group	1.98	1.72	93.74
Task 9	Create a new group	1.85	1.59	109.5
Task 5	Invite friends	1.67	1.51	56.77

Table 4. Average scores and completion time for the nine main tasks investigated in the usability study. Tasks are ordered and coloured based on the reported difficulty.

Based on the results of the usability tests, the main findings were the following:

- **Task 7** (Insert your and your child's availability for the activity “XXX”) was the most difficult ones and the task that required more time. The interaction required to add the availability to participate in a co-play activity was difficult to understand and mainly reported as confusing and perceived as non-standard.
- **Task 2 and 3** (editing personal profile and add children profile) can be further improved to make the information fields more accessible and easier to fill in.
- **Task 8** (create a new activity) the process of creating an activity needs more editing functionalities, it was perceived as too rigid.

Usability testing results

Figure 8. Average score for reported difficulty in completing the main 9 tasks. The green area indicates the time taken to complete each task.

Overall, the major issues encountered by every user were interaction problems for sharing availability. Since this is one of the core functions of the Families Share digital platform, this section was completely redesigned. The homepage screen and the calendar views were also adjusted based on the qualitative outcomes that emerged during the usability study. The improvements to the first pre-release are described in the following section.

1.5 Further platform improvement and second release

According to the quantitative and qualitative outcomes of the usability tests, three main redesign actions were proposed for improving the interaction with the mobile application:

1) Redesign the interaction for sharing availability

The task of adding personal availability was considered the most difficult one among the nine tasks. Interface and interaction issues included the many steps that were required for adding the availability (form the

homepage the user had to select the group, select the activity, select the time slot and select the corresponding button). Moreover, the availability screen was displayed as an overlay dialog box and included a horizontal scrolling container with different “chips” representing the user and her children. The overlay window and the horizontal scrolling interaction have been mainly perceived as non-standard and unintuitive: for these reasons the redesigned screen included a more traditional use of Google Material language, a clear separation between individual’s and children’s availability, and a separate screen for selecting such information.

Sharing availability – v1 main issues

Figure 9. Main issues of the sharing availability functionality

Sharing availability – v2 redesign

Use a more standard visualization and interaction patterns

Timeslots are displayed when an activity is selected (instead of clicking the bottom element)

Availabilities (parents and children) are more clearly separated

Participation to a timeslot is more evident

Users can add location for activity and location for timeslot (option)

Figure 10. Redesign of the “sharing availability” screens based on the observations collected during the usability tests. The interface and the interaction were completely redesigned to improve intuitiveness and ease of use.

2) Improve the homepage screen

Homepage redesign - comparison

Calendar in the homepage is confusing

Difficult to see groups below the calendar

Simplify the homepage by moving the calendar in a separate section

The homepage shows a list of groups and activities

The interface displays messages and shortcuts for joining groups or activities

A second option would be to move the calendar below the list of activities

Figure 11. Homepage redesign

Homepage redesign – *new design*

Figure 12. Homepage new design

From the qualitative observations, the homepage was considered by many users as confusing and unclear. The first pre-release version included the calendar in the homepage (taking out a relevant portion of the screen), while the group list was displayed below the calendar. This GUI organization gave much emphasis on the personal calendar, limiting the user in exploring other functionalities.

A cleaner version of the homepage has been redesigned to highlight the main social functionalities of the app (the “groups” and the “activities” related actions), while the personal calendar was included in a dedicated section accessible from the lateral menu.

Some call-to-action were also displayed in the homepage in order to motivate the user in joining new groups and/or in exploring the activities proposed by each group.

The new homepage was designed to gradually change during the user involvement in the Families_Share activities, including more graphical elements once the user joined a group or participated in some activities.

3) Redesign personal and group calendar sections

In the Families_Share app the user can access different calendars: the personal calendar and the group calendar. The personal calendar includes all the activities in which the user gave his/her personal availability or his/her children availability across the different groups. This calendar was placed on the homepage in the first pre-release, and then moved to a dedicated section in the second version.

The group calendars display all the activities that are confirmed for that specific group and it is meant to help group members and group administrators in planning the proposed activities. New colors and visual feedback were included in the visualization of group calendar to highlight different activities and different status for each activity (i.e. planned, confirmed and closed)

Calendar

Pre-release v1

Pre-release v2

Personal calendar
(was in the home screen)

Group calendar
(in the group screen)

Move personal calendar in a separate section

By default, the group screen shows the list of activities (and not the calendar)

The group calendar is in a dedicated section

Figure 13. Calendar redesign

4) Other improvements

A number of GUI improvements and bug fixes were also identified during the usability testing. Such issues were submitted on the GitHub¹ repository and addressed by the technical team.

The table below shows some examples of such improvements.

	Description	Example (issue)	Example (solution)
GUI structure	Address incorrect appearance and layout structure Eg. Improve the dialogue box for adding new parents to a group		

¹ <https://github.com>

<p>Compatibility</p>	<p>Ensure compatibility with different devices</p> <p>Eg. Identify and address compatibility issues with different mobile devices and Android OS versions</p>		
<p>Interaction behavior</p>	<p>Address incorrect behaviors of user interaction</p> <p>Eg. Provide meaningful constraints (e.g. set the default number of parents required for an activity to two)</p>		
<p>Reversibility</p>	<p>Address incorrect results of undo or redo operations</p> <p>Eg. Provide icons for closing overlay box (e.g. notification box)</p>		

<p>Feedback Confirmation dialogues</p>	<p>/ Provide adequate feedback to system actions</p> <p>Eg. Add confirmation box for accepting or discarding edits.</p>		
---	---	--	---

Figure 14. Other improvements to the Families Share application following the usability testing.

The second release of the app took place in May 2019, when a dedicated app downloadable through Google Play was created per each City Lab.

Part II. Digital social innovation pilots in the City Labs

Objective of Part II of the report is to present the results of the first real world experimentations carried out in each City Lab within the month of July 2019, as well as all the processes and dynamics taking place in the preparatory and piloting phases. The overall goal is to describe both the social and the digital experience of people taking part to the pilot activities, in order to point out strengths and weaknesses both of the social model and the digital platform, and make the necessary adjustments in view of the second piloting phase (M24-M32).

2.1 Overall approach and research methodology

The present paragraph describes the methodology adopted to report on the digital social innovation pilots, and in particular, on the activities carried out during the preparatory phase, the piloting phase and the evaluation phase.

The adopted methodology implied collection of a mix of qualitative and quantitative data, as well as a mix of online and offline approaches. In particular, used methods were written reports on the preparatory phase and the pilot prepared by the partners in charge of City Labs, individual interviews, focus groups, a survey, group and bilateral calls among City Lab managers. The time frame taken into consideration goes from February to July 2019 (M14-M19), being the present report due by M20 (August 2019).

The figure below sums up the adopted methodology.

Figure 15. Methodology structure

2.1.1. City Labs reporting approach

As concerns the reporting activity, City Labs were at first asked to provide periodical updates about the status of preparatory activities, then to report about the pilots and finally about the evaluation activities. This allowed to achieve a continuous monitoring of all the steps and developments.

As far as the preparatory phase and the piloting phase are concerned, in order to facilitate the reporting process, the mentioned period (February-July 2019) was divided in three bi-monthly sub-periods: February-March, April-May, June-July. City Labs representatives were asked by the Smart Venice team as WP3 leaders, to report on the activities carried out during each sub-period. In order to do so and as already mentioned, activities were divided in two “categories”: **preparatory activities** and **pilot activities**, the former representing the activities carried out in each City Lab in order to involve and engage stakeholders and families, and to undertake all the necessary actions for setting up the pilot, and the latter consisting in the concrete realization of the pilot aimed at using the Families Share app/platform to support childcare sharing activities among groups of parents.

For the monitoring purposes, the Smart Venice team elaborated a reporting template (see Annex 3) to be filled in and submitted by partners within given deadlines (one week after the end of each sub-period except for the last report that due to time constraints had to be submitted by the 26th July). The template’s structure was updated and adjusted during the overall reporting period in order to meet the emerging information needs.

In their periodic reports, City Labs were asked to summarize in dedicated tables numbers and socio-demographic features of stakeholders and parents involved in the period. In particular, sex, age range and migrant background of parents were kept monitored, as well as the type of institution and the role in the activities of stakeholders involved.

Furthermore, detailed information about preparatory activities were collected. As mentioned, with preparatory activities we mean all those activities such as meetings with both parents and stakeholders or other activities related to logistics and regulatory frameworks, needed for the set up of the piloting actions meaning the co-playing sessions, which took place either before or during piloting. The aim was to gather as many information as possible regarding the activities carried out, the people involved, opinions and eventual issues on the Families Share social innovation model. Per each preparatory activity, City Labs were asked to provide the following information:

- features of the place-neighborhood where the activity took place;
- the overall number of adults (and eventually children involved);
- presence of institutional representatives or stakeholders with legal entity and their roles/contribution;
- socio-demographic profile of participants;
- discussed issues;
- emerging needs and motivations;
- emerging perceptions and expectations about FS;
- technology mediation for community’s engagement and for relations within the communities (e-mails, social media, etc.);
- any other issues related to the action in view of piloting shared-childcare.

Besides meetings, City Labs were asked to indicate other preparatory activities consisting, for instance, in the stipulation of contracts/agreements (i.e. insurance contracts, agreements with public entities, etc.), creation of ad hoc entities (i.e. NGOs), etc.

Regarding the section of the report dedicated to the pilot activities, City Labs were asked to provide details about the activities carried out: information related to the participants (adults and children), duration and the type of the activities.

Also, a description of the overall piloting action capturing its main elements/contents in terms of participation, educational content, type of usage of the app/platform made was requested.

Details on offline-online dynamics and the type of use made of the platform were also collected, in order to understand the pilot action features in real life contexts, as well as the relation between the social and digital aspects of the experiment, the and the extent to what the platform/app was an effective tool to make shared childcaring possible.

City Labs managers were also asked to clarify reasons and/or hypothesis behind any observed gaps between the social innovation/childcare sharing experience and the platform usage.

The last section of the report concerned other useful information related to pilot experience in terms of social innovation (parents' expectations, quality of relations, trust among parents), possible conflicts/misunderstanding arisen, role of the platform/app in the experience and suggested future improvements, insurance and safety issues.

The periodic reporting was combined with dedicated bi-weekly calls among City Labs representatives and mediated by the Smart Venice team, during which each City Lab was asked to give an update about activities carried out, as well as about any encountered issues. City Labs exchanged also tips and good practices they met during the process. In total, 5 calls took place during the period. The most discussed topics were resistances from parents and/or stakeholders to accept the proposed social innovation model, and insurance aspects.

Once the pilot activities were concluded, City Labs were asked to complete the last periodic report and to carry out evaluation activities involving parents taking part to the pilot actions. It is important to highlight that while all the periodic reporting was meant to explore both the social and the digital components of the pilots, evaluation activities were mainly (not exclusively) meant at investigating the latter. Therefore, results related to the digital experience will be thoroughly outlined in the next chapter (Part III).

2.1.2. Evaluation methodology

The evaluation activities carried out by each City Lab were based on standard methods following the evaluation guidelines described in D3.1: individual semi-structured interviews, focus groups and a survey. Each City Lab was required to conduct at least 5 individual interviews and one focus group involving around 10 people. All participants to the first pilot needed to be involved either through an interview or a focus group. However, such target numbers were not always reached by City Labs due to various constraints (see sections from 2.3 to 2.9).

Individual semi-structured interviews² were organized as open conversations allowing new ideas coming up as a result of the interviews dynamics. During the interviews, participants were guided without strictly imposing the given formulation of the questions, allowing to tailor the templates to the specific context and to the specific interviewed participant. Most of the questions were open, but participants were also asked to

² See Annex 4

rate the level of perceived usefulness and usability of the platform by using Likert scales (see part 3 for more information regarding the interview structure).

As concerns focus groups, instead, they consisted in group interviews where a moderator guided the group discussion on a topic. Focus group should have involved min 6 and max 10 people taking part to the same pilot activities. The use of focus group at this stage was important for allowing participants to freely express their opinion; this technique usually generates more information than multiple individual interviews and since no one is required to respond to a question, spontaneous responses are encouraged. The moderator followed a schedule and paid attention to discuss each of the relevant dimensions as well as to eventual emerging issues and discussions among participants.

During interviews and focus groups, besides the moderator, the presence of a note-taker was recommended to City Labs. Moreover, they were invited to record both evaluation activities in order to be able to provide detailed reports.

Both interviews and focus groups included a few questions related to the overall social experience, but more space was given for exploring the digital experience, hence aspects related to usability, usefulness, trust and privacy and future improvements³ (see templates for interviews and focus groups in the Annex 4 and 5).

As concerns the survey, it was intended to investigate the following dimensions⁴:

- Perceived usefulness of the system;
- Perceived ease-of-use;
- Attitude toward using;
- Intention to use;
- Social diffusion;
- Privacy.

Dedicated questions aimed at exploring the above listed dimensions were included in the survey elaborated by IMEC in the frame of the impact assessment (WP4). Indeed, since the target of the WP3 and WP4 questionnaires was the same, decision to merge the two tools was made, in order to facilitate participation to the study and not overcharging participants with double tasks.

Dedicated bilateral calls with City Labs were set up, so to explore missing or uncertain data/information from the dedicated reporting templates they were asked to provide for the periodic reporting and for focus groups and interviews.

Efforts were made to render City Labs pilots descriptions as uniform and comparable as possible, although the various City Labs were featured by considerable differences in the quantity and quality of the documentation provided and in the activated processes setting up pilot activities.

In the following paragraphs, an overview of the engaged participants and stakeholders, and a punctual description of the pilot experiences per each City Lab are provided.

Each City Lab description is introduced by a paragraph on the background and previous steps, followed by the 3 already mentioned phases: preparatory activities, pilot activities and evaluation activities with focus on the social innovation model.

³ The mentioned dimensions were explained in details in D3.1 “Methodology of pilot testing and evaluation, and Guidelines for Community Managers”.

⁴ More information of the methodology behind the survey structure is provided in paragraph 3.5.

2.2 Overview of the main City Labs features, engaged participants and stakeholders

2.2.1 Overview of the main City Labs features

In the present paragraph an overview of the City Labs features will be provided trying, from one side, to highlight possible common features and, from the other, to identify peculiarities.

The following table sums up the City Labs' most relevant features. It takes into account a number of dimensions that will be explained below.

City Lab	Managing partner (Private entity, social enterprise/no profit organization, public entity)	Implementation stage (early phase, rapid take off, maturity/saturation)	Presence of volunteering parents in the managing partner's project team
Trento	Private entity (Company)	Early stage	Yes
Venice	Private entity (SME) -intermediary	Early stage	Yes
Bologna	Public entity (University)-intermediary	Early stage	No
Thessaloniki	No profit organization	Early stage	Yes
Kortrijk	No profit organization	Rapid take off	Yes
Győr	Social enterprise	Early stage	No

Table 5. City Labs features

As concerns the kind of **entity** in charge of the City Lab management, the table above shows how half of the City Labs are managed by social enterprises/no profit organizations, while one is managed by a public entity (University Ca' Foscari) and two by research oriented private entities (FBK and Smart Venice). It is worth to point out that only 2 entities, consisting both in social enterprises/no profit organizations base their own core activity on childcare. This is the case of De Stuyverij (Kortrijk City Lab) and the Parents House Foundation (Győr City Lab), the first one with a model entirely based on supporting self-organized/volunteer childcare sharing parents' groups. As concerns the others, in two cases (Venice and Bologna) the legal entities managing the City Labs do not normally provide childcare activities and act as intermediaries in the involved territories. In Trento, childcare solutions do not represent the core activity of FBK but the organization provides childcare solutions for its own employees, whereas in Thessaloniki childcare is not the main core activity either, but Ergani plays an important role in the integration of women in the socio-economic life and childcare represents an important aspect of such process.

The type of entity undertaking the management role affected the way piloting activities were organized. Indeed, only those partners which do not normally deal with childcare activities had either to set up a new entity (in the form of an NGO like in Venice) or to join forces with an existing one which already deals with childcare (like in Bologna), in order to overcome regulatory issues regarding either volunteering or access to public spaces.

Another important aspect to take into consideration is the **development stage of the social innovation component in each City Lab**. According to Mulgan⁵ social innovations spread in an "S curve", with an early phase of slow growth among a small group of committed supporters, followed by a phase of rapid take-off, and then a slowing down as saturation and maturity are achieved. Identifying in which phase each City Lab is

⁵ Mulgan G. (2006), The process of Social Innovation, Tagore LLC

currently situated helps understanding encountered processes and criticalities. Indeed, as it will better explained in Part IV, different stages of implementation imply different issues.

From the table above, it is immediately visible how most of the City Labs are now in their early phase in terms of the spread of the proposed social innovation model, with the exception of the Kortrijk City Lab, which has been running co-playing activities for years. Indeed, as it will better explained in the dedicated paragraph (see paragraph 2.7), after an initial phase, the Belgian City Lab is now living a rapid take off with a fast increase number of families involved (see also D3.1. “Methodology of pilot testing and evaluation, and Guidelines for Community Managers” for more details on the Families_Share approach to the community development).

The presence of **volunteering parents in the City Lab management** is an interesting indicator revealing how the childcare solution offered by the Families Share model directly emerged and was thought as a solution to childcare needs thought of by parents for parents. Indeed, according to Mulgan, personal motivation plays a critical role in social innovation process, since *“people may want to solve their own problems and (...) some of the most effective methods for cultivating social innovation start from the presumption that people are competent interpreters of their own lives and competent solvers of their own problems”*⁶. As indicated in the table, 4 out of 6 City Labs had volunteering parents in the management team.

While in the previous table features of the City Labs managing partners have been analyzed, in the following one the most relevant features of piloting activities carried out in each City Lab are reported.

City Lab	Type of pilot activities (co-playing weeks, afterschool/afternoon activities)	Professional educators involved	Costs related to the pilot (insurance or others)	Use of public spaces
Trento	Co-playing week, afterschool activities	Yes	Insurance, materials, Professional educators	No
Venice	Co-playing week	No	NGO setting up and insurance	Yes
Bologna	Co-playing week	Yes	Insurance and membership fee	Yes
Thessaloniki	Afternoon activities	No	No	Yes
Kortrijk	Co-playing week	No	Insurance	Yes
Győr	Afternoon activities	Yes	No	No

Table 6. Pilots features

At first, it is important to identify the **kind of pilot activities** carried out by the City Labs. Two major typologies emerged: co-playing weeks and afterschool/afternoon activities. Only one City Lab (Trento) experimented both options. This is definitely influenced by a variety of macro and micro factors in each one of the involved cities and neighborhoods, and points out to different contexts. In the former case, it indicates a more straightforward choice prioritizing the goal of offering a solution to childcare during holiday periods and requiring more volunteering efforts from parents, while in the latter it reflects a more gradual approach putting the need for building trust and communities of parents up front.

⁶ Again Mulgan G. (2006), The process of Social Innovation, Tagore LLC

A dedicated reflection is needed as regards the **monetary costs** bore by each City Lab in order to carry out the pilot activities and the **involvement (or not) of professional educators**. This dimension is important to be monitored since the first pilot for a series of reasons:

- both dimensions might impact on fees charged to parents influencing their choice to participate, also depending on income and the availability (or not) of formal/conventional alternative childcare offers;
- the involvement of professional educators is a mark of a mixed, less 'radical', interpretation of the proposed social innovation model as it comes to shared childcare: it implies that volunteering parents activities are supported by paid professional educators. It means that formal and informal childcare coexist, and that childcare is only partially 'de-commodified' and brought out of the service economy (Federici, 2012)⁷. Such choice can be influenced by different motivations, among others lack of trust among parents or lack of self-confidence in being able to 'manage' a group of children, and the belief that performing childcare outside your own family requires professionalized skills and abilities.
- in both cases this can be an indicator of how the social innovation components position themselves in relation to different models, again more or less radical, of sharing economy⁸.

As the sixth column shows, 3 out of 6 City Labs involved professional educators in the activities, even if with different modalities that will be explained in each City Lab description. However, only in one case (Bologna City Lab) the professional educator did not receive a fee since she belongs to a volunteering association. The majority of costs concern insurance. Only 2 City Labs did not have insurance costs due to two different reasons: in Thessaloniki, parents were all present during all the pilot activities, whereas in Győr the pilot took place at the Family Center which already had an insurance policy in place. The costs bore by each City Lab are summarized in the following table:

⁷ Federici S. (2012), *Revolution at Point Zero. Housework, Reproduction, and Feminist Struggle*, Oakland, PM Press. See also paragraph 4.2.2 for further reflections on these aspects.

⁸Ossewaarde, M. & W. Reijers (2017), *The illusion of the digital commons: 'False consciousness' in online alternative economies*, Organization, Vol. 25, Issue 25, pp. 609-628; Acquier A., Carbone V. (2018), *Sharing Economy and Social Innovation*, ESCP Europe.

	Materials	Lunch	Paid educators	Insurance	Other/notes
Trento					
<i>Friday Mini Labs</i>	30€ (FBK)	5,90€ x child (parents, optional)		4€ x child (FBK)	
<i>Summer Camp</i>	50€	5,90€ x child	25€ x hour	8€ x child	100€ x child fee, discounted of 50% for volunteering parents, including all listed costs for one week full day participation
Venice	shared among parents	Prepared by families individually	//	20€ x participating adult as membership fee to the NGO	Administrative costs for setting up the Families Share NGO (donation by SV)
Bologna				25€ per participating adult paid by parents	10 € x parent membership fee Dadamà NGO
Thessaloniki	//	//	//	//	
Kortrijk	Shared or bought by families together	Prepared by families individually	//	Covered by the membership fee	30€ annual membership fee which also covers costs related to helpdesk, community management and tools
Gyor	//	//	Small amount to be determined	//	//

Table 7. Costs at each City Lab

The last relevant aspect considered in the present analysis is the involvement of the **public sector** in the pilot activities. Even though, generally speaking, public bodies tend to move too slowly for social innovation actors (Mulgan, 2006), their involvement is crucial in order to guarantee a wider impact of the proposed models in their territories. Also, with particular reference to the Families Share model, the support of public entities was particularly relevant. Indeed, except for those entities already using their own premises available for free (this is the case of Trento and Győr), most of the City Labs made use of public under-utilized spaces during holiday periods, like schools (Venice and Kortrijk) or other public areas (Bologna and Thessaloniki). In Venice, the local city authorities made also other resources available in terms of support from the pedagogical teams of the municipality, help in reaching out to parents from the network of school, offering cleaning services in one of the 2 Venetian pilots and making a young ‘civil service’ volunteer available for part of the activities.

2.2.2 Parents and stakeholders involvement in the preparatory phase

In the period from February to July 2019, in each City Lab, the preparatory phase took place. During the mentioned period, indeed, community managers of each City Lab carried out a number of activities, mainly consisting in meetings with stakeholders and families in order, from one side, to receive all the necessary support by institutions and other stakeholders involved for the organization of the activities, and from the other side, to identify parents interested in taking part to the first pilot. It is well known how the role of

supporting stakeholders is crucial in facilitating diffusion and scale up of social innovations⁹ (NESTA-DSI report) therefore in the present and following paragraph (2.2.2) we provide a more detailed picture of stakeholders and participants in all the City Labs engaged during the preparatory phase, trying to identify common features and differences.

In paragraph 2.2.2 the same analysis will be carried out with reference to the piloting period, whereas all the processes and dynamics occurred during the first pilot organization will be described in details for each City Labs in sections from 2.3 to 2.9.

Engaged stakeholders

During the preparatory phase, all City Labs got in contact with different stakeholders, both in order to disseminate and promote Families Share throughout the local territory, and to receive the necessary support for the later organization of the pilot. The following table indicates the number of stakeholders (entities) involved by each City Lab, divided per typology.

City Lab/Stakeholders typology	Schools	Public Bodies (Municipal offices, region, etc)	Local associations active in childcare	Insurance companies	Other organizations (NGOs/cooperatives)	Internal offices	Research centres	TOT
Trento				1	2	2	1	6
Venice	3	2		1				6
Győr								
Kortrijk	1 per co-playing group		1		2			4+*
Bologna	1	6	7	2	3		1	20
Thessaloniki	5		2		1			8
TOT	10+*	8	10	4	8	2	2	54

*The number of schools involved in the Kortrijk City Lab depends from the number of co-playing groups, that is varying every period

Table 8. Stakeholders categories

The type of stakeholders is obviously reflecting the features of the City Lab and of the kind of pilot carried out. For instance, at the **Trento** City Lab, meetings were mainly held with internal offices of FBK, since the Trento Pilot is the only one focusing on social innovation in an organizational context and pilot activities addressed FBK employees. Differently, the **Venice** City Lab engaged Municipality's offices in charge of public schools/kindergartens and play centres, aiming at making such public spaces available for the Families Share pilots and to reach out to parents through public childcare services run by the Municipality itself. In **Kortrijk**, there were already consolidated contracts between co-playing groups of parents and public schools, so the Belgian City Lab held meetings with stakeholders to enlarge support services offered to co-playing parents. In fact, they got in contact with *De gezinsbond*, a big no profit organization for families that provides different childcare support (baby-sitters database, discount for children's stores, holidays camps, and so on); *Refu*

⁹ Stokes M., Baeck P., Baker T. (2017), What next for digital social innovation? Realising the potential of people and technology to tackle social challenges, NESTA - Digital Social Innovation

Interim, an employment office for refugees who are looking for places where they can volunteer; and with *Bsit*, an application to find babysitters.

In terms of numbers, the City Lab of **Bologna** was the most active in stakeholders' engagement, managing to involve stakeholders from all categories. This was due to the ongoing attempt of the City Lab to set up a so called 'collaboration pact'¹⁰ with the Municipality, in order to obtain the future possibility of using public spaces. This is, however, a long process, that needs to be checked and validated by different internal offices of the Municipality. The City Lab also aimed at identifying and making agreements with local associations and cooperatives interested in actively running the Families Share pilots (Leila and Dadamà Associations). The **Hungarian** City Lab did not have the chance to engage any stakeholder at this stage, due to the little time available for the pilot organization (see section 2.6.1). Finally, in **Thessaloniki**, different schools were involved to disseminate the project among parents, as well as local associations, like for instance scouts' groups and an NGO working with young people and children for the promotion of human rights, through artistic actions. The role of the engaged stakeholders in the project in each city will be explained in detail in the dedicated paragraph (Background and previous steps) of sections from 2.3 to 2.9.

Engaged parents

The figure below shows the overall number of parents engaged in each City Lab during the preparatory phase, from February to July 2019¹¹. These data result from the periodic reporting summary tables provided by each community manager. In the mentioned tables, community managers indicated both the overall number of involved participants and the number of new participants engaged in that specific sub-period (February-March, April-May, June-July).

Figure 16. Overall number of parents engaged

¹⁰A "Collaboration Pact" is a contract between a local public authority and groups of citizens (associations or informal networks) regulated by a City Protocol on shared management of urban commons, to formalized the active role of citizens in taking care of whatever public space, with focus on under-utilized or abandoned spaces. 185 Cities in Italy are reported to have such protocols in place (<https://www.labsus.org/2019/03/ecco-chi-sono-i-patti-protagonisti-dellitalia-che-si-prende-cura-dellitalia/>). They could represent a facilitating framework for the sustainability and replication of the Families Share social innovation model.

¹¹The numbers were obtained by summing up the new engaged parents per each reporting period.

It is immediately visible how the City Labs of Kortrijk and Győr represent the exceptions, due to their intrinsic features. Indeed, in Kortrijk the co-playing model has been run and used by families over the last 4 years, reaching about 50 groups of parents up to now. The 210 participants shown in the chart above represent the overall number of parents involved in co-playing activities during the mentioned time frame.

On the other side, the case of the Győr City Lab is peculiar, due to the fact that the Parents' House only joined the project starting from May 2019 and started with the preparation activities leading to the pilot in June 2019. The short available time did not permit the Győr City Lab to reach an high number of parents.

The diagram below offers an overview of the **parents' involvement trend**¹² in the considered time frame per each City Lab. The diagram does not show the trend for the Győr City Lab since, as already explained, only 4 parents (female) were engaged between June and July 2019.

Figure 17. Engaged parents trends

The chart reflects a similar trend in Bologna, Trento, Venice and Thessaloniki, all in their early stages, and the gap with Kortrijk where, as mentioned, the City Lab is already in a 'take off' phase.

As far as gender differences are concerned, the diagram below offers shows the gender gap featuring parents involvement in the City Labs.

¹² The numbers were obtained summing up the overall number of parents engaged in the reporting periods.

Figure 18. Involved parents by sex

The figure shows that the share of female parents involved is predominant.. Indeed, the gender dimension represents a relevant issue within the project, considering that the male involvement spans from 0% (in case of the Győr City Lab) to 33% (in case of Trento), with an average 11%, therefore far from the 40% considered as a mark of gender balance. In Bologna, the limited participation from fathers was (partly) due to cultural background of the involved migrant communities. The scarce involvement of men in childcare activities is definitely widespread at a European level and not a feature of single socio-economic contexts¹³. The two City Labs where men are involved to a higher extent are Trento (33%) and Venice (27%). However, it is important to point out how in Trento FBK employees are mainly men, and this most likely impacted on higher levels of involvement from their side. As the Families Share consortium considers gender equality in childcare one of the key features of its desired social innovation component, additional efforts will be put to improve a gender balanced participation in the second pilot iteration.

2.2.3 Parents and stakeholder involvement in the piloting phase

For most of the City Labs the first pilot occurred between June and July 2019, with the exception of Trento, where the first pilot activity was conducted in May and the second in July, and Kortrijk, where parents co-played also during Easter holidays (April). In general, during the piloting phase, **stakeholders engagement** activities in the form of meetings were less frequent than in the preparatory one, even though in some of the City Labs, their involvement played a crucial role for carrying out pilot activities:

- In **Bologna**, the pilot was conducted in collaboration with Dadamà association, which provided the space and organized the summer camp activities.
- In **Trento**, beyond the continuous collaboration with the FBK HR office, for the second pilot the community managers collaborated also with Kaleidoscopio, a social cooperative that provided external educators in support of the FBK summer childcare activities.
- In **Venice**, a continuous relation was maintained with the Municipality, due to the use of two public spaces for the pilot (a kindergarten and a Play Centre). In addition, a policy insurance was stipulated with UnipolSAI in order to cover the pilots' participants (parents and children) and the spaces.
- In **Kortrijk** some agreements with new schools were signed by the co-playing groups.

¹³ In this regard see Oláh L. Sz., Kotowska I. E. and Richter R. (2018), The New Roles of Men and Women and Implications for Families and Societies, in *A Demographic Perspective on Gender, Family and Health in Europe*, pp.41-64.

For what concerns the participating parents to the first pilot activities, the figure below summarized the main data available per each City Lab.

Figure 19. Number of co-playing parents per City Lab by sex

While more details on pilots' participants in each city will be provided in the following section (see sections from 2.3 to 2.9), it is here important to report on some overall considerations:

- The **format** was varied and required different **intensity of participation and degree of shared childcare from parents**: Venice and Kortrijk used a model based on a self-organized and self-managed full time summer camp; Trento held workshop activities managed by parents, in one of the 2 pilots embedding them within an existing summer camp and engaged parents as carers during lunch breaks as well. Győr experimented childcare afternoon activities; in Bologna parents were invited to freely and informally contribute to childcare activities offered for free by a volunteering NGO (Dadamà Association). Thessaloniki organized networking and trust building activities where parents took part jointly with their own children and where some of the parents were taking care of the children in turns during the same activity while the rest of the adults were socializing among themselves.
- In most City Labs volunteering participants were **parents** (no grandparents or other adults were involved), with few exceptions. In Trento some of the volunteering FBK employees co-playing with children were not parents themselves. Also, during the second pilot activity (the Summer Camp) other adults beyond parents and employees were involved (educators of the Kaleidoscopio cooperative). The same happened in Bologna, where the representative of Dadamà association volunteered in co-playing. In Győr parents were supported by an external educator too.

- As mentioned, there was a high **prevalence of mothers** involved in the pilot activities, and in some cases, men were totally missing (Győr and Bologna).
- The **age range** of participants spanned from 30 to 55 years old.
- Many **families with a migrant background** took part to the pilots, mainly in the City Labs of Bologna (all the families involved), in Trento (2 parents out of 15) and Venice (5 out of 19).
- The majority of participants were **employed** and in couple, mostly with a **middle socioeconomic status**. Only a few of the participating parents were unemployed, the majority belonging to the Győr City Labs (2 out of 4) and Thessaloniki City Lab (5 out of 11). **Single parents** in Thessaloniki counted 4,1 in Venice 1 and in Győr.

The next sections will investigate in detail the processes and dynamics of the first pilot preparation and implementation in each City Lab.

2.3 Bologna City Lab

2.3.1 Background and previous steps at the Bologna City Lab

The Bologna City Lab managed by UNIVE engaged and contacted local stakeholders since the early phase of the project, in order to assess local needs and possible ways to implement Families Share in the city. Initially, the City Lab got in contact with three associations who had sent the letter of intent to collaborate in the project in the proposal submission phase, namely:

- The ASP (*Azienda pubblica di Servizi alla Persona*), a public association working on offering social welfare services;
- Mondo Donna, an NGO working on social inclusion through an intercultural and gender perspective;
- Momo Banca del Tempo, a Time Banking system run by an informal network.

Other four involved NGOs in the childcare system were contacted in a second stage of the project, to investigate their possible collaboration with Families Share:

- Banca del tempo Zoè (a time bank);
- three parents' associations: Mammabo, Damadà, and Amaca.

The community managers conducted different meetings with the above-mentioned organizations in order to assess the current situation in Bologna concerning the **public and private offer of childcare services**. It emerged that different associations working on childcare are already present in the territory, but they are usually small and scattered across the city. According to the interviewed stakeholders, the involvement of migrant families, highly present in the peripheral neighborhoods of Bologna, would be very important: even though the local childcare offer is very rich and constantly improved, the emerging picture showed how less central areas of the city are less covered by public services. According to the contacted stakeholders, the Families Share model could be a possible solution, since it allows to create different networks based on pre-existing communities, in all the different areas of the city, through the help of technological tools.

Childcare needs were investigated during the first year of activity and it was highlighted how **lower-class families (and migrants** in particular also due to language barriers) usually encounter more difficulties in creating a network of support with other families. The need emerged for after-school childcare activities and during long school holidays, like in the summer-period. On the other side, **middle-upper class families** could more easily afford childcare services, but they have difficulties in organizing extra-school activities and in finding trusted and reliable childcare solutions during emergency situations (like in case of frequent school strikes or children illnesses).

The **co-design workshop** of the Families Share platform was conducted by the Bologna City Lab, together with other two associations, during an existing event (*Moms Market/Il Mercatino delle Mamme*). Out of the 6 different scenarios proposed by the organizers, the preferred one focused on the organization of shared childcare during both school and summer periods, among a group of parents with the help of an external facilitator/educator. This model was then used in the first pilot in WP3.

In addition, during the co-design the importance of a **time-banking system** was stressed, something that was actually not perceived as needed in the following steps of the piloting, and was therefore discarded.

2.3.2 Preparatory activities

In the period between February and July 2019, the Bologna City Lab organized different preparatory activities aimed at diffusing the project in the territory, thanks to the collaboration of different local bodies and organizations. Community managers organized a high number of **meetings** with a variety of **stakeholders**: from the public administration (Bologna Municipality and Emilia Romagna Region), to the social cooperatives and associations working with parents or offering childcare services. Thanks to this wide project dissemination, the City Lab obtained four endorsement letters for supporting Families Share, from the Municipality, the Region, the Open Group cooperative and the Urban Innovation Foundation.

Moreover, the Bologna City Lab participated in a working table in the Savena district answering to a municipal call for proposal, in which different associations were presenting ideas for bottom-up territorial and community development. Additional bounds with local realities were created during this consultation. The several meetings held both with the Municipality and with the local associations were all necessary steps in order to ask the City Administration for a “collaboration pact” (see above, footnote n° 10), an agreement between a group of citizens and the Municipality to request the use of public spaces for self-organized community activities. In this way the Bologna City Labs aimed at getting dedicated spaces for groups of parents to organize self-managed childcare activities and to make the collaboration with supporting NGOs operational in view of organizing the pilot.

Among these meetings, the most important ones were with:

- **Leila** (association), with which the City Lab established a partnership for organizing some preparatory activities for the project dissemination,
- **Dadamà** (association) and **MammaBo** (informal group), who both had a central role for the organization of the first pilot, as it will be explained in section 2.3.3.

Such meetings had on one side the goal of facilitating interaction, socialization and outdoor co-playing among parents to increase trust in the shared childcare model, and connecting Families Share to other initiatives featured by a strong ‘sharing’ approach, like the so-called ‘Leila’s Cargo Bike’, a bike wandering along Bologna parks and squares to encourage toys’ sharing and recycling.

On the other hand, several meetings with Dadamà were needed for the purpose of concretely organizing the pilot activities. This small association became the core player and partner for the pilot. Operated on an entirely volunteering base, it provides support to families of the San Donato - San Vitale multicultural districts, through different childcare services and parenthood support. Meetings with the Association’s leader and some engaged parents led to the decision of organizing a summer co-playing week where parents would volunteer and share their time in taking care of the children, still supported by an experienced educator, such the Dadamà leader herself. Socialization meetings and dinners were held with parents to further engage them and present the app as well.

The following table sums up the preparatory meetings carried out at the Bologna City Labs.

Preparatory activity	Kind of activity	Type of participants	Number of participants	Parents (M/F)	Topics
Leila's Cargobike (2 afternoons)	Co-playing of children and their parents out of their school with the Cargobike full of toys	Parents with their children, going at Marconi elementary school	3 adults (1 community manager + 2 part of Leila association); 10 parents; 20 children.	2 M 8 F	Project presentation, model and the app Trust among parents (how to create new groups or how to select among already formed groups). Which advantages Families Share could bring to their lives.
	Free play and co-play thanks to the Leila Cargo Bike (toys for outdoor activities) + a picnic.	Parents with their children, going at Scandellara school	12 parents; 25 children; 2 community managers	10 F 2 M	Sharing opinions about Families Share model and possible participation to the pilot.
Summer weeks with Dadamà	Introductory meeting to the pilots' activities	Parents	8 parents; Dadamà responsible; 2 community managers	8 F	Summer co-playing week organization and parents' role
	Movie beaming for children and social dinner (shared food)	Parents and children already informed about Dadamà activities	9 parents; 15 children; Dadamà responsible; 2 community managers	8F/ 1M	Socialization gathering
	6 Meetings with Dadamà responsible	The community managers and the responsible of Dadamà	3	3 F	Organization of the pilot in collaboration with Dadama' association

Table 9. Preparatory activities in the Bologna City Lab

2.3.3 Pilots

Picture 2. Images of the Bologna pilot

As anticipated, the Bologna City Lab organized piloting activities together with Dadamà association, already used at holding free of charge **summer camps** for children of San Donato - San Vitale districts in the past years, with the goal of promoting migrant families' inclusion. The pilot took place during the first two weeks of July, in *Piazza dei Colori*, a public square considered the ideal place for carrying out a social innovation experiment for its vivacity in providing social welfare solutions¹⁴. During these two summer weeks, the Dadamà responsible organized different activities for children (museums visits, days at the swimming pool, readings and games in the park, etc). Parents were volunteering in these different activities, being involved in whatever the children were doing, or helping in cleaning the location and providing food for lunch. There were 20 children participating in the activities, with an age range between 3 and 13 years old. An insurance was set up by the NGO and parents were charged for a related fee of 35 covering also costs of membership. No paid care givers/educators were engaged in the activities.

8 parents were involved in the pilot, all of them female, mostly with a migrant background and from a low socioeconomic status, working mainly as housemaids/ babysitters, or housewives. As pointed out in the need assessment of the Bologna City Lab (2.3.1), this kind of families are those that are more in need of cheap childcare services, since they are not able to afford the existing ones. These migrant families are both Muslim and Christian, mostly coming from Romania and Morocco and they live in the social housing blocks that surrounds *Piazza dei Colori*. In these families, mothers are often the only ones in charge of childcare since men are working full-time or on night shifts, and this explains the **encountered gender gap**. In addition, the lack of men in childcare activities in this neighborhood is due to cultural aspects as well, given that Muslim men cannot stay in a space where there are too many women, as a form of respect. They tend to participate only to common social events, when all the family is present. This was underlined during the evaluation activities by some of the participants, as one of the main reasons why fathers didn't join the pilot activities. During this first pilot implementation the City Lab managers faced **some difficulties**: several parents didn't show up and didn't take full responsibility, and few of them used the app, plus communication challenges emerged related to a limited knowledge of Italian from participants.

2.3.4 Results from evaluation in Bologna

The evaluation activities conducted by the Bologna City Lab involved 6 parents in the focus group and other 5 in the individual interviews. All of them were women and almost all (5 out of 6 in the focus group) had a migrant background, thus they were not all able to speak in Italian well. Thus, there was a mother during the focus group who was translating when someone was not able to understand or express her opinion in Italian. Evaluation activities were also used for a guided, one-to-one demonstration of the app/platform.

The evaluation led to identify **some challenges and critical issues** as following:

- the **twofold, enabling and inhibiting role at the same time of the promoting NGO and its leader** who acted as main educator in charge of the childcare activities supported by parents: although she was the main enabler of the pilot and all participants acknowledged the great contribution of the NGO in making the public space more lively and inclusive through its outdoor childcare support, to some extent she was perceived as inhibiting the ownership and empowerment of parents;
- this resulted also in a **low level of integration between the digital and the social innovation elements**: as the local promoting organization is mostly relying on the childcare provided by its leader and a few other volunteers, and lets the parents free to help when they have time only, without a

¹⁴ Indeed, Piazza dei Colori, since 2017, is part of the PON METRO project¹⁴ aimed at contrasting socio-educational poverty. It is also the place where the Dadamà venue is located.

set calendar of shifts for shared childcare, the app/platform which is mostly focused on organizing calendar and shifts could not prove to be useful in such a scenario.

- **communication problems in a multicultural group:** some of the parents were not able to speak either Italian or English. This created additional obstacles also in the use of the app.

Still, many **strengths of the Families Share pilot** were highlighted during evaluation activities:

- all participants underlined the **sense of community** that the activities of Families Share with Dadamà helped to create: being from different countries, cultures and religions, was never perceived as a barrier during the pilot. It was shared how the sense of community and the Families Share shared childcare approach it is something 'natural', already existing in the countries where their families come from. Instead, what it is innovative, is this same model brought in Bologna, where they are continuously facing barriers to social inclusion and community building;
- the **involvement of elderly people**, as some of them were enjoying the presence of children in the square. A promising future direction of the project would be the merger of two parallel activities: integration and socialization of over 65 elderly people in the same square and childcare share and support to parents with kids;
- the **positive effect** of this model **on children**, who felt free and had the possibility of socializing with their peers but also with kids of different ages. The outdoor feature of the project was not perceived as risky for the kids by parents. Being part of their own children's activities is also seen as an added value of the project, something which is not possible in traditional summer camps;
- the **potential positive role of the app in a future pilot**, provided that a fixed calendar with precise roles for each parent is set and greater responsibility expected from parents.

Further positive aspects emerged with regards to the overall experience from the **individual interviews**:

- proximity of the square to the houses of the participants;
- affordable price of the summer camp (35 euro overall);
- small group of children, that allowed a deeper knowledge of each other;
- spontaneous trust between parents.

Overall, the proposed mixed model of the City Lab of Bologna fostered the creation of mutual **trust** between parents, although coming from different countries and cultures. All the parents recognized the role of Dadamà as fundamental for them to join the activities, but they did not totally exclude the possibility to take more responsibilities in sharing childcare and planning activities. This leaves space for a possible future improvement of the Families Share model within the same community, by passing the ownership of co-playing to parents.

2.4 Trento City Lab

2.4.1 Background and previous steps at the Trento City Lab

The Trento City Lab is coordinated by FBK (Fondazione Bruno Kessler), partner of the project. The Families Share team and community management is composed by two employees of FBK, one of which is also a co-playing parent.

The Trento City Lab has the peculiarity of being thought of as a workplace piloting. Co-design and needs assessment activities during the year 2018 were organized involving the "Trento Family Audit District"

(Distretto Family Audit di Trento)¹⁵, an inter-organizational association where FBK is a member: the district is supported by the local government of Trento that aims at creating networks of public and private entities active in promoting work-life balance policies, increasing women participation in the labour market and experimenting novel forms of social organizations targeting families' needs. The regional context is featured by advanced work life balance policies and good quality/accessibility of childcare services, especially in urban contexts. The organizational context at FBK sees many CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) and 'company welfare/well being' already set up.

In this phase and during the initial consultations, the HR Departments of the Family District member organizations identified two possible scenarios in which the Families Share approach could be exploited:

1. Integrating Families Share approach in the already running FBK Summer Labs that are one-week long STEM educational and recreative activities organized for employees' children during the summer school break. These camps are part of the work life balance activity where the Families Share model could be integrated. Such Summer activities, run by external childcare professionals (a local cooperative) were already experimenting forms of volunteering and engagement of FBK employees at various informal and non-systematic levels, including laboratories based on the exploitation of the various scientific/research background, expertise and skills of employees, mostly researchers.
2. Shorter self-managed childcare initiatives to be organized in the FBK spaces dedicated to work-life balance activities (The 0-100 room).

A number of barriers and potentially critical issues were identified which kept being raised also in WP3:

- the difficulty to engage employees during their working hours;
- the lack of forms of substantial recognition from the management of employees' efforts when they take part to childcare activities as volunteers;
- insurance and legal aspects to be tackled;
- the importance to involve external educators in order both to ensure continuity in the childcare activities and to support employees in managing relational dynamics among children;
- trust issues.

As an outcome of this initial phase, decision to keep the piloting open to non-parents employees willing to volunteer was also made.

The first pilot phase in Trento was characterized by the exploration of two different scenarios: on one side, embedding the Families Share model in an existing childcare setting mostly run by childcare professionals, and on the other hand setting up entirely self-managed informal childcare. Timing misalignment created limitations in the app usage in both cases, and adapting the use of technology to already existing processes generated additional challenges in the full use of all the existing functionalities.

The peculiar work-place setting seems to create particular 'control related' concerns to parents who feel in need of external professionalized childcare support, fearing that relations/issues among colleagues could affect kids' relationships, and vice versa. Also due to this, the entirely self-organized model results feasible upon 2 main conditions: short duration (half a day activities) and dedicated training of parents.

¹⁵ The Trento Family Audit district is composed of 9 partner associations together with the City and Province of Trento <https://www.trentinofamiglia.it/Certificazioni-e-reti/Distretti-Famiglia/I-Distretti-Family-Audit/Distretto-Family-Audit-di-Trento>.

2.4.2 Preparatory activities

In the period from February 2019 to June 2019, the Trento City Lab carried out a number of preparatory activities, which mainly consisted in 8 meetings with organizations of the Trento Family District and various FBK departments.

After the initial involvement of the Family District, the second phase of activities at the Trento City Lab was featured by a decision to ground the pilot testing of Families Share within the FBK organization itself: several FBK departments were involved to discuss about the details. Indeed, an official executive decision was formalized to launch the Families Share pilot activities, to be structured in two different settings, Summer Camps (already in place) and the 'Friday MiniLabs', to be set up as a new educational initiative to entirely rely on parents/employees self-organized care.

In the preparatory period, 5 meetings with the FBK departments (Safety and Insurance Dept. and HR Dept.) took place in order to explore in depth crucial issues related to the pilots. In particular, potential risks in Families Share activities concerning trust, safety and security and insurance coverage were discussed with the appointed departments.

Considering the peculiar features of the Trento City Lab, the insurance aspect was particularly important to settle. Since the Families Share activities were launched as part of the institutional activities of FBK, the insurance provided by FBK to its employees covering civil responsibility was exploited together with an additional specific insurance policy covering potential injuries to children participating to Families Share activities activated on purpose. As concerns the Summer Camp, indeed, the insurance was directly managed by the external childcare provider hired for managing the camps (an external social cooperative).

Some criticalities were identified by the FBK Head of Prevention and Protection Service regarding penal responsibilities of adults taking care of children. Some actions were identified to mitigate the risk, such as offering training for adult volunteers on safety issues (e.g. preventive measures), checking all spaces and areas used for the childcare activities (even if such spaces were already formally compliant with standards), ensuring that the educational/recreational material was appropriate and safe for children.

The Trento City Lab had also a meeting with UnipolSAI, project's advisor, concerning the topic of insurance, in view of the second pilot activities, since FBK will not be the legal entity promoting Families Share activities and another existing or new legal entity will be established at this purpose.

Several preparatory activities were specifically organized for the organization of the two pilot activities: the Friday afternoons' MiniLabs which took place in May 2019 and the Summer Camp which took place in June-July 2019.

The typical profile of an employee taking part to Families Share activities is: 35-40 years old person, who works as researcher especially in ICT fields (software engineering, linguistic, developers), interested in work-life balance, who looks for a balance between the work-related duties and the participation to the Families Share activities, as well as for an institutional recognition of such participation.

The following table sums up the meetings carried out for the organization of the two pilot activities.

Pilots	Kind of meeting	Type of participants	Number of participants	Participating employees (M/F)	Topics
Fridays MiniLabs	Meeting with parents/employees	FBK employees	30 employees	8 male, 12 female	Presentation of the activity, employees involvement and identification of

					the first group of participants.
	Meeting with stakeholders	FBK offices (HR staff, Legal representatives of FBK, Health and safety Unit FBK).	5 people	3 male, 2 female	Insurance issues; Employees involvement and program draft
		FBK staff, UNIPOL SAI and other partners representatives	12 people	2 male, 10 female	Insurance issues
Summer Camp	Meeting with parents/employees	FBK employees	10 employees ¹⁶ (8 out of 10 are researchers ¹⁷)	4 male, 6 female	Activity presentation and employees engagement
	Meeting with stakeholders	Team "AUDIT Space 0-100" ¹⁸ (HR staff + researchers) and social cooperative Kaleidoscopio	7 people	3 male, 4 female	Integration of the Families Share model in the Summer Camp organization and activities planning

Table 10. Preparatory activities in the City Lab of Trento

The Trento City Lab conducted also preparatory activities for a third forthcoming pilot activity to be conducted in September 2019, involving the University of Trento (UniTN). Indeed, a meeting took place among the Families Share team, the FBK HR department and the University's HR office in order to put the basis for the organization of new labs to carry out at the University premises.

The roles of the different actors involved were defined as follow:

- FBK will provide the physical space and the lunch for children;
- UniTN will provide two educators and collect children's online registration;
- The Families Share team will take care of engaging employees for the organization of the 3 labs to be delivered in the morning and to coordinate the participants' efforts through the app. Volunteers are supposed to be engaged mainly among the ones who already participated to the previous editions of the Summer Camps. Later, a meeting with volunteers will be organized to define the final structure of the labs, finding material and looking for more volunteers if needed.

¹⁶ The 10 employees were contacted through e-mails, face-to-face informal meetings and the internal website <https://families-share.fbk.eu/>

¹⁷ to this regard, it is necessary to specify that in FBK employment contracts are either for researchers or for administrative staff, whereas the former is more flexible and as a consequence researchers are more easily involved in Families Share activities.

¹⁸ The team "AUDIT Space 0-100" (in Italian "AUDIT Spazio 0-100") is part of the project "Audit Family and Work" of FBK and aims at offering childcare activities to children aged 5-10. They are organized with the collaboration of the social cooperative Kaleidoscopio and external professionals. <http://hr.fbk.eu/it/servizi/spazio-0-100>

2.4.3 Pilots

Picture 3. Images of the Trento pilot

The Trento City Lab conducted 2 pilot activities, in May and July 2019 respectively. The pilots were managed by the Community Management of the City Lab, composed by the Families Share team (two FBK researchers, one male and one female) and two people from the HR staff.

First pilot activity – Friday Minilabs

The first pilot, named “Friday MiniLabs”, was organized during 4 Friday afternoons of May 2019. The activities, organized for the very first time within the Families Share project, were carried out in collaboration with the “Family audit Space 0-100” team and in synergy with HR team. The childcare activities targeted a maximum number of 10 children, due to place related security and insurance constrains, aged 6 to 12. This pilot consisted in **entirely self-organized after school childcare**, with no presence of external care/education professionals.

Ten children (mean age 7.9 years, min 6 and max 11) were registered to the activity and participated to the four MiniLabs (4, 7, 9, 6 participants respectively).

The Minilabs involved also 12 parents/employees (6 male and 6 female), 5 of which volunteered during the pilot activities. Other 6 non-parents FBK employees volunteered in proposing activities for the MiniLabs. On average 3 adults were present during the labs (excluding the support from the 2 project team’s member who were also always present), therefore the children/volunteering adults average ratio during each Lab was 1:3. The pilot consisted in 4 afternoon MiniLabs preceded by a shared lunch. Each MiniLab was structured as follow:

- **Lunch**: from 12:30 to 14:00 employees/parents with their children could eat together in the FBK canteen. Only 3 children had lunch in the canteen;
- **Laboratories**: from 14:00 to 16:00 children could attend Laboratories (focused on STEM/environmental issues with a creative approach)¹⁹;
- **Snack, free play or homework**: from 16:00 to 17:00, after the laboratory a snack break was offered and free time to children was given.

The pilot activities took place at FBK premises, in the area called 0-100, which consists in a room dedicated to work-life balance initiatives, and therefore compliant with legal standards on safety. Each laboratory was managed by minimum two employees who were supported during the whole activities by the community

¹⁹ The detailed program of the MiniLabs can be found at the following webpage <https://families-share.fbk.eu/le-attivita%3%A0> (in Italian).

managers. In general, the pilot had a positive outcome. However, some safety issues emerged in relation to the management of the group of children, especially after the end of the labs, when children had some free time to play. HR staff proposed to organize ad hoc courses/trainings with professional educators in order to give guidance to volunteers in 'how to better manage children'.

The use of the Families Share app/platform was limited in this first pilot by misaligned timing: as the organization and schedule of the pilot started before the app was available for the download (20th of May) its perceived usefulness was hindered. Even if a group was created and participants were invited to download it, but not all of them did it.

Second pilot activity – Summer Camp “Circular Eco Lab”

The second pilot activity carried out at the Trento City Lab consisted in a **Summer Camp** which was conducted in the period June-July 2019, in synergy with the “0-100” FBK Work/Life balance initiatives, named “Summer kids initiatives”. As anticipated, in this case the activities of the Families Share pilot were integrated in already existing and implemented initiatives targeted at FBK employees’ children and taking place at FBK premises, and adopted a mixed model including both self-organized informal care run by volunteering parents/employees and support from childcare professionals. As we will see below, this peculiar use case limited the full application, if not use, of all the app functionalities. In the frame of such activities the role of the parents/employees is to propose specific activities for children (related to their professional expertise or their hobbies) or support the professional educators in other activities (i.e., supervision of the children during lunch). The participation of employees is part of the Social Corporate Responsibility plan of the organization and the participating employees are rewarded with a discount of the summer camp fees for their children, although volunteering was not set as pre-requisite to apply for enrolling kids.

The Families Share approach was tested during the summer week called “Circular Eco Lab”, which involved 15 parents (11 female and 4 male) and 4 non-parent employees; two professional educators were also present. 16 children aged 7-11 took part to the Summer Camp.

The Circular Eco Lab activities were structured from Monday to Friday, from 8:30 to 17:00, as follow:

- 8:30 - 9:30 : Welcome and play (educators only)
- 9:30 - 11:30: Labs (Educators + FBK employees/volunteers)
- 12:00 - 14:00: Lunch break (Educators + employees/volunteers)
- 14:00 - 17:00: recreational activities (educators)

Of the 19 involved FBK employees (parents and non-parents)

- 11 used the app (they subscribed to the group “Circular EcoLab and volunteered during the Summer Camp (mainly parents, 9 female and 2 male);
- 7 employees gave support during the lunch break: children had lunch in a dedicated room and educators needed the support of two parents each day to distribute lunch and to manage the group of children;
- 4 employees conducted the labs during the morning activities. Each lab involved 2 or 3 employees.

As far as the use of the app/web platform is concerned, also in this case the planning of Labs activities starting in April was misaligned with the app release, so to compensate this and still favour its use, the Families Share team recommended to use it to organize the lunch breaks. Therefore, only some of those employees who volunteered during lunch breaks (6 out of 11) downloaded and used the app to organize their shifts, while 4 parents still preferred to rely on other communication channels: e-mails and face-to-face interactions and the same happened with employees organizing the labs. Even if registered parents included their children in

their profile, the app was not used to register or keep track of participating kids as the registration process is handled centrally at the HR level and because, as stated, volunteering is not a prerequisite for registration. This implies that the kids registration functionality even if usable (and partially used), was not entirely functional in the process. Finally, the chat included in the app was not used either for scheduling shifts during lunch breaks or for organizing the Labs.

For both the pilot activities, the role of the community management (composed by the Families Share team and the HR staff) was to get in contact with employees, inform, engage and motivate them to take part to the project and the initiatives, through e-mails, newsletters, a Trento City Lab dedicated website, and face-to-face meetings. The Families Share team also acted as group administrators during the pilots, creating the groups and the activities inside the app/platform: the use context for organizing lunch breaks did not raised the need from users to be active in describing the activities. If, as it is foreseen, it will be also become a tool for scheduling and organizing the educational activities, it might be needed to attribute registered volunteers/parents group some of the administrators roles.

2.4.4 Results from evaluation in Trento

According to the evaluation activities conducted in the two pilots activities carried out by the Families Share team in Trento, it is possible to make some overall considerations. 15 FBK employees took part to the evaluation activities. Most of them were researchers or computer scientists, aged 40-50 and 6 male and 9 female. Some of them were also parents, whereas others volunteered without having any children taking part to the activities.

As explained in paragraph 2.4.3, the two pilot activities differed per kind of proposed activity (after school activity vs summer camp) and per people engaged (entirely self-organized childcare by only parents/employees in the case of the first pilot and parents/employees together with childcare professionals in the case of the second one).

A first point of attention regards the role of **professional educators**: most of participants agreed that in case of week-long activities (e.g. the model of Summer Camp), the presence of external educators is fundamental in an organization setting. This was justified with a number of arguments:

- efforts required to self-manage week-long activities (considering 8h day) is considered too much intensive;
- employees do not have the required skills to manage big groups of children (more than 15) - (even though employees sees the participation to ad hoc trainings as a good opportunity) and children with behavioural/emotional difficulties;
- educators can better manage the different dynamics that arise in a group of children, especially when children are of different group ages, since they have the right role to establish effective rules and the authority to enforce such rules. Managing conflicts among kids is considered sensitive especially in a working environment where volunteering parents are also colleagues and where power relations/hierarchies are in place;
- educators can support employees in ideating and conducting a lab, which is considered as an effort consuming activity, especially helping employees in adapting contents and vocabulary to the specific children age and needs;
- educators can guarantee continuity of care, since children can always rely on a one or more people during the activity period.

Still, the support from professionalized childcare can also pose problems, in fact, parents taking part to the Summer Camp as volunteers reported to feel they were not much involved by external educators who,

probably due to some miscommunication, preferred to manage the lunch break themselves since the number of children was low.

Instead, self-organization by parents/employees is considered appropriate for shorter childcare activities which involve a limited number of children (e.g. 4 to 6), even if some of the participants expressed concern about taking care of children without an external supervision. In this case, **training** would help volunteers in properly manage a group of children. However, the realization of childcare activities without the supervision of an external educator is considered to be possible if other conditions are present:

- the availability of a dedicated space with toys and creative material, which would permit to parents to quickly organize ad hoc activities without putting many efforts in the planning phase;
- the presence of children of the same age, in order not to spend additional efforts and time to prepare ad hoc activities.

Some considerations must be done as concerns the **role of the technology** in the pilot activities carried out. As already mentioned in the previous paragraph, the Families Share app was available once the pilot activities organization had already started, therefore the Families Share team decided to propose the app to participants for organizing little/minor tasks such as the lunch breaks. On the contrary, the lab activities were decided and organized in the frame of dedicated meetings with parents/volunteers. The request to download the app represented an entrance barrier for some of the participants and since the past activities were all organized offline, it took time to participants to understand how the technology could be integrated into the existing ecosystem, as well as the opportunities it offered.

Overall, 11 parents/employees downloaded the app and used it for managing childcare activities during the two pilots.

According to the participants inputs, the app is perceived to be more useful for self-organized activities (short time, limited number of children), whereas for supporting the second scenario (long activities with compresence of employees and external educators), more advanced functionalities would be needed in order to make it useful. Indeed, in this last scenario, different stakeholders are involved in the process of organizing the activities (HR department, external educators from a social cooperative , FBK employees) and several steps are taken (ideate, plan, launch the activities). In order to be useful, the app should be able to provide support in the following tasks which are at the moment carried out through face to face meetings, e-mail exchanges and other tools:

- identifying 5 weeks in which to propose Summer Camps according with employee's needs;
- engaging FBK employees;
- defining contents for the labs;
- launching the initiative;
- applying for registration.

In general, employees were very satisfied about both the initiatives. The following positive aspects were identified by employees during the evaluation activities:

- Families Share makes it possible to teach to children something adults like (a passion they have);
- employees learn how to deal with different target groups of children, also thanks to the exchange with the educators;
- new relationships are built with work colleagues;
- it makes possible to spend more time with children, especially during the lunch breaks;
- the quality of the childcare offer is very high;
- employees know the people taking care of their children and this helps in terms of trust.

In particular, in relation to the self-organized activities (Friday MiniLabs), participants expressed a very positive attitude toward the initiative. They represent a very good opportunity for the work-life balance, especially for employees living close by to FBK, considering that they are conducted at the workplace. The high quality of the laboratories proposed by FBK employees, which are people parents trust, is also very much appreciated.

For most of the parents, childcare initiatives are very convenient when they match their work schedule.

With reference to the second pilot consisting in the Summer Camp with the presence of external educators (mixed model), the parents involved identified the following advantages:

- the location of the initiative;
- the high quality of the initiative in terms of the presence of educators and of the laboratories conducted;
- useful and interesting laboratories (e.g. robotics);
- the low/discounted price;
- the appropriate balance between laboratories and free play.

The participation of employees as **volunteers** in both the activities was perceived in a very positive way by most of the participants. However, they identified also some criticalities:

- preparing and leading labs is quite demanding, more than just supervising children. Less demanding activities should be also foreseen;
- it is difficult to identify activities for heterogeneous group of children of different ages (e.g. 7 to 12 years old). In order to create different activities for different target groups there is the need to involve more volunteers and more efforts;
- activities are planned for younger children. Also, laboratories for middle school children should be foreseen;
- it is complex to manage children dynamics, therefore an external educator could help a lot in this;
- sometimes it was a bit complicated to hold a lab in which the employee's child was present;
- in general, more employees should be involved. For this to happen, further formal recognition of volunteering should be put in place. Although participation is already taking place within working hours and employees are authorized by HR, it was suggested to allocate employees a certain number of hours to spend for volunteering activities, which can be internal work-life balance activities but also volunteering activities for external organizations;
- parents/employees should be involved in different ways, not only for the organization and conduction of the labs. In particular, employees could help in buying the required materials, giving support during the labs, giving suggestions and ideas. However, none of the participants would be willing to managing the financial cost since they expect the organization to be responsible for such task (e.g. for collecting the money and to pay the insurance).

Participants were also asked about the **children's feeling**: they reported that all children had positive experiences with Families Share activities. In general, children felt happy and enthusiastic both before and after the activities and always felt part of the group. It is worth to mention that children did not report to parents any differences in having professional educators or other parents as minders.

Moreover, children felt safer since they knew parents were in the same building and this was perceived as a very positive aspect, except for older children (>11 years old). In general children are happy to be somehow part of the organization where their parents work, see their offices and get to know more about their parents' job. Parents' participation to the labs also make the children feel proud of their parents.

As far as the **safety** topic is concerned, only a child had a minor injury during the Summer Camp. The mother of the child reported that she was happy that the child was in her same building so she could take care of him/her. Therefore, having the possibility to intervene in case of children accidents is perceived as a positive aspect.

During the evaluation activities also the **social dimensions** was explored. Parents who took part revealed that at the moment they did not feel that a real “group” exists. However, they recognized the need to ensure a sort of continuity and relationships among the people taking part to the childcare activities, this would be important also for children even though it is necessary to identify the right way to manage the group.

The organization of childcare activities inside the workplace and the involvement of the employees as volunteers had a very positive impact for parents in terms of **trust**. Indeed, for them it is important to know the people who take care of their children. However, the peculiarity of the relationships that exist in a workplace also presents a darker side; indeed as a parent reported “if my child becomes friend of the child of a colleague with whom I had some problem, the situation is not easy to manage”.

Finally, as concerns the **gender dimension**, it is worth to make some preliminary considerations and underline that there was no balance among female and male employees involved in the childcare activities, indeed more female employees than male employees took part to the activities, even though at the organizational level (in FBK) the number of male employees is higher. Parents tended to run the activities in same-sex couples. Another aspect to be highlighted and be observed in future steps is the majority of male kids taking part to the Friday mini Labs where the STEM component is emphasized.

2.5 Venice City Lab

2.5.1 Background and previous steps at the Venice City Lab

The Venice City Lab was started up by the Smart Venice team, partner of the project. Three researchers formed the Families Share team as well as the City Lab community management.

The Venice City Lab has the feature to be spread on four different areas of Venice: Cannaregio in the main island, the Giudecca island, Marghera and Mestre in the mainland. In all the areas a number of activities were conducted from the beginning of the project for engaging stakeholders and parents to participate in the pilot activities.

While in the areas of Cannaregio, Giudecca and Marghera which were involved from the very beginning, parents were mainly interested in the organization of activities during holiday periods, in Mestre the interest in planning routine activities emerged.

As regards the socio-economical features of the four communities involved, in Giudecca and Cannaregio almost all parents are Italian or expats, with middle income and most of them already knew each other. In Marghera there is a great heterogeneity with parents having different nationalities, backgrounds and economic situations. About Mestre, the parents met are all Italian and their kids attend the same school.

The main strength of the Venice City Lab is represented by the collaboration with the Municipality of Venice, in particular of the Educational Services office. Indeed, from the very beginning of the project, the office showed to be very interested in the Families Share model and willing to support it, mainly in terms of dissemination and public spaces concession. The support of the Municipality consisted also in authorizing some municipal employees (seven people) to participate to project preparatory activities as part of their regular working hours. Thanks to this, the Families Share team collaborated with the coordinators and educators of three pre-primary schools of the areas involved: the pre-primary schools San Girolamo in Cannaregio, Duca D’Aosta in Giudecca and Nerina Volpi in Marghera. The mentioned schools represented, together with the municipality and some NGOs, the main stakeholders all around the preparation process.

In the needs assessment phase, stakeholders and parents were involved to present the project, identify similar childcare initiatives, as well as discuss about opportunities, needs, barriers and risks of the Families Share model, which was immediately perceived as potentially useful for families with few resources and time available, or in families where both parents work. However, educators/teachers played a crucial role in the community building process and raised the awareness of families about the values of reciprocity and solidarity which represent the basis of the project model.

Although many potentialities were identified, the project presented also some barriers and risks according to the people involved in the initial steps. In particular:

- the lack of trust among people, which can create resistances;
- the problem of delegations;
- insurance issues;
- cultural and intercultural barriers;
- the risk of poor reciprocity.

According to parents opinion, the Families Share model resulted to be useful both for the management of the families' daily routine (taking and picking up children from school, the management of extra school activities, school meetings, etc.) as well as the holiday periods (summer, winter, Eastern and Carnival holidays).

The two identified scenarios - management of daily activities and management of periods when schools are closed – were better explored during the co-design phase, where around 30 parents were involved.

The most relevant and useful outputs of the co-design phase were the followings:

- small groups of families are preferred;
- grandparents should not be involved, but eventually professionals, in case of need;
- info about children should be shared with the other members of the group, but health issues should be shared with group administrators only;
- a time banking system is not a good option;
- as regards spaces, public spaces are preferred.

All the outputs emerged during the initial steps of the City Lab were further discussed and analyzed during the preparatory activities leading to the pilot, in order to meet parents' needs at best. Indeed, as it will better explained in the next paragraphs, the Families Share team focused its efforts in the following processes:

- identification, with the support of the Municipality, of suitable public spaces for carrying out co-playing activities in the summer period and stipulation of an ad hoc formal agreement with the Municipality;
- engagement of group of families (max 10 families per area involved) and organization of meetings in order to co-organize the pilot activities and build trust among the participants;
- consultation and meetings with different insurance companies in order to identify the best solution;
- setting up of an NGO as a legal entity to deal with all bureaucratic issues.

2.5.2 Preparatory activities

The preparatory activities carried out by the Venice City Lab concerned numerous meetings and exchanges with stakeholders and parents in order to plan the pilot activities to be held in summer. Indeed, the purpose of the meetings was to set up 3 groups of parents, one for each of the communities where the need and interest of summer co-playing week arose (Cannaregio, Giudecca and Marghera), of around 8-10 adults, in order to co-play for one or two weeks during the month of July.

In total 23 and 6 face-to-face meetings were conducted with parents and stakeholders respectively. During the meetings, 48 parents and 16 people belonging to different entities/organizations were involved.

In this table a recap of the meetings carried out in the period February – June 2019 is done:

Period	Area(s)	Type of meeting	N. of meetings	Kind of participants	N. participants (FS team not included)	M/F rate	Topics
Feb-March	Giudecca, Cannaregio, Marghera, Mestre	Meetings with parents (bilateral and group meetings)	13	Parents (during some meetings also school staff was present)	23	18 F / 5 M	- project presentation and parents engagement - usability tests
Feb-March	Cannaregio	Meeting with stakeholder	1	School coordinator and educator	2	2 F	- project presentation and space availability
Apr-May	Marghera, Giudecca, Cannaregio	Meetings with parents	4	Parents and school educators/coordinators	21	15 F / 6 M	- project dissemination and parents engagement
Apr-May	Giudecca	Meeting with stakeholder	2	One meeting with School coordinator and educator. One meeting with UNIPOL SAI (7 people present) in Bologna	9	1 M / 8 F	- pedagogical tips - insurance issues
June-July	Cannaregio, Marghera	Meetings with parents	5	Parents	16	4 M / 12 F	- pilot preparation
June-July	Cannaregio	Meeting with stakeholder	1	Municipal employee and two parents	3	3 F	- pilot preparation and space rules

Table 11. Preparatory activities in the City Lab of Venice

In general, families involved through the project were composed by two parents and have one or two children each. Most of them could not benefit from the support of grandparents for the childcare, since they are not originally from Venice but from other Italian cities or from abroad. They were interested in Families Share for a number of reasons, in particular:

- the opportunity to create a network among parents and therefore to meet new people;
- the possibility to save money and time for childcare and to have more free time;
- the willingness to spend more quality time with their children offering them a “non-standard” summer activity;
- the opportunity to increase parenting skills;
- its social innovation component.

The meetings with parents were meant, at the beginning, to inform them about the Families Share project and eventually engaged them for the first pilot. Motivated partners were asked to spread the word about the project in order to find other interested parents to start piloting with. Indeed, word of mouth was found to be the most effective way for people to approach the project. The meetings took place mainly at the pre-primary schools’ premises, generally with the presence of the school coordinator and one or more educators.

In some cases meetings were held in places which were supposed to host pilot activities in the summer. This was useful for the involved parents and allowed them to start familiarizing with the space.

At a later stage, meetings with parents and stakeholders were organized for concretely planning the pilot activities as well as for engaging new parents in case of “last minute” withdrawals. During these meetings everyone was allowed to express their time availabilities and to propose activities to be done with the children. Discussions took place on daily schedules and possible parents’ roles. The Families Share staff also introduced the platform to all parents and explained how to use it. In the last meetings, rules and guidelines for the piloting week were presented by community managers and parents were invited to join the ad hoc founded NGO “Families Share a.p.s.”²⁰, by filling a module and providing the membership fee.

Parents were all contacted through Facebook, e-mails, individual calls and messages. At a later stage, when the parents groups were formed in the different areas, Whatsapp groups were created, in order to facilitate and speed up communication among group’s members.

Several issues were faced by the Families Share team during the preparatory phase. One of the most relevant concerned the **spaces** where to carry out the pilot activities. Indeed, already from the initial steps taken into the project, the importance to have the availability of public spaces where to run the activities emerged. The availability of the Municipality of Venice to support the pilot by assigning some municipal places (pre-primary schools or play centers) represented a great help in this sense. However, some issues and conflicts arose in the process from the side of a few teachers and other school staff members in some sites. In particular, several concerns were expressed such as:

- possible damage of the school’s equipment, as well as on the use of the school as a space for extra-scholastic activities;
- children attending the school could have been exposed to different ‘rules’ during the co-playing period and this would have affected the teachers’ work for the following school year;
- parents not being apt at taking care of kids with an ‘educational’ or coordinating role, especially when their own kids are involved, risks related to injuries and potential lawsuits from one family against the other.

Such perceptions didn’t favour the communication towards parents in some of the neighborhoods, although in general a supportive environment was met among teaching and support staff at schools.

- The final venues identified as suitable and made available by the Municipality and/or School managers were “Palladio” middle school in Giudecca (unused space since the school was closed last year);
- Nerina Volpi kindergarten in Marghera;
- Play Center La Cicala e la Formica in Cannaregio.

Another crucial issue still related to spaces, is **insurance**. Indeed, the Municipality soon clarified that pre-requisites for accessing all municipal spaces for free, were the setting up of a formal agreement between a legal entity and the Municipality, aimed at excluding the Administration from any liabilities and the stipulation of an appropriate insurance to cover all participants (from injuries and civil liability). In this regard, parents had already expressed in previous meetings they were not available to set up their own NGO to make this possible, partly due to a lack of time but mostly for not being willing to take the responsibility up. Therefore, the Families Share team decided to establish a new volunteering NGO themselves. The entity was founded in June also thanks to the support of the local “Centre for volunteers” (Centro Servizi Volontariato)

²⁰ See more information on the NGO later on in the present paragraph.

which helped the team in setting the NGO under the new Third Sector Reform (Legislative Decree n. 117/2017).

After some consultations with different insurance company an insurance policy was stipulated with UnipolSAI (project advisor) and all parents taking part to the pilot were asked to join the association in order to be covered by the insurance (a membership fee of 20 euro was also asked in order to cover the insurance costs). The NGO is managed by the Smart Venice staff, and has one representative from UNIVE and two parents involved in the first pilot as founding partners.

Another relevant issue that emerged during the preparatory phase dealt with the **involvement of parents** in the different areas. Indeed, parents involved can be “categorized” as follow:

- a) parents who participated to informative meetings (both after being informed through the Facebook page “Families Share City Labs”, posters or word of mouth) showed enthusiasm towards the project and took part to the pilot activities;
- b) parents who participated to informative meetings, showed enthusiasm towards the project but finally decided not to take part to the pilot activities,
- c) parents who participated to informative meetings but did not like the Families Share approach.

Parents who withdrew did it for different reasons:

- a sudden real impossibility to take part to the activities, due to work loads or holiday reasons;
- lack of trust among parents and not enough time for getting to know each other properly;
- children groups with different age ranges;
- a few parents were already in the process of setting up on payment after school creative activities for kids and were not available in establish a synergy with the project as it was clarified the main scope was to have free of charge childcare activities based on parents volunteering;
- some parents started to be afraid of not of being able to reach the minimum number of families to start the pilot, others perceived the Families Share model as too demanding in terms of personal time to dedicate and skills needed to entertain children for a day or half a day.

The latter was also one of the motivation for parents for not finding the project interesting from the beginning (group c) together with a general worry in not being able to take care to others children and a lack of trust towards the other parents.

On the basis of the parents expressed concerns, the pedagogical coordinators were consulted in order to have some tips/guidelines to transfer to parents with reference to:

- co-playing in a group in which his/her own child/children is present;
- the children conflict management;
- the importance of being patient when dealing with children;
- the importance to set some rules at the beginning of the experience and to have some “rituals” during the day (welcoming, lunch, goodbyes);
- the mutual respect as a fundamental value of the entire experience;
- the opportunity to involve some older children as young assistants;
- the importance of sharing any info about children’s allergies/ intolerances/ health problems.

It is worth to mention that one family with a child with disabilities got in contact with the Families Share team expressing the willingness to participate to the pilot activity in Cannaregio. The child would have been accompanied by an educator. Unfortunately the family had to withdraw its participation since the educator was not available for the selected week.

In spite of the efforts for involving more parents, the minimum number of 10 families was not reached in all the areas, this was also due to some “last minute” withdraws. Therefore, the community managers decided to merge the groups of Cannaregio and Giudecca and to carry out one pilot at the Play Centre in Cannaregio and the other one in Marghera. This was made possible only because a Families Share team member, who was also a volunteering parent, offered to bring and pick children up from Giudecca to Cannaregio every day (30 minutes by public transport), as proximity of the activities to home is an important pre-requisite for families.

Also in Marghera some last minute withdraws discouraged the group a bit, and two mums decided their children would attend for the mornings activities only., as the group was too small.

Just before the starting of the activities in Cannaregio and Marghera parents were invited to meet the officers in charge of the two places. During these meetings, the use of the space, rules, safety regulations as well as cleaning were discussed.

The summer activities were not the only ones to be explored. Indeed, a group of parents living in Mestre, in the mainland, got in contact with the Families Share team showing a lot of enthusiasm towards the project but mainly with reference to routine activities (i.e. taking children to and back to/from school). The Families Share team took contact with their primary school in Mestre, in order to explore the opportunity to start a collaboration. A formal meeting is expected to take place in September.

Also the opportunity to start after-school activities emerged during the preparatory meetings and it will be also better explored starting from September.

2.5.3 Pilots

Picture 4. Images of the Venice pilot

In the following table the features of the two pilot actions in Venice are shown.

	Number of involved parents and M/F ratio	Number of other involved adults (non parents volunteers, educators, coordinators etc)	Number of involved children	Age (divided in the 2 groups 3-6/7-11) and sex of the children	Duration	Type of Activity
Action 1 – Co-playing week in Cannaregio	TOT:12 7 F 5 M	1 volunteer of the civil service was supporting parents in some of the morning activities	13	3-6 years old: 7 7-11 years old: 6 8 M	5 days	Co-playing week, self- managed by parents, it was organized like a summer camp, with two main laboratories organized by parents (one in the morning and

				5 F		one in the afternoon). Every parent/family covered 2 half day or 1 entire day.
Action 2- Co-playing week in Marghera	TOT: 7 5 F 2 M	2 community managers participated with a lab	8	3-6 years old: 5 7-11 years old: 3 6 M 2 F	5 days	Co-playing week, self- managed by parents, it was organized like a summer camp, with two main laboratories organized by parents (one in the morning and one in the afternoon). Every parent/family covered 2 half day or 1 entire day.

Table 12. Features of pilot activities in the City Lab of Venice

As concerns the co-playing week in **Cannaregio**, it was hosted by the play-center “La cicala e la formica” in Villa Groggia, Cannaregio and took place during the second week of July. Participants could use one big room of the play-center, the toys corner in the main room and the garden. The features of the venue was facilitating for parents: the Play Centre was open almost all day, its toys, books and materials were available, a volunteer was available to support (although her help was not really needed in practice), and cleaning was partly performed by the routine cleaning service of the centre. Thanks to the nice weather during the whole week, the majority of activities were run in the garden.

Parents were fully involved in the organization of the week structure as well as in its educational contents. Indeed, all of them contributed to the co-play week through specific labs and activities. The day was divided in two, having two parents co-playing in the morning and other two in the afternoon.

Everyday started with a welcoming and free play moment, followed by a snack break. One or two arts & crafts labs were held per day, one in the morning and one in the afternoon, free play and reading aloud sessions complemented .

Participants had similar middle highly educated socio-economic background. Some of them self-employed, some other employed in the educational or public sector, just few of them unemployed. One mother was native from Croatia and another one from Canada, whereas the others were Italian but mostly coming from different cities/regions. None of them were single parents. They joined the pilot mainly in order to try a different experience and create a new network of parents.

The time dedicated by parents to the co-playing week was balanced, every parent/family dedicating one full day or two half-days. Some parents gave more time spontaneously, supporting parents in charge during their labs. In most cases, only one parent per family took part to the co-playing week, except for two families where both parents participated giving half-day each. It is worth to mention that one person of the community management (Families Share team) was also a volunteering co-playing parent during the experience.

No conflicts or big issues emerged during the pilot activities. Both parents and children, as it will be better explained in the following paragraph were enthusiastic about the experience and wish to repeat it soon.

Regarding the pilot in **Marghera**, the activities took place at the pre-primary school “Nerina Volpi”, also during the second week of July. Participants could use a big room, the dining hall as well as the garden. Also in Marghera thanks to the nice weather, most of the activities were run in the garden.

The structure of the co-playing week was the same as in the Cannaregio, with parents fully involved in the organization of the week and in the ideation of the activities/labs.

From the socio-economical point of view, participating parents had different backgrounds and personal situations. 4 of them were Italian, whereas 3 had a migrant background (they were originally from

Bangladesh, Colombia and Serbia). They were all employed except for one mum who was unemployed. One participant was a single parent. In general, they joined the pilot for saving money and creating a new network of families.

Differently from the Cannaregio pilot, co-playing parents were less than 10, therefore, some timeslots were not fully covered. For this reason, and in order to ensure the feasibility of the pilot, the community management supported in conducting a lab and taking care of the children during one of the afternoons. However, in general the time dedicated by parents to the co-playing week was quite balanced, every parent/family generally dedicating one full day or two half-days. Mostly, only one parent per family took part to the co-playing week, except for one family where both parents participated. A couple of parents was present during the whole week in order to support the others in managing their child which had some relational problem and was not easy to involve him in the different activities. It is worth to highlight that the unemployed parent, during the course of the week, decided to dedicate more time than the one she initially planned, since she was happy about the experience and liked to spend time with the children instead of staying at home.

Although parents had different backgrounds and educational approaches, no conflicts or issues happened. As concerns the use of the platform, in both actions the community management introduced it to the parents and undertook also the role of group administrators by creating the group and the activities. All the parents, except one, downloaded the app, created their profiles and their own children's profiles. They inserted their availability in the different time-slots and added children to the activities too. In order to let them insert labs ideas and descriptions, they were all upgraded as group administrators. No big issues emerged in the use of the platform, however some parents complained for not having been able to insert her child or having some bugs. A parent joined the platform very late, just before the starting of the experience, and this was perceived as very annoying by the other parents.

Timeslots planned through the platform were respected during the real pilot in both experiences. In a few cases there was a change in the labs carried out which was not updated in the app.

The app was mainly used during the preparatory phase, to set the activities and the timeslots, however some parents used it also during the pilot to check who was co-playing that day, which activities were planned and how many children were present. More detailed information about the use of the app in both the actions will be provided in Part III.

During the piloting week, parents communicated both face-to-face and through the WhatsApp group. The face-to-face communication mainly happened at the beginning or at the end of the day and they were related to organizational issues (for instance of the keys exchange). Through the Whatsapp group, parents were instead exchanging insight and opinions on the experience trend and pictures of the activities. The chat function of the app was not used.

As concerns the community management role, as already mentioned, it was assumed by the Families Share team. Its function was to deal with all the bureaucratic tasks, set up the groups of co-playing parents and facilitate and supervise all the process before and during the activities. In particular, the community management was in charge of:

- checking parents' shifts;
- managing the communication among the group;
- setting up the new NGO;
- managing insurance issues and stipulating related documents;
- stipulating the agreement with the Municipality of Venice for the use of public spaces;
- social media and communication;

- supporting and guiding the parents in the use of the app/platform.

2.5.4 Results from evaluation in Venice

After the conclusion of the pilot some evaluation activities were conducted in both the communities. All parents taking part to the co-playing week in Cannaregio participated in a final focus group, whereas 5 of the parents co-playing in Marghera carried out 5 individual interviews.

During the evaluation activities many dimensions were explored. At first, families were asked to explain the reasons for joining the families share pilot. The main reasons emerged were:

- saving money;
- feeling helpful and in solidarity with others;
- creating a network of families and therefore making new friends;
- the willingness to support the Families Share's study;
- experimenting something new;
- having the possibility to spend some quality time with the children.

According to all the parents, it was fundamental to have the support of the community managers in issues regarding the insurance and the agreement with the Municipality, since they would have perceived such duties as obstacles not easy to overcome and it would have affected the realization of the pilot. All of the parents agreed on the fact that the place where the activities were conducted was suitable, especially having, in both cases, a big garden to use.

In general, parents were very satisfied and enthusiastic about the experience. Some of them declared they felt the experience helped them to give their best, especially during the labs. Parents did not pointed out big criticalities due to the presence of their own children during the activities. Only one parent claimed her child was not behaving well when she was present.

Children, on their side, felt very happy about taking part to the co-playing week. Parents reported the children were every day thrilled and excited and, in general, felt happier when their own parents were co-playing. Indeed, children were looking forward having their parents co-playing and felt proud about the labs the parents carried out. Also the smaller children were very happy in participating to the co-playing week. According to parents opinion the fact that there was a small number of children and that only parents were co-playing helped a lot in this sense.

The daily parents turnover was positively perceived by the children. Parents argued that in a traditional summer camp the continuous changing of educators would not have been perceived in the same way.

The most relevant positive aspects of the experience underlined by the parents interviewed are:

- the variety and the innovativeness of the activities compared to a traditional summer camp;
- the familiar environment and the positive energy and creativity of the parents;
- the possibility to save money;
- the creation of a new community and the new friendships;
- the opportunity to enter in contact with people with different backgrounds and personalities and break any initial prejudices;
- the opportunity to spend quality time with the children;
- the very good relationships among children;
- the opportunity to learn parental skills from the other participants;
- the enthusiasm of children;
- the flexibility.

A few negative aspects were mentioned during the focus group and the interviews:

- some parents felt a bit of concern before the starting of the activities;
- for one parent participating to the pilot was a bit demanding in terms of time and efforts;
- sometimes the day program was a bit too dense;
- there was not much time for team building among parents before the experience;
- the last minute withdraws;
- some different educational visions emerged but this did not create any conflicts. A parent suggested to involve an educator;
- the fact that some of the parents were late in inserting their availabilities in the app;
- the duration of the activities (some parents perceived it as too short).

In general, parents trusted each other, even if some of them did not know each other before the pilot. However, in general, they would have preferred having more time to know each other for enhancing reciprocal trust.

No specific roles were defined in the preparatory phase, since the community management dealt with most of the organizational issues. However, some parents spontaneously took some initiatives; for instance, checking the weekly timetable and reminding to parents to add their availabilities, listing things and materials needed, etc. Some parents pointed out that it would be useful in the future to set some responsibilities and roles according to the each competences and attitudes. In both actions there was no need for a petty cash since each parent shared materials and games had already at home.

In general, since children had different age range, smaller groups were created during the labs, in order to manage the labs according to the children different level of ability. Parents observed that the older children often felt responsible for the younger ones. Sometimes, they were also playing altogether during the free play moments.

Concluding, most of the parents were satisfied about the experience and wish to repeat it, also in different contexts (during the short school holidays like Christmas, Carnival and Easter holiday, before the beginning of the school in September, for routine activities like the so called “pedibus”, occasional shared childcare, as well as for after school activities). The piloting experience helped to create new friendships and a sense of community among the different families participating.

2.6 Hungarian City Lab

2.6.1 Background and previous steps at the Hungarian City Lab

The Hungarian City Lab has been coordinated until the end of 2018 by the Regional Environmental Center (REC) until when they had to leave the project consortium due to internal issues. Therefore, it was necessary for the project consortium to look for another Hungarian partner, with enough capabilities and expertise to continue with piloting in Hungary, and catch up at that a rather advanced stage of the project. The choice fell on Parents’ House Foundation²¹, under suggestion of one of the project’s advisory board member²², given their already established and consolidated network of parents in several Hungarian cities. However, until the end on 2018, REC kept contacting and engaging different stakeholders and parents’ networks, both from local and international organizations, mostly based in Budapest, such as Cargonoma, the Center of Monoparental families, with which they collaborated during some events, besides obtaining to have direct contact with their parents’ networks. They also participated in *FutureKids – Children’s EQ Pop-up Festival*²³,

²¹ <https://tegyeljot.hu/>

²² Eszter Salamon from the European Parents’ Association (<https://euparents.eu/>)

²³ The Pop-Up Festival is an international event organized by SixSeconds and UNICEF during the Children’s day (20th of November). For more information, please check the dedicated website <https://www.6seconds.org/popup/>

in collaboration with Jövő Gyermekéi and the SixSeconds international organization. Thanks to these collaborations, REC managed to conduct the needs assessment survey of Families Share (77 answers collected, 44 after data cleaning)²⁴ which confirmed need and interest from families and a good potential for the piloting in the Hungarian context.

The Parents' House Foundation is a cultural institution established in Hungary since 2007, which aims at supporting families in childcare provision and counselling, fostering community building and parents empowerment. It offers (full time/part time) childcare activities targeting children (aged 0-12).

The Parents House Foundation officially joined the project starting from May 2019. After a first month (May-June 2019) of internal meetings and preliminary assessments, it decided to move the City Lab from Budapest, to the smaller but more innovative city of Győr. It is indeed in this last city that Parents' House can count the bigger community of families involved in their activities (2500 families reached per year, among which 500 families in need²⁵). In addition, this choice was facilitated by the fact that in Győr there is a high number of young families, considered to be more "open-minded" and likely to be interested in the project. The city is an important centre of cultural life and it is one of the most dynamic of Hungary. In the last few years, Győr started to focus on city's innovation and smart solutions, therefore numerous projects financed by EU programs are being developed in the city until now. In fact, Győr Parents' House center is also involved in another relevant project aimed at supporting employment and work life balance, within the framework of Human Resources Development Operational Programme, funded by the ESF and ERDF, where synergies with Families Share can be leveraged.

In joining the Families Share project, Parents' House Foundation aimed at overcoming different problems they are witnessing in the Hungarian childcare sector, mostly related to difficulties for parents to afford the private offer, due to economic reasons (unemployment, single parents, lack of a network of support). The childcare sector is also facing the issue of the lack of spaces for day-care, especially for 0-3 years old children. In addition, childcare roles are highly gendered, in general seen as a "mothers' task", it is therefore difficult for them to reach an appropriate work-life balance, especially for single mothers.

Another obstacle to the increase of childcare offer in Hungary is given by the current regulation (20/2017. IX. 18) of the Ministry of Human Resources, which states that a person who provides day-care services for kids, must complete a 100-hours training course, with a secondary education as a minimum requirement to access. Nevertheless, this and other regulations regarding education are currently under reform, due to the creation of a new national plan for education in Hungary, which foresees to centralize the educational sector, in order to handle the current issue of missing spaces and formal education for children in preschool age. The Parents' House is dealing with this problem, by offering formal childcare to children from 0 to 3 and a number of other activities for children up to 12. In this respect, the Families Share model can be seen as a possible solution for parents of smaller children who are looking for cheap childcare solutions as well as for a community of support in dealing with such task since it can help them in getting in touch and self-organizing childcare activities.

²⁴ These data are collected and described in D1.3 "Behavioral mapping and engagement toolkit for Families-Share", section 3, pp. 33-41

²⁵ They identifies as main problems related to families: income inequalities; separation of mothers, children and families; low level of social acceptance of minorities; gender inequality; educational inequalities.

2.6.2 Preparatory activities

From May 2019 the Hungarian City Lab has been involved in different introductory meetings and communication both with the project lead partner, and with the WP3 leader, to start working on the pilot preparation, the needed documents, and scenarios.

Following the decision to move the City Lab from Budapest to Győr, two meetings were held:

- Internal meeting at the Győr Parents' House Family Centre (26th of June) for project/platform presentation, definition of details for the forthcoming pilot, to be hosted in the Family Centre venues, communication strategy to reach out to parents (newsletter to be sent by email to all the families registered in Parents' House database).
- Open meeting with parents (4th of July at the Parents' House Family Centre in Győr), with 4 parents, 8 children, and 2 childcare professionals attending. The community manager presented the project and the app, that parents downloaded and surfed to explore its main functionalities. During this meeting motivations to join Families Share were discussed, and parents reported the following reasons:
 - willingness to build a network of parents;
 - need of having some support in childcare;
 - curiosity to be part of a social innovation solution for time- and care-sharing.

The participating parents were all middle-class with an age range between 34 and 41. Among the 4 that attended the meeting, 2 were unemployed while the other 2 were full-time employees; they were all females and 1 was a single mother.

The Győr Parents' House employees reacted in a positive way at the proposal to host the project in their space, since they considered it as a good opportunity for parents in need for creating a network of support. Limited space was available for the piloting due to already planned and ongoing Summer Camp activities already organized by the Győr Parents' House Foundation during the same days: Families Share co-playing activities were therefore organized in late afternoons (from 4 pm to 6 pm) and engaged families whose kids were not already attending the Summer Camp. This choice had an impact on the number of participants, since the parents' working hours were not covered by the pilot and volunteering in childcare sharing was not that much useful/effective for them, if not for social networking purposes. In addition, the community managers did not have much time to promote the activity for obvious time shortage reasons (i.e the newsletter for promoting the project activities was sent only 1 week and a half before the starting of the pilot) and childcare organization is usually set up well in advance by parents.

2.6.3 Pilots

Picture 5. Images of the Győr pilot

The Győr City Lab decided to conduct the pilot activities spread in four different afternoons along 2 weeks. Originally, it should have covered these time-slots:

1. 4th July 2019 (17.00-19.00) – after the preparatory meeting with parents
2. 8th July 2019 (16.00-19.00)
3. 10th July 2019 (2 activities – one in the morning [10.00-13.00]; one in the afternoon [16.00-18.00])
4. 15th July 2019 (16.00-19.00)

Unfortunately, the City Lab had to cancel the two activities planned for the 10th of July given to a viral disease that affected 3 out of the 4 participating families, and it was not even possible to find another date available for all the families to make up the missed one.

The 4 parents that participated were all females while the children were 5 females and 3 males, from 2 to 10 years old.

The 4 parents participated altogether in almost all the afternoons (one parent and her children could not attend one afternoon), and they were helping the community manager and two educators in managing their children. The choice to involve educators in the pilot was made by the community managers in order to attract more people in joining it, given the short time at their disposal to properly present the project. In this respect, the pilot was not fully organized through the concept of sharing childcare, but the City Lab aimed at parents' community building in this first phase, by giving them the tools and the possibility to know the Families Share model in view of using it in the next round of piloting activities. Indeed, at the end of the pilot, parents were already discussing on the possible use of the app for self-organizing some events at the end of August or during the next Fall school holidays.

Along with the preparation of the pilot, the community manager set up and created the activities in the Families Share app. However, the app had a technical issue on the same days and, even if it was immediately fixed, none of the parents was able to add their availability to the planned activities. Also, the app functionalities are designed to be useful whenever parents play a truly active role in managing and organizing childcare activities, which was not the case in this first experiment, as mentioned. Therefore, although they all downloaded it and registered their personal profile, its usage was extremely partial.

For what concerns insurance issues, the Győr City Lab conducted the piloting activities within the Parents' House spaces, which are covered by an *ad hoc* insurance and meet the requirements of the related national regulations.

2.6.4 Results from evaluation in Hungary

The Győr City Lab organized one focus group and four individual interviews with all the participating parents, in order to investigate their perceptions on the pilot and on the app (although limited), and to explore future possible scenarios of implementation of Families Share in Győr.

Parents confirmed the impressions and motivations expressed during the preparatory meetings:

- they liked to be part of a ‘social experiment’.
- they appreciated the possibility **to build a supporting network** in their neighborhoods in order to release the stress of all the responsibility of childcare, that in the Hungarian society is usually all on mothers. The perceptions is the Families Share model and app would help them to feel less alone and more in contact with other parents that are facing their same difficulties.
- they stated that they could **save time and energies** if they feel they can count on someone’s help, in case of need.

All the parents reported a positive experience during the pilot, both for them and for their children, who really enjoyed the activities and the fact that their mothers were present in the same place, playing with them. The peaceful environment and the small group were all facilitating elements in creating connections.

Parents stress also the **criticalities** in running the pilot:

- the malfunctioning of the app that did not allow them to really try it during the pilot
- the choice of the piloting period, causing such a little number of participants.

Still, the **emerging picture is quite promising**: all the parents were enthusiastic about the idea of having an app for managing their childcare in a community, mainly because they don’t want to use the other social medias any longer. They feel indeed that they are not safe in adopting Facebook, for instance, because of privacy issues (they do not feel their privacy is respected). Having a ‘clean’ tool to manage childcare and community’s relationships is seen as a great and a promising opportunity.

Concerning **trust issues**, all the parents were sure they could trust each other, and they felt honored by being trusted by the other as well. They stated that the choice of the location helped them a lot in the decision to join. This is because some of them already knew Parents’ House and they always had positive experiences with it: this was an added value that made them more confident in their decision to join the pilot. While in this specific case all the parents were present during the activities, they stated that they would be totally confident with the idea of covering shifts for co-playing with the children, even without the presence of professional educators.

2.7 Kortrijk City Lab

2.7.1 Background and previous steps at the Kortrijk City Lab

The Kortrijk City Lab represents a peculiar case within the Families Share City Labs, given its already well-established co-playing model before the starting of the project. Since 2016, De Stuyverij, a no profit organization, in charge of the management of the Kortrijk City Lab, has developed bottom-up solutions for parents interested in shared childcare possibilities. They managed to reach up to now almost 50 groups of parents who are co-playing in 25 different Belgian cities. Their approach, named Cokido, is based on the participation of parents in all the processes of creating the group and following the formal steps to stipulate the agreement for starting a co-playing group. In this way, the different parent’s groups reached a good level of autonomy that allows a collaborative and self-managed childcare.

Within the Cokido community, the **typical profile of co-playing parents** are those whose kids are attending the so called ‘*specifiek school methode*’. These schools are characterized by the ‘learning by doing’ as teaching methodology and promote the project-based learning, mostly within natural environment. They usually directly involve parents in their children educational activities, so they often have a more engaged

parents' group. In addition, another typical profile is represented by single mothers who are searching for a network of support, in order to better manage the school holidays. Most of the co-playing parents are women, but the community managers are witnessing a slowly increased presence of men in the childcare activities as well.

In 2018, De Stuyverij engaged different **stakeholders** and parents for conducting the needs assessment and the co-design of the Families Share platform. The engaged stakeholders were local governments, companies, organizations working with families or people in vulnerable situations, and sharing platforms, among which feedbacks on the strengths and weaknesses of the Families Share model was investigated. What emerged, in terms of **social cohesion**, was **the advantage given by Families Share to build up a community of parents** who could live and recognize their neighbourhood as a social space, based on **mutual trust for creating a network of shared childcare**: to this respect, the helpdesk offered by De Stuyverij to parents' groups contributes to enhance trust. As it was well expressed in the Community Management Workshop report, organized by De Stuyverij, in Families Share "trust becomes the new currency"²⁶.

Flexibility of the work life balance solution, the possibility to save money on traditional childcare services available during holidays (expensive and often employing teenagers as educators) and the possibility for parents to spend time with their own children were also highlighted as important.

A fundamental stakeholder are public schools. In fact, every new group of parents is usually coming from a specific school, in which a first Cokido info session is organized. It is then the group of parents interested in co-playing that creates a first contact with the school headmaster for signing the agreement to use the school spaces for the co-playing activities. This agreement has a double strength and win-win feature for both parties: from one side, parents have at their disposal a safe and child-friendly space, from the other, the school is not left empty during the holidays period.

During the needs assessment phase, both stakeholders and parents pointed out different issues and **possible barriers**. Families Share is seen as a great opportunity, but also as a risk, especially for what concerned **safety issues**: a first aid course and an insurance policy need to be made available in order to avoid difficult situations. **Cultural differences**, that are reflected in educational models, could also create some issues between parents. Many of them reported that they would not co-playing with unknown parents, since there is the need of having a basis of trust among the different members of the group, and a shared idea of educational models. The possibility to build up a sense of trust and community before the starting of the co-playing period was perceived as fundamental for a good outcome of the experience. This indicates how social networking functionalities of an app/platform might play a limited or indirect role only.

The Kortrijk City Lab conducted the **co-design workshop** in April 2018, in order to collect inputs from different groups of parents, about the additional functionalities for a platform able to support co-playing activities²⁷. A workshop was organized using the SUNA method²⁸ (Van Helvert & Fowler, 2003), namely the Scenario-based User Needs Analysis, proposing asking participants to evaluate their already existing and partially developed COKIDO platform under different proposed scenarios, and to identify new needs and features, to be added to the Families Share platform.

These results have represented a useful starting point for the development of the Families Share platform and have shed light on the needs of co-playing parents after reaching a certain level of experience in it. Some of them were already added in the Beta version of the app, while others will be taken into account as future

²⁶ The workshop took place between the 4th and 5th of September 2018 in Kortrijk, Belgium. It was directed to the other Families Share City Labs. For more information about the discussed issues, please visit <https://www.families-share.eu/index.php?mact=News,cntnt01,detail,0&cntnt01articleid=9&cntnt01returnid=73>

²⁷ De Stuyverij based the co-design on their an already existing in-house COKIDO platform, upon which the Families Share app was designed and developed.

²⁸ Van Helvert, J., and Fowler, C., (2003) 'Scenario based User Needs Analysis', Chimera Working Paper 2003-02. Colchester: University of Essex. Available on <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/a26e/b920937e9d45959b58643431afaba9d08498.pdf>

improvements for the second release, based as well on the results of the evaluation activities of the first pilot, described in detail in Part 3 of this report.

The Belgian City Lab is indeed featured by a **strongly developed social innovation model** featured by high levels of acceptance and autonomy by parents **whereas the most challenging part is now to introduce the digital innovation component**: self-organized groups of parents schedule their childcare shifts for co-playing using *ad hoc* tools and spreadsheets (see Par. 2.7.2) provided by the De Stuverij community managers, and don't feel really comfortable in changing, while the Families Share app was made available to them after they already finalized their planning schedules for the Summer co-playing activities. Furthermore, expectations from parents toward further digital supporting tools are now higher after the recalled test and partial development of the in house COKIDO app.

2.7.2 Preparatory activities

Cokido had the idea of sharing childcare between families already 4 years ago, starting with only one group in Kortrijk. From then they grew quickly, up to reaching 50 groups of parents adopting co-playing solutions in 25 different cities. This model had immediately a big success in Belgium, and this has demanded a rapid adaptation of organizational tools from the community managers, in order to continuously have a high rate of satisfaction by the growing co-playing groups. After several tries, the community managers have developed some step by step guidelines for the new groups to get organized, and the process is following the structure illustrated below.

Figure 20. Co-playing group start up process

The group starts organizing about 3 months before with the planning phase and parents cover all the needed roles in the group by themselves (calendar setting and planning the co-playing, finances, responsibility for the location, relations with De Stuyverij staff). The **following digital tools are used** (in italic, those whose functions are also covered by the current version of the Families Share app):

- *google sheet for each family to indicate the needed period for childcare and availability of each parent to co-play.*
- *planning google sheet with co-playing shifts*

- *google sheet about the division of tasks that need to be performed/by whom along the co-playing period;*
- *a google sheet with all the families' information and numbers to contact each other;*
- financial report where they indicate the amount that every family has to pay to cover the rent of the school, and the cost of the shared material or tools. The total amount per family is also related to the quantity of time a parent co-plays and on the total number of the days he/she brought the child to the activities;
- sheet for keeping track of details of the days (co-playing parents, number and age of children, time of arrival, and other extra information).
- *WhatsApp group for on-time communication, sharing pictures etc.*

Indeed, the most relevant issue faced by DeStuverij in piloting the Families Share approach with different groups of parents was about their **reluctance in using the Families Share app**, perceived as useless after having already learned how to efficiently run co-playing activities with the existing tools. To recap, three main factors were impacting at this level:

- misalignment between the Families Share 2nd release and the Cokido parents planning (all co-playing schedules for summer holidays already set by May);
- already existing and well known/tested set of digital tools with same functionalities as the ones from the Families Share app (and featuring even additional extra functions not covered in Families Share yet)
- high expectations linked to the previous and partially tested COKIDO app (before Families Share project).

De Stuverij reckons that the Families Share app would need to be further developed in order to include all the different functionalities not covered yet, in order to be perceived as useful by Cokido's parents.

In order to enrich the possibilities to shared childcare solutions, in the last period (between June and July 2019), Cokido community managers had three meetings with different **external stakeholders**, in order to set some partnerships useful to co-playing parents:

- De Gezinsbond²⁹, a big no profit organization for families that provide different childcare support (baby-sitters database, discount for children's stores, holydays camps, and so on). Possible synergies to increase the number of co-playing parents were discussed, reachable through De Gezinsbond's community.
- Refu Interim³⁰, an employment office for refugees who are looking for places where they can volunteer. They managed to have some refugees collaborating in co-playing activities with one group for 5 days in July 2019. This collaboration was perceived positively from the parents, who received an extra help in co-playing activities, and it was surely a step forward for refugees' social inclusion, who had the possibility to enter in contact with local families and networks.
- Bsit³¹, an application to find babysitters, in order to investigate how they can work together in case a group needs to have an extra adult for covering a co-playing shift.

²⁹ For more information, visit <https://www.gezinsbond.be/>

³⁰ <https://www.refuinterim.be/>

³¹ <https://bsit.com/>

2.7.3 Pilots

Picture 6. Images of the Kortrijk pilot

Being the Kortrijk City Lab really peculiar with respect to the others, it is not possible to individualize and describe a specific pilot experience occurred in the project first piloting period (M13-M20): in fact, most of the groups started to co-play different months or even years before, and in 2019 different new groups were formed (8 new groups already at the end of May).

Between the different groups it is possible to list some common features in their **co-playing model**, even though it can slightly vary. Normally, co-playing periods occur during the **school holidays** (spring, Easter, summer, fall, and Christmas) with a **full-day schedule** (usually from 8am to 5pm according to the groups' needs), and **hosted in public schools**. The group of parents plan their co-playing days together, with inputs from all the participants.

They have some fixed rules they comply with:

- co-presence of at least 2 parents;
- children must be in school age (from 2,5 to 10 years old);
- co-playing carried out in public and child-friendly spaces.

These rules are needed to have the co-playing activities covered by the Cokido co-playing insurance.

Insurance and all the support/helpdesk offered by the De Stuyverij team are made available to parents based on their membership fee (30€ x participating family).

During a usual co-playing day there is a balance between structured activities organized by parents (like creative laboratories) and moments of free play. This is an interesting mix and children usually really enjoy it. The number of adults co-playing varied depending from the period: during the spring holidays in 2019, Cokido counted 95 adults and 187 children co-playing, while in summer holidays in 2019 they counted 11 groups of parents co-playing until July. Overall, the people involved in co-playing activities between June and July 2019 are 210 parents (170 F/ 40 M) and 315 children (158 F/ 157 M). Still, in spite of very high number adopters of the social innovation model, none of the parents of the groups used the app for organizing co-playing: starting to get organized before the release of the Families Share revised platform, therefore they found it not useful and redundant.

Experience from co-playing groups in the period, fully confirmed the feedback and opinions collected in previous stages and reported above in 2.7.2.

2.7.4 Results from evaluation in Kortrijk

The evaluation activities were carried out by community managers at the end of the June and July co-playing experiences with two different groups: 11 parents (9 F and 2 M) participated in the focus group, while 5 members of a different group (4 F and 1 M) were selected for individual interviews. At the end of the latter, a demonstration of the Families Share app was proposed and parents asked to register and test it.

During the focus group, parents agreed on the overall positive experience they are having with the Families Share model. They stated that organizing childcare by themselves is much easier than what they were expecting, and this makes them proud. They liked to be involved and they felt they are creating strong bonds with the other parents, while children are happy of the familiar environment created through the co-playing. Parents faced some difficulties as well, mainly in organizational issues, when there is the need to select the co-playing week(s) based on everyone's availability.

When interviewed individually, different parents reported similar opinions on the overall experience. Almost all of them had a negative idea of the traditional summer camps, both because they are usually run by teenagers and because the group of children is often too large; they did not perceive these traditional solutions offered an adequate environment for children. On the contrary, they felt they could trust better other parents, who are more experienced with children, and they perceived it as a safer environment. Moreover, in their opinion, children socialize better in small groups and they are all happy to attend. For instance, one parent used to co-play even if he did not really need it, since he is a teacher, just because his children loved it. In addition, parents could spend some good time with their children, because they were free to play with them. The economic reason was also important, even though not the main one, given that the Families Share model is cheaper than any other childcare solutions. Lastly, trust between parents comes automatically when a family decided to co-play. Indeed, a solid sense of trust has been developed between participants since the beginning of the experience.

Interviewed parents reported some organizational difficulties to fill the co-playing calendar on time, and they really perceive the necessity of having someone taking the leading role.

Planning was facilitated by a set of refined shared Google sheets (as explained above), thus all interviewed parents did not see the point for using the Families Share app at a stage when they already got organized. They liked the idea of organizing everything from an app, but in their opinion, the current version would need to be further developed to cover all the functions for what they have spreadsheet templates already in place.

2.8 Thessaloniki City Lab

2.8.1 Background and previous steps at the Thessaloniki City Lab

The Thessaloniki City Lab is coordinated by Ergani Center, partner of the Family Share project. The Families Share team and community management is composed by two employees of Ergani, one of which is also a co-playing parent.

The City Lab involves the area of the Sykies district, Municipality of Neapoli-Sykies in the northwest part of the Thessaloniki Metropolitan Area as well as part of the 2nd District of the Municipality of Thessaloniki. Sykies is a classic residential area of medium and lower classes families, whereas the east part of the 2nd District of the Municipality of Thessaloniki, situated in the center of the city, is a business and commercial area, which residents are lower and medium classes Greek citizens, as well as members of minorities.

The first steps taken by Ergani concerned a number of actions aimed at involving different stakeholders: local authorities, NGOs, citizens organizations, business organizations, primary schools and parents' associations. Therefore, various meetings were organized and interviews carried out in order to identify existing childcare initiatives, families' needs and opportunities of the Families Share project.

All the stakeholders, as well as the parents consulted through meetings, interviews and focus groups agreed that an organized self-help and self-support system could be an answer to the economic issues faced by Greek families nowadays, especially single parents. Indeed, in Greece, due to the economic crises, many families have low income and can hardly afford childcare services. Moreover, Families Share was seen as an opportunity also for families where both parents work.

According to opinion of the involved people, the Families Share model presents also some barriers especially regarding the trust among involved parents. Indeed, stakeholders proposed to organize special activities in order to overcome this barrier. Also insurance issues were discussed during the meetings as a critical aspect. Reciprocity was perceived as an important feature, however parents pointed out the need to manage it with a solidarity approach, according to each one's needs and capacities.

The Thessaloniki City Lab involved around 30 people in the co-design phase. Two scenarios were presented:

- a scenario situation concerning the management of every day routine: taking and picking up children to and from school and to and from their after school activities;
- a second situation concerning the organizing of additional education activities.

The opportunities and potential barriers identified during the needs assessment were confirmed. The most interesting outputs of the co-design regarded the identification of the schools as the most suitable places where to carry out activities with children as well as the opportunity to use the Families Share model also to exchange services among parents.

According to the results of the activities carried out in the starting up phase, efforts were put in the creation of collaborations with schools and other entities as well as in the engagement of families for the organization of pilot activities mainly consisting in afternoon educational activities for children in order to help the process of trust building.

The Thessaloniki piloting of Families Share has **two main and linked distinctive features: graduality and incrementality**. Due to **emerging trust issues raised by parents**, on one side experimenting with the social innovation model was given absolute priority over the digital innovation component. **The childcare sharing innovation model was also very gradually implemented** by itself, and all participating parents were present during the activities together with their own kids, therefore only partially delegating and entrusting other parents to take care of their own kids.

On the other side, and as a consequence, the **use of the app/platform was minimized in practice**, and the **pilot was more of a demonstration type**, rather than a use-focused one. Still, the pilot's results are promising, activities are still ongoing and planned for the upcoming months, and show potentials to progress in a fully-fledged adoption of both the social and the digital components of the Families Share models.

2.8.2 Preparatory activities

The preparatory activities carried out at the Thessaloniki City Lab were mainly aimed at building up possible future collaborations with some Associations/NGOs, schools as well as public authorities. Also, a number of meetings with parents took place in order to help them in the process of trust building.

In the following table all the events/meetings organized in the preparatory phase are listed.

Period	N. of meetings	Type of meeting	Type and number of participants	Topics
Feb-March 2019	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meetings with schools (nursery school of Eptapyrgiou, 4th, 10th, 8th primary schools of Sykies, 55th primary school of Thessaloniki), the Scout organization from Sykies and Neapoli. Dissemination events (University of Sykies and International Convention and Fair Center of Thessaloniki).	Schools and organization representatives, parents. 57 adults involved	Presentation of the project, discussion about potential collaborations
April-May 2019	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Informative meeting for families in April at Ergani premises. Informative day for parents during Mother's day. 	19 parents	Inform parents about the project and the application
June-May 2019	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meeting with parents for the organization of the pilot Meetings with stakeholders (Parent and Guardian Association of 55th Elementary School of Thessaloniki and "Sxedia stin Poli") 	3 parents 7 people of the stakeholders (president, vice president, treasurer, communication officer and 3 volunteers)	Pilot preparations and discussion for collaboration

Table 13. Preparatory activities at the Thessaloniki City Lab

At an initial phase, the Families Share model and app was presented to several schools (the nursery school of Eptapyrgiou, the primary school of Sykies, the primary school of Thessaloniki), to the Scout organizations of Sykies and Neapoli and to the Municipality of Neapoli Sykies during ad hoc events/meetings in which 57 adults were informed. Some of the meetings/informative events were combined with activities for children in order to make the participation more appealing for families. For instance, in one event, while parents were informed about the project, children were busy in exploring the aromatic and medical herbs of the Greek nature. This event took place at the International Convention and Fair Center of Thessaloniki. During the mentioned meetings new parents were informed about the project and possible new collaborations with stakeholders explored. The collaboration was discussed mainly in terms of dissemination of the project and implementation of the Families Share model in events/initiatives co-organized with schools and parents associations.

At a later stage, meetings were mainly directed to meet and engage parents in the pilot set up, demonstrating the app and its potential use. An event took place at the Ergani premises and involved 10 parents, some of whom part of the "Associations of parents and guardians of primary schools". The mentioned associations are spread in different schools all around Thessaloniki.

A larger event targeting parents was held during Mother's day at the Municipality of Neapoli Sykies, where 9 families took part. Still information about the project and the app were given to parents while children

were involved in parallel playing/educational activities. Also, parents were invited to start using the app by downloading it, creating their own profile, groups and activities.

The last events organized by the Thessaloniki City Lab before conducting the pilot concerned a meeting with parents for organizing the pilot itself taking place at the Ergani premises and two more meetings with the Parents and guardians association of the 55th Elementary school of Thessaloniki and with the NGO “Sxedia stin Poli” (Artistic Pedagogical Team). During those meetings the opportunity to start up a collaboration in the frame of the Families Share project, new ideas for activities for children and new ways of disseminating the project and the app were discussed to be held in September, with a similar model to the one adopted in the pilot which is described below. In particular, a dedicated event at the 55th Elementary school with the collaboration of the “Association of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants of Greece” was agreed and procedures to follow for the necessary permissions as well as the safety requirements were discussed. The Families Share platform will be used to schedule the activity and inform parents about it. During the activity the Families Share model will be adopted since parents already involved in previous co-playing activities will take care of all the children, while other parents will be informed about the project and children will attend the seminar. As concerned the type of people taking part to the mentioned preparatory activities, generally they were mostly Greek women, unemployed and single parents. Their interest in Families Share appeared to be twofold: from one point of view they need cheap childcare solutions due to economic constraints and from the other one they see in Families Share an opportunity to socialize with other families.

A general concern was expressed by parents and was related to the management and protection of personal data and data of the children inserted in the app. The issue of the protection of personal data represents the main concern of parents participating to the City Lab’s activities as it emerged will better explained in the dedicated section (3.6).

Parents and stakeholders were engaged mainly via face-to-face communications, but also through e-mails and chats.

2.8.3 Pilots

Picture 7. Images of the Thessaloniki pilot

The Thessaloniki City Lab carried out a pilot activity in the month of July consisting in 3 afternoons during which a group from 10 to 14 parents met and shared educational activities for children. Overall, 17 parents (15 families with one or two parents participating each) took part to the activities. 10 parents were present in all the three afternoons whereas other 7 parents joined only one afternoon. The majority of them were

female (14 out of 17). As concerns the children, 19 children participated in activities and team games (7 male and 12 female).

Parents taking part to the pilot activities had an age range from 30 to 55. As concerns their economic status, according to the information available, 5 of them were unemployed, one person had a part-time job whereas 7 were employed with a full time job. 4 people were single parents.

They were motivated to join the pilot since they saw in the Families Share model and the online platform a good opportunity to socialize and take part to an innovative form of shared childcare at a low budget.

The pilot activities were carried out in the center of Thessaloniki. Families together with one person of the Families Share team (community manager) met in a coffee shop located in a little square closed to the church "Dodeca Apostoloi". The square is a protected and safe space for children.

The activities lasted two hours per each afternoon and were structured as follow: while the children were involved in some activities and team games, with 3-4 parents looking after them, the remaining parents socialized and talked about possible future developments of the Family Share model and app.

Normally, parents rotated during the afternoon, with 3-4 parents staying with children for one hour and then changing. Since parents were not already familiar with app yet, at the beginning of each afternoon activity they agreed verbally on who of them would have taken care of the children that day, in order to guarantee a balance about the time spent by each parent with the children.

The pilot structure described above let the parents start familiarizing and trusting each other and experimenting the Families Share model gradually.

During the afternoon, children, divided in small groups, besides some free play and team games in the church's yard had the chance to do some cultural activities with the parents taking care of them, discovering the history of the orthodox church "Dodeca Apostoloi", an UNESCO world heritage monument.

While children were busy with the above mentioned activities, parents were free to spend some time socializing and talking. They all agreed on the potentialities of the Families Share model for organizing more structured childcare activities shared among the group starting from September. They had the chance, guided by the Families Share team, to test the app. Indeed, all the involved parents tested it, creating a profile for themselves and the children, starting up a group, setting activities and checking the calendar. 13 parents (out of 17) registered in the platform creating a profile and adding 15 children in total, while the rest learned about the platform but did not download it.

The role of the community management concerned the organization of the groups before the activities, whereas during the activities the person provided help during the discussions regarding future childcare activities and the app test. Two people covered the role of group administrators instead (one person of the Families Share team and one parent), by creating the group and the activities in the app.

The communications among the members of the group happened mainly through mobile phones, social media and in part also through the Families Share app, by consulting the calendar. The majority of the exchange happened among three of the members who transmitted the relevant information regarding date, time, duration and place of the activities to the other parents.

The Thessaloniki City Lab started to deal with the insurance issues but did not apply any insurance yet, since parents of children taking part to the activities were all present during the pilot.

2.8.4 Results from evaluation in Thessaloniki

After the pilot, some evaluation activities (focus group and interviews) were conducted by the Families Share team. 15 people took part to the mentioned evaluation activities, 11 females and 4 males.

Parents joined the Families Share project in part thanks to the other parents or friends advice and partly thanks to the dissemination events which took place during the preparatory activities. They were all curious about the social innovation features of the model and about the platform as well.

Overall, parents gave very positive feedbacks about the activities carried out. Most of the parents agreed that they felt helpful adopting the Families Share approach and could spend more time with the children. In general, they developed a sense of community during the experience and are willing to improve it with more future activities. The positive experience regarded all the three afternoons activities even though there were some differences according to the number of people participating and the kind of shared activities.

Most of the parents would have preferred a longer experience, since they found it useful. They mentioned the following positive aspects of the Families Share approach both in general and related to the specific experience they took part into:

- It lets them save time and money;
- It reduces parents' stress;
- It helps socializing;
- It helps creating and increasing the sense of community;
- Activities organized for children have good quality.

The topic of trust is a bit controversial according to the feedbacks received by the parents, since not all of them feel they can fully trust the other parents involved yet. However, none of them reported any conflicts arose during the pilot activities.

Parents felt that for the pilot activities responsibilities were equally divided among participants, even though group administrators had more work to do. Parents are in general willing to assume some responsibilities, but this would depend on the type of the activity and the number of participating children.

Children were also happy about the pilot experience. According to the parents' opinions, it is important for children to feel they belong to a group, it is a good way for improving their social skills. In general, children felt enthusiastic before joining the group; this was also due by the fact that most of the children already took part to previous activities with the same group of children so they already knew they would have fun. Indeed, children felt sad when the activity got over since they could not spend time with their friends anymore. Parents highlighted that children benefitted from the good relationship among the parents.

Most of the parents would like to repeat the experience also in other situations, for instance during other periods of holidays or for sport activities.

With regard to the role of the Families Share technology in the pilot, we can observe how it was kept marginal in the overall experience, to give priorities to piloting the social innovation model and overcome trust concerns. From the digital innovation point of view, Thessaloniki and can be defined more as a demonstration pilot than a fully use-focused pilot. Indeed, the organizational steps of the childcare sharing activities didn't benefit from the use of the platform as a facilitating tool, neither for planning/scheduling of shifts or for information sharing among participants. Nevertheless, in general, parents considered the platform as an useful and easy to use tool in perspective, since it allows to have immediate and fast feedback on the activities among participants. As it will be better explained in the dedicated section (3.6) parents confirmed the concern they showed during the preparatory meetings regarding sharing of personal data on the app/platform.

As regards the gender dimension the first piloting phase counted a small number of fathers taking part to the activities. Indeed, only 3 out of 17 participating parents were male. The community managers will work on these issues trying to engage more fathers in the upcoming pilot activities.

2.9 Hamburg City Lab

2.9.1 Background and previous steps at the Hamburg City Lab

The Hamburg City Lab was started by the Urbanista team as partner of the consortium. The area initially involved was the neighborhood of Harburg, which is a diverse district where people with different cultural and religious backgrounds live.

A number of stakeholders were involved from the initial steps, in particular some local authorities and other private organizations, parents networks included. Among the local authorities, the project was introduced to the Municipality of Hamburg which showed an initial interest in the Families Share model.

The Families Share project was promoted also through a cultural open space called “Kulturwohnzimmer”, holding activities for public participation and part of the urban development agenda of the district. In such space also project activities and workshops were held.

In the needs assessment phase, 7 face-to-face interviews with stakeholders and 17 interviews with parents were performed. During such interviews mainly mothers with a migrant background were reached.

In general, stakeholders and families perceived the Families Share project would have offered the following opportunities:

- It could help in covering the lack of exchange between private initiatives and institutions and integrate local resources;
- It could facilitate the exchange of knowledge on childcare experiences;
- It could support the integration process in multicultural environments.

Nevertheless, several barriers critical issues were identified:

- an risk of overload in care services and projects in Hamburg as well as possible competition with already ongoing initiatives;
- a general lack of use of digital technologies among the involved parents. Therefore, alternative ways of participation combining offline exchanges and the online tool were deemed necessary.
- reaching out parents represents a demanding task since it implies continuity and face to face invitations and reminders to participate in activities;

Regarding the co-design workshop, it involved both stakeholders and parents. During the workshop, six scenarios describing a variety of local situations and possible solutions were presented to participants.

During the workshop the following outputs emerged:

- lots of parents were already connected informally (e.g. via Whatsapp groups) and they did not see how an online platform could help them;
- use the platform seen possible as a first contact opportunity in order to find people with similar childcare interest;
- exchange of personal data perceived as problematic and to happen offline;
- interest in an online mapping of available and unused spaces in Hamburg;
- support the access and use from the (many) parents who do not have smartphones.

2.9.2 Preparatory activities

According to the information collected by the community management in Hamburg, the involvement of families in the neighborhood of Harburg was not successful, as it will be better explained in the next paragraph (2.9.3). Therefore, the team decided to try to activate new networks through already existing connections in other areas of Hamburg. In particular, the activation of participants towards the piloting phase focused on personal contacts and networks of Urbanista team members - especially parents, frequent users

of digital technologies, partly already connected to or in exchange with other parents for organizing childcare. Indeed, the Urbanista team members introduced the project to their personal everyday life networks in the neighbourhoods of Eimsbüttel, Altona and Ottensen. The following stakeholders and groups of families were involved:

- Kindergarten Altona
- Primary School Rellinger Straße, Hamburg Eimsbüttel
- House community Hamburg Eimsbüttel (5 families)
- Two circles of friends in Hamburg Altona and Ottensen (10 families each)
- Horse riding club (2 families)

Further steps undertaken consisted in:

- online promotion through the Urbanista homepage and through Facebook (via NEXTHAMBURG page);
- creation of an ad hoc website³²;
- dissemination of newsletters;
- offline promotion through posters, leaflets and postcards produced and distributed and through interviews and face-to-face contacts with potential community members, local institutions and initiatives active in child care.

Also, usability tests were conducted among the Urbanista community in order to pre-identify issues before introducing the app to a larger public. The Urbanista team also tried to engage parents within the Nexthamburg³³ community. In total, about 40 adults were involved through the Urbanista community, while the promotional material created reached about 170 people.

Although the efforts put in place and the activities carried out, the Urbanista team had to acknowledge a general resistance towards the project. In the following paragraph the reasons inducing the team to abandon the Hamburg City Lab are illustrated in details.

2.9.2 Cancellation of the Hamburg City Lab: reasons and reflections

As concerns the first neighbourhood involved, Harburg, the engagement process was not successful firstly due to the existence of an **oversupply of childcare services** in the area. Also, in Harburg **residents tend to organize their daily routine through mutual informal support in pairs or very small groups**, but rarely with the help of institutions or others.

As already mentioned, the Urbanista team tried to explore feasibility in different neighborhoods with the hope to be able to build up a community starting from the Urbanista employees networks. However, it did not work either for the following reasons:

- general scepticism and lack of trust towards EU research projects, perceived as far from people's everyday life.
- perceptions that already existing networks among families are working well in supporting childcare
- reluctance to the use of digital tools: some prefer to rely on off line and face to face meetings

³² <https://familiesshare.urbanista.de>

³³ Nexthamburg is a citizen-based think tank in urban development of Hamburg, giving the citizens the possibility to contribute to current discussions about urban development with their own ideas. It represents a successful previous experience of Urbanista <https://nexthamburg.de>

- reluctance to the use of additional digital tools: the use of a few tools like synchronized calendars and WhatsApp groups is felt as already covering all needs
- lack of trust on privacy protection and consequent reluctance using Apps that are intended to support everyday life organization: Indeed, data protection itself represents a hot topic in Germany, especially after the latest EU data protection regulation (GDPR)³⁴.
- usability tests carried out did not help in increasing these feelings since the majority of participant to the tests found the app particularly confusing and not user-friendly.

According to the community management team from URBANISTA, the key factor is the presence of an already well-structured and dense childcare offer both in terms of informal networks and institutionalized activities. The existing offer is varied with regards to the holiday periods and comes from a wide range of entities such as museums, cultural associations, companies etc. For most parents, adopting the Families Share model for the upcoming summer holidays was even too late since they already found childcare solutions. Basically, the childcare needs of people living in the target neighborhoods were already covered, both through formal or informal solutions.

Concluding, despite all the efforts employed, the Urbanista team realized that institutions, companies, kindergartens and schools within its network saw no benefit in participating in the Families Share project. Therefore, it was not possible to activate a community neither for participating to the first pilot activity nor for carrying out future project activities. According to the Urbanista team's opinion, the issues encountered do not represent a peculiarity of the Hamburg social and cultural context, they rather characterize all Germany since in all the country a well-organized and diverse system of childcare already exists.

Part III. Evaluating the Families Share app

An evaluation of the Families Share app and model was conducted after the completion of the pilot activities at the different City Labs in Summer 2019. Participants were involved in face-to-face interviews and focus groups for discussing the co-play activities and exploring their opinions and suggestions on the digital platform, following the guidelines reported in D3.1. Information from interviews and the focus groups were further coupled and complemented with insights from survey questions and log analysis.

3.1 Participants to the study

In all City Labs, parents taking part to pilot activities also participated to some evaluation activities aimed at gathering feedbacks from participants related to the experience of the pilot. Evaluation activities consisted in focus groups, individual interviews and a survey. Each City Lab conducted at least one focus group and five interviews, with the exception of Győr City Lab. In general, people taking part to the focus groups also filled the survey in. The survey was based on a broader questionnaire prepared by IMEC in the frame of WP4 for the impact assessment, but it was agreed at the consortium level to also include some questions for evaluating the pilot experience of the participants with the Families Share model and platform, in order not to overwhelm the same small number of participants with request to take part to many time consuming evaluation activities.

³⁴ The fear of becoming a so-called "transparent" citizen is huge in Germany, since many people feel like they lost control of what happens to their own data. This is even more critical when it comes to share data on childcare.

During focus groups and interviews, participants were asked to report about the overall experience with shared childcare (already reported above in Part 2) and about the experience with the technological platform³⁵. Specific questions were aimed at exploring the perception of users in terms of usability, usefulness and trust and privacy. The survey also tackled the above mentioned dimensions including questions meant at understanding attitudes, social diffusion and intention to use in each City Lab.

The following table sums up numbers (75) and sex of people engaged in the evaluation activities³⁶. Each City Lab involved from 14 to 16 people, except for Bologna which involved 11 parents and Győr with only 4 parents. In the Győr City Lab parents took part both to the focus group and the interviews.

In line with participation to piloting activities, no surprise that the great majority of involved parents are females (mothers) in each City Lab.

CITY LABS	TRENTO	VENICE	GYÖR	KORTRIJK	BOLOGNA	THESSALONIKI	ALL City Labs
TOT parents (headcount)	15	14	4	16	11	15	75
FOCUS GROUPS	10	9	4	11	6	10	50
SURVEY*	9	8	4	5	10	10	46
INTERVIEWS	5	5	4	5	5	5	29
TOT Males	6	4	0	3	0	4	17
TOT Females	9	10	4	13	11	11	58

Table 14. Number and features of people taking part to evaluation activities per City Lab and type of methods * see footnote n°36

3.2 Log in data analytics and improvement of the platform app based on users feedback during the pilot

The aim of the present section is to provide data analytics on the use of the platform during the first piloting phase, as well as to summarize issues encountered by users in such period and the related improvements to the platform. Such data were provided by the partner (Vilabs) in charge of developing the platform under WP2.

With reference to data analytics, the most relevant data taken into consideration are the following ones:

- total number of users;
- number of users using the web platform (Apple users);

³⁵ See Annex 4 and 5

³⁶ As explained, in almost all cases parents responding to the survey were the same who took part to the Focus Groups so the “Total parents” in the table doesn’t count for the latter ones.

- number of users using the mobile app (Android users);
- total number of children profiles added by parents;
- total number of groups.

The time frame taken into account goes from the 1st May 2019 to the 24th July 2019 and it includes the period when all the piloting activities were conducted.

As concerns the **overall number of users** in all City Labs, as of July 24, 95 new users were counted³⁷. The distribution among the different City Labs appears to be quite unbalanced, ranging from 5 (in the case of Kortrijk) to 28 (in the case of Venice).

The graphs below show the overall trend of new users as well as the trend per each City Labs in the mentioned time frame.

Figure 21. Overall trend of new users per City Lab

Figure 22. Overall trend of new users

³⁷ According to the project GA, the overall number of 100 new users were expected to be engaged in the first piloting phase.

As it is possible to observe, in most City Labs people subscribed to the platform starting from mid-June since pilot activities started at the end of the month of June or beginning of July. The only exception is in Trento where the first users accessed the app already in May for the preparations of the “Fridays Mini Labs” activities. Differences in the extent to which the use of the technical tool actually supported the social innovation shared childcare activities were clarified in Part 2 and have to be taken into account when looking at the evaluation results presented in the following paragraphs. Indeed, as recalled and motivated, and as quite normal for a first experiment, 2 City Labs only (Venice and Trento) witnessed a full alignment of the social and digital innovation component of the pilot. In other cases the use was limited to registration and testing of the system either after the activities or during them, but as a demonstration and not for supporting their organization/management.

Table 15 compares the number of users per City Lab with the real number of people taking part to pilot activities.

	N. of users	Real n. of people
Bologna	19	8
Győr	8	4
Kortrijk	5	210
Trento	20	27
Thessaloniki	15	17
Venice	28	19
Total	95	285

Table 15. N. of users and real number of people involved in the pilot

Before commenting the results it is important to point how that the number of users generally includes also people belonging to the community management not only people taking part to the pilots. However, what stands out is the remarkable difference between users and real number of participants in the activities for the Kortrijk City Lab. The reason of such discrepancy is that in Kortrijk none of the co-playing parents used the app/platform during the pilot activities, as already explained in the dedicated paragraph (see paragraph 2.7.3). Also the City Labs of Trento and Thessaloniki had an higher number of people involved in the piloting compared with the number of users, but the difference is less relevant. These were the two cases which were affected by misalignment between the parents’ organizational and planning needs and the project’s timeline in releasing a ready to use improved version of the platform.

Regarding the use of the **Android mobile app** and of the **web platform** the following data were registered, showing a general balance between the two options. However, taking into account the data per each City Lab it is possible to observe that in half of the City Labs they are not balanced, showing a great prevalence of web platform users in the case of Thessaloniki and Győr City Labs. On the contrary, in Bologna the great majority of users installed the Android app.

	Web	App
Bologna	4	15
Győr	7	1
Kortrijk	2	3
Trento	9	11
Thessaloniki	10	5
Venice	15	13
Total	47	48

Table 16. N. web and app users

The following table sums up other useful data to understand the size of the communities created in each City Lab, since the numbers of children added by users and groups created are shown.

	n. of registered children	Real n. of children	n. of groups
Bologna	13	20	3
Győr	9	8	4
Kortrijk	12	315	9
Trento	8	26	6
Thessaloniki	22	19	14
Venice	22	21	3

Table 17. N. of registered children, real n. of piloting children and n. of groups created in the platform

It can be observed that in Trento and Bologna the number of actual children participating to the pilot activities is higher than the one of the children inserted in the platform. This means that only a low number of users (parents) inserted their children profiles in the app. In the case of Trento it is actually important to recall that the platform was not used during the first pilot activity (Fridays' Mini Labs) while in case of the second pilot (Summer Camp) not all the participants to pilot activities were parents, as already explained in section 2.4. In Győr, Thessaloniki and Venice the difference is irrelevant while it is huge in the case of Kortrijk. The same considerations expressed above with reference to the number of users apply.

Moreover, the number of groups created at the Kortrijk, Thessaloniki and Győr City Labs appears to be quite high compared to the number of users, and this can be justified considering that during the pilot activities, in the three City Labs, the app was tested by participants during the piloting or the evaluation activities rather than used to concretely organize co-playing activities.

Independently of the use of the platform done during the piloting phase, every City Lab reported to the technical partner a number of **issues**³⁸ encountered by participants. Obviously, during the piloting period the platform was used in a more extensive way compared to the testing period and this led to the discovery of some bugs/unexpected behavior.

In total, in the time frame May-July 2019, 20 issues were reported to Vilabs. The following table provides a full lists.

Id	Title	Date Reported	Labels
170	Issue login - home screen not responding	28-05-2019	Frontend
171	Switches Color Issue	31-05-2019	Frontend Improvement
174	New member notification issue	31-05-2019	Frontend bug
175	Strange member (Nuage Laboratorie)	31-05-2019	Frontend
181	Not possible to delete a specific timeslot	01-07-2019	Frontend Improvement Timeslot management
189	Cannot confirm availability / issue confirm dialogue	08-07-2019	Frontend bug
190	Go back from the notification screen	08-07-2019	Frontend Improvement
191	Not possible to switch / change google account	08-07-2019	Frontend Improvement Profile management
192	Invite friends item missing from the menu	08-07-2019	Frontend Profile management
193	Issue when adding a new group administrator	17-07-2019	Frontend Group management bug
194	Issue when time slots include days from two months	19-07-2019	Frontend Improvement Timeslot management
195	Issue with new group request	22-07-2019	Frontend Group management
196	No indication that activity is being created when clicking the "create" button. Users think they didn't press it properly	31-07-2019	Activity management Frontend Improvement
197	Timezone issue: Created timeslots change timezone	31-07-2019	Backend Timeslot management bug
198	Mail and phone icon not clickable in web app	31-07-2019	Frontend Improvement
199	Calendar visibility issue (overlapping with bottom navigation bar)	31-07-2019	Calendar Frontend Improvement
200	Orange outlines sometimes appear when pressing buttons	31-07-2019	Frontend Improvement
201	Missing text in Dutch when removing kid from timeslot	31-07-2019	Frontend Improvement Localization Timeslot management
202	Additional reporting tools are needed in community management screen. (e.g. charts)	31-07-2019	Community management Frontend Improvement

³⁸ Issues were collected using Github.

203	Design of Community interface needs improvement	31-07-2019	Community management Frontend Improvement
-----	---	------------	---

Table 18. Lists of issues encountered by pilot participants

The second column presents a short description of the issues, the third one the date in which the issue was reported, while the last column classifies the issues according to the layer they affect and their features. In particular, a first distinction is between the frontend and the backend, meaning with frontend the presentation layer and with backend the data access layer. As immediately visible, **the great majority of issues concerned the frontend** (19 out of 20). Only one issue affects the backend and it is related to the creation of time slots.

The other labels present in the fourth column give more information about the type of issues, explaining which of the following functionalities they affect:

- timeslot management (4 issues);
- community management (2 issues);
- profile management (2 issues);
- group management (2 issues)
- localization (1 issue);
- calendar (1 issue);
- activity management (1 issue).

Finally, a distinction between bugs and improvements is made. It indicates which issues represent bugs that need to be resolved in order for the platform to run correctly and which issues are related to new improvements to better meet users' needs. 12 issues represent improvements, while 4 are bugs. Some issues are not classified.

Based on the issues pointed out by piloting users, new functionalities were added even during the piloting period by developers. In particular, major new functionalities related to the timeslots' management were added. These included the support of timeslot deletion following an activity's creation (id Issue 181) and the spanning of activity timeslots' dates over different months. Another major addition was the implementation of the community manager interface to assist the latter with functionalities as well as some graphs and statistics on the usage in their respective communities.

It is important to underline that **all identified issues have already been solved by the technical partner.**

3.3 Perceived Usability and Technology Acceptance

The term Usability refers to the ease of access and/or use of a product or website. According to the official ISO 9241-11 definition, usability is: "the extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use"³⁹. In order to gather inputs from users in terms of usability, participants to focus groups and interviews were asked to discuss how they evaluated their experience with the app and to report any issue or criticality encountered. In details, they were initially asked if they used the web platform of the mobile app and to explain how they evaluated the experience in using it, mentioning eventual issues they encountered in the use of the technological tool and how they were faced. Also, the role of the group administrator in the platform was

³⁹ See ISO 9241-11:2018, section 3.1 on Usability, <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:9241:-11:ed-2:v1:en>

explored. In case of interviews, participants were also asked to rate the platform on a scale from 1 to 7 (Likert scale) in terms of usability.

Usability and ease of use was also explored in the survey, according to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM - see D3.1).

3.3.1 Overall results

On the basis of the analysis of the results of the evaluation activities conducted in each City Lab in terms of usability, it is possible to say that the majority of participants considered the platform quite easy to use. Indeed, 6 and 8 out of 24 participants to interviews and focus groups considered the app respectively slightly easy and moderately easy to use. However, most of the people involved reported some criticalities in using it, some of them minor, some other quite relevant. Criticalities regarded different processes of the app, but the most critical process was the one related to the management of the activities. However, in most cases, criticalities were solved during the pilot with the help of the community managers and the developers.

As far as the different detailed results from interviews are concerned, the following table sums up rating of the platform during individual interviews in terms of usability, grouped by number of votes per each rate (Likert scale used).

City Lab	1=not easy at all	2=moderately difficult	3=slightly difficult	4=neither difficult nor easy	5=slightly easy	6=moderately easy	7=extremely easy
Bologna		1			3		
Trento				2		2	
Venice				1	1	3	
Győr		1	3				
Kortrijk					1	1	
Thessaloniki			1	1	1	2	

Table 19. Rates given by interviewees in terms of usability

As it is visible, “moderately easy” and “slightly easy” are the rates which received the majority of votes. According to the results of the **survey (see chart below)**, almost 60% of respondents in the 6 City Labs agreed or strongly agreed that the application was easy to use. Participants in the City Labs of Venice, Budapest and Thessaloniki were mostly positive with the usability of the app, while half of the responses from Trento, Kortrijk and Bologna were positive and half neutral/negative

Usability / Ease of use

Figure 23. Results of the survey’s item “the application is easy to use”

Considering technology acceptance (a broader construct with respect to usability), the results of the survey show that almost 50% of the respondents in the City Labs considered the platform useful and easy to use, they have a positive attitude toward the application and have a positive intention to use the app in the future. The results suggest that while the app is mostly perceived as usable and useful, users would need a stronger motivation for sustaining adoption and continuous usage of the platform.

Technology Acceptance

Figure 24. Results of the survey in terms of usefulness, ease of use, attitude and intention to use⁴⁰

3.3.2 Perceived usability in the City Labs

According to the results of focus groups and interviews, the following considerations can be done. The **Bologna** City Lab did not use the Families Share app for organizing the pilot activities for the already mentioned reasons (see paragraph 2.3.3). In fact, the platform was shown and used during the evaluation activities (focus group and individual interviews), with the help of community managers, which explored the app usability. Nevertheless, the overall feedback on the app was positive since it was perceived by

⁴⁰ See Annex 6 for more details on the survey’s items.

participants as easy and intuitive to use, even though they stated that **the process to create activities is a bit too long**. Among the 5 interviewed people, 4 used the app and 1 used the web-version (iOS users). The only usability issue reported by the group of Bologna consisted in a bug in the functionality 'I forgot my password', that did not work. Due to this error, the participant was not able to get back her ID information and consequently to enter again in the app.

As explained in paragraph 2.4.1., at the **Trento** City Lab two pilot activities were conducted. Usability was explored with the participants of both pilots. Parents participating in the Friday Mini Labs did not use the app much, whereas parents taking part to the Summer Camp mainly used it for lunch breaks. In general, they found the app easy and intuitive to use, even though someone stated that there are **too many functions**, and **this makes the app a bit complex**, making easier to use other apps like WhatsApp or Doodle. As regards issues encountered during the use of the platform, parents found some difficulties in managing activities, inserting availabilities, and in using the chat function; also, notifications were a bit problematic, due to some technical issues. According to interviewees, **activities should appear in chronological order** and all the process related to the activity status should be made easier and more visible. Moreover, notifications should be interactive. All the issues were reported to the Families Share team at the e-mail address families-share@fbk.eu.

In **Venice** the majority of the parents used the mobile app during the pilot activities. In general, all the participants to evaluation activities found the platform easy to use. However, they reported some issues and bugs that in most cases were later solved. Among the main criticalities there were the creation of the profile of the child, a counting bug not showing the real number of children taking part to the activities, push notifications not working properly, and the process of adding a name and description of an activity was perceived as a bit complicated. Also, the calendar can be improved according to parents. Issues were reported to the Families Share team. Some parents reported they used the platform not only in the organizational phase but also during the piloting week, for checking time slots and planned activities.

During pilot activities in the City Lab of **Győr**, the Hungarian version of the platform resulted to have some issues in the functionality for joining an activity, consisting in an error message when trying to add the availability. The mentioned criticality affected the usability perception of the participants, which considered the app quite difficult to use. Three people used the app, while one person used both the app and the web-version. Besides the activities-related problem, the interviewees reported that at a first glance the app seemed easy and practical, with well-organized menu and interface for what concerns the account and group creation. They encountered also other issues, both in the number of participants to an activity, that was continuously changing and not reflecting the reality, and with the back-arrow function that, when pushed, it was leading them directly at the homepage or out of the app. The community manager was continuously in contact with the platform developers, who managed to fix most of the criticalities by the end of the pilot.

The **Kortrijk** City Lab did not use the Families Share platform to organize the co-playing activities (see paragraph 2.7.3), thus the community managers showed a demo-ed of the app during the focus group and made other parents test it directly during the individual interviews. All the interviewees used the mobile application, but not everyone evaluated it, just two people did. Although for most of the parents the platform seemed quite intuitive and easy to use, they encountered different criticalities while surfing through it. For instance, the visualization of the personal calendar was considered as not clear (not distinguishing between

parents’ activities and children’s ones). In addition, they reported that the app does not provide a good overview of participants for each activity, making it necessary to open them one by one to visualize the participants. Almost all the interviewees underlined that it was not easy to spot notifications when a user asked to join a new group. They all agreed on the fact that the app will need further developments for them in order to be used use for organizing their co-playing periods, especially for replacing the already existing and consolidated spreadsheet templates they are very satisfied with.

At the **Thessaloniki** City Lab, in general, parents participating to evaluation activities used the mobile app and considered it easy to use, even if they made a limited use of it during the pilot activities. However, they reported some technical issues. For instance, parents reported having some struggles in the calendar functioning as well as in the creation of the account and the participation to an activity. One parent, who took the role of group administrator, reported that once the request from another parent is approved the new member becomes automatically group administrator.

3.4 Perceived Usefulness

With regards to Usefulness, according to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), it is considered as the user’s subjective probability that using a specific application system will enhance his or her job or life performance. It easy strictly connected with the ease of use dimension, which can be defined as the degree to which the prospective user expects the system to be free of efforts. In order to explore the usefulness dimension, participants were asked to say if they found the platform useful and to rate the level of usefulness (in case of interviews). They were also asked to explain if the co-organization of childcare activities was successful and how much of the organization happened through the platform and how much outside it. Also, the usefulness in terms of new social connections was explored.

Perceived usefulness of the platform has been investigated also in the survey as the degree to which a person believes that using the system would enhance his or her task related to childcare.

3.4.1 Overall results

According to the feedbacks received by parents during the evaluation activities, the Families Share app was considered, in general, quite useful or “potentially” useful, with 7 and 6 out of 25 participants considering it respectively “neither useless nor useful” and “moderately useful”. However, 4 parents considered it as “extremely useful”.

The following table sums up the rates given by parents taking part to individual interviews in terms of usefulness, grouped by number of votes per each rate (Likert scale used).

City Lab	1=not useful at all	2=moderately useless	3=slightly useless	4=neither useless nor useful	5=slightly useful	6=moderately useful	7=extremely useful
Bologna			1		2		
Trento				1		2	
Venice				1	1	1	2
Győr						2	2
Kortrijk			1	3	1		
Thessaloniki			1	2	1	1	

Table 20. Rates given by interviewees in terms of usefulness

As it is visible, the majority of votes were given to “neither useless nor useful” and “moderately useful”. The results from the **survey**, instead, show that the platform was considered to be useful by the majority of respondents, with Trento and Venice City Labs collecting most positive responses. Kortrijk and Bologna City Labs collected less favourable feedback.

Figure 25. Results of the survey’s item investigating the usefulness of the app according to the user

It is however necessary to specify that while a few City Labs fully used the platform for planning the pilot activities (this is the case of Venice and partly of Trento) the others made a limited use of it during this first phase due to some organizational and/or technical issues, but participants found it potentially useful for planning childcare activities in the future. However, in most of the City Labs, in order to be fully useful, some functionalities of the app should be added or improved, according to parents’ feedbacks. This is especially the case of the Kortrijk City Lab, where participants have been co-playing for a long time and are already adopting other tools. In order for them to change their planning habits and move to the Families Share app, it should be improved by adding more advanced functionalities.

3.4.2 Perceived usefulness in the City Labs

In the City Lab of **Bologna**, although the Families Share platform was not used for planning the activities, all the participants agreed on the usefulness of having an app for organizing childcare. They stated that it would be useful to have a set calendar for organizing shifts and activities, this would help them to save time and to be more organized. However, not all the participants felt comfortable in using technology for this purpose. All the interviewees stated that the pilot was organized 100% out of the platform, therefore they did not get in contact with new families through it. One person stated that the platform cannot be useful to find new people for co-playing, since it cannot substitute face-to-face meetings. Nevertheless, most of the parents were looking forward to trying to use the app for the next pilot’s organization.

In **Trento**, some participants of the Summer Camp were in doubt about the usefulness of the platform for the organization of lunch breaks showing a bit of reluctance in changing the approach already adopted over the years. Others found the app useful for coordinating groups, giving availabilities and sharing a calendar,

but the face to face interaction was still considered fundamental for planning activities and trusting other people. Some participants thought the app could be useful also for the enrollment process and for organizing other collaborative activities among families. Participants reported that the app would be more useful if additional functionalities are added. As parents had to learn how to use the app, they found it a bit time consuming, but only at the beginning. In general, all parents participating to the pilots already knew each other so no new connections were created through the app.

In **Venice** the platform was perceived as useful to plan activities and structure the co-playing period even though some functionalities should be improved according to parents' opinion. For instance, the functionality "export the activity" can be improved giving the possibility to export only the calendar and making info visible without the need to export them. Only one parent reported that for the first pilot the platform was not very useful because most communications among parents happened through a WhatsApp group. However, in general, the organization of the activities through the app was successful even though some parents were late in subscribing in the platform and inserting their availabilities, etc. Parents had different perception about the percentage of the platform use in the organization of the childcare activities (from 40% to 90%). Some parents pointed out that it would be useful if the app could create new networks with new families.

The **Győr** City Lab conducted the pilot with four parents who were then part of both the focus group and of the individual interviews. The temporary malfunctioning of the platform did not allow them to fully exploit the app functionalities for the organization of childcare; however, they all believe that the app could be extremely useful for this purpose. Participants stated that they appreciated a technological tool that allows them to organize childcare without having commercial ads or privacy issues (as it is now with Facebook). One of them thought that the app will be very useful to a lot of families in her city in the future.

The **Kortrijk** City Lab represents a peculiar case, given that groups of parents have been already co-playing for 4 years. Those groups therefore have created and adjusted their own technological tools for organizing childcare (usually three or more google sheets). For this reason, and for the fact they were already organized for the summer co-playing activities when the ready for use version of the platform was released, they were not available in using the app for the co-playing organization, they just tried it or saw the demo-ed during the evaluation activities. In the focus group, when asked about the usefulness of the app, the participants had two different visions. From one side they felt it could not substitute their current tools, given that the planning functionality is lacking, and the messaging section is not a good alternative to WhatsApp (that is what they were currently using). From the other side, some parents were more positive, seeing the potentialities of having all the childcare organization in one single tool. They liked having all the members neatly listed, including their children's information and special needs, and having an overview of all the time slots. However, they all agreed that, as it is now, the app would not be an added value for them. They would need an app where it is possible to add the childcare availabilities and needs as starting information, from which the app automatically proposes a structure of the co-playing weeks. Someone would also appreciate a time-banking system, in order to count the effort of every parent.

At the **Thessaloniki** City Lab, parents found the app useful for organizing group activities, setting the timetable, the place and the duration. According to their opinion, using the app limits the use of other communication channels, like phone calls and messages. The co-organization of the activities through the app was perceived as easy and useful for saving time and money. Some parents reported that the app helped

to create new connections for co-organizing childcare with other parents. They indicated that during the pilot the organization of the childcare activities happened in majority outside the app (in general, they indicated a percentage from 20% to 40%). Only one parent perceived the activities were organized mainly through the app (60%).

3.5 Attitudes, social diffusion and intention to use

According to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), user's perceptions concerning usefulness and ease of use of a technology are hypothesized to be salient beliefs that determine attitude toward the use of the technology and eventually lead to the acceptance and use. However, usefulness and ease of use (usability) are not the only variables that affect acceptance, but also external factors such as social diffusion and internal factors such as attitude mediate acceptance and affect the behavioural intention to use the application in the future.

Attitudes and intention to use indicators draws on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davies, 1985, 1989) and its further extensions (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000; Kim, Chun & Song, 2009), and they describes the level of acceptance of a new technology based on its perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. Attitudes, social diffusion and intention to use the Families Share platform were investigated through the survey distributed by IMEC in the framework of impact assessment (WP4). In fact, as already explained in the methodology (paragraph 2.1), in order to facilitate the participation in the study, a unique survey was elaborated for gathering data both for the impact assessment (WP4) and the platform evaluation (WP3). In general, participants to the survey coincided with the ones taking part to the focus groups.

Specifically, **attitude toward using indicate the user desirability and capability of using the system** and it was explored in the survey through a set of dedicated questions which can be found in Annex 6 and which were aimed at exploring:

- what activities the respondent performed on the Families Share apps;
- how many groups were joined on the app;
- participants perception of the benefits of using the app.

Intention to use was measured through the following items:

- intention to use the app again for future shared childcare activities;
- intention to recommended it to others.

Lastly, the survey measured the **social diffusion** that indicates the **level of spread of the platform among a group of potential users** (Rogers, 2003), which usually happens through words of mouth. This dimension is investigated with two items:

- for which ones of the performed activities, invitations to others were sent;
- in what relation with the invited persons respondents were (family members, friends, colleagues).

3.5.1 Overall results

We will here provide an aggregate analysis of the above mentioned dimensions without going into details for each one of them given the low number of responses to the survey and the fact that the validity of collected data is still understandably partial at this stage. This is due to the extremely different contexts of use, and the fact that in most cases respondents tested the technology out of the concrete planning task and after having already organized the activities it was meant to support.

Concerning general attitudes toward digital technologies, it is possible to observe that, in general, users had good level of interest towards technologies as well as digital skills. There are of course a few exceptions

especially in the case of the Bologna City Lab where half of the participants admitted not having good digital skills.

Considering the attitude toward using the app measured by **appreciating to what extent the application provides benefits to the individual user**, participants to the survey indicated a neutral/positive response when asked to rate their level of agreement. While the majority of respondents in Thessaloniki and Venice City Labs expressed a highly positive attitude toward the use of the Families Share app, respondents from the other City Labs perceived less benefits in using it.

Figure 26. Results of the survey's items in terms of benefits of the app to the user

With reference to the activities performed in the app there is heterogeneity among City Labs, and this is related to the use done of the platform during the pilot activities. Indeed, in general, in those City Labs in which the app was fully used in the organization of the pilots, more activities were performed on line by the users inside the app, with the exception of the Thessaloniki City Lab where the testing activities were numerous even though not with the purpose to concretely organize the pilot. Just a few users sent messages through the dedicated function.

Regarding the **intention to continue using the app in the future**, the answers are quite varied. While the Venice, Bologna and Thessaloniki City Labs showed more positive feedbacks, Trento and Kortrijk respondents showed a lower willingness to use the current version of the platform in the future.

Figure 27. Results of the survey's item investigating the intention of the user to continue using the app

Finally, concerning the **social diffusion**, only a few users invited other people to use the app. This can partly be explained by the fact that in some City Labs users could assess the app only through direct invitation by the community managers.

3.5.2 Attitudes, social diffusion and intention to use in the City Labs

In the present paragraph the answers to the survey's questions will be reported and commented per each City Lab, stressing especially feedbacks related to the three dimensions object of the present section.

In **Bologna**, 10 parents testing the app during the interviews and focus group answered the survey. They were all women between 33 and 53 years old, 6 of them with Italian nationality, 2 from Morocco, and 2 from Romania. Users appeared to be quite heterogeneous since half of them resulted to be rather good or very good in using technologies while the other half rather bad or very bad in it. However, most of them indicated they learn easily to work with digital technologies, or they are keen in trying them, being interested (in 6 out of 10 cases) in technologies. In general, they did not perform any activity in the app, except for 2 people, that tried all of them, whereas they were in doubt on the number of groups they joined in the app. The majority neither agree nor disagree whether the app could help them in organizing childcare arrangements and if it was easy to use, given that they did not utilize the app for this purpose. For what concerns the intention to use, 8 people out of 10 did not know whether they would like to continue to use the app, and 6 did not know if they would recommend it to their friends. Lastly, regarding the dimension of social diffusion most of the people did not invite anyone to register in Families Share, apart from 3 people who invited their colleagues and friends.

At the **Trento** City Lab, the survey was filled in by participants of the focus groups. 9 people responded, among which 3 men and 6 women, eight from Italy and one from Albania with an age range between 31 and 54 years old. From their responses on the attitude dimension, it is possible to detect that they mostly had very good digital skills (this is confirmed by the fact that, as already explained, most of the parents taking part to the pilot were FBK researchers), as well as reported to learn easily to use technologies and to be interested in them. With the Families Share app, they mainly checked the proposed activities and half of them also added their availability through the app. They agreed that the application was easy to use, that it

would facilitate the organization of childcare arrangements, and that this service could benefit them. The intention to use the app instead was less clear according to the answers given, since 4 people neither agreed nor disagreed whether they would continue to use the app, 2 disagreed and only 3 agreed. Moreover, 5 people disagreed that they would recommend the app to their friends. In general, nobody invited other people to register to the app, apart from 1 person who invited his/her own partner and two others who invited their colleagues.

In **Venice**, parents attending the focus group, also filled the survey. Among them, there were 3 men and 5 women, 7 Italians and 1 from Croatia, with an age range between 33 and 49 years old. The participants defined their digital skills between “neither good nor bad” and “rather good”, but most of them indicated that it is easy for them to learn to work with digital technologies and that they are keen in trying them, although they did not show to have an high interest in them. Within the Families Share app, all of them created an activity (except for one person), checked the proposed activities and added their availability during the pilot; also, 5 people sent a message through the app. Moreover, 5 out of 8 people indicated that the app was easy to use and 7 out of 8 that the platform facilitated the organization of childcare with other parents. Concerning the participants’ intention to use, 3 of them would like to continue to use the app while 5 were in doubt on the future use of the platform, answering “neither agree nor disagree”. However, all of them would recommend it to their friends. In terms of social diffusion, at this stage the app was downloadable only under invitation by the community managers, therefore, the participants did not invite anyone to register.

The City Lab of **Győr**, as described in the chapter 2.6, faced some technical difficulties with the Families Share app during the pilot, thus they did not manage to fully use it. 4 mothers, age range 33-40, took part in the piloting activities and completed the online survey. 3 out of 4 participants indicated they have rather good digital skills. Concerning the attitude of use, most of the participants managed to send a message in the app, to add their availabilities (to an activity already created by the community manager) and invite someone else to register. In general, they agree the app was easy to use and that it would make easier to organize childcare arrangements with other parents. 2 out of 4 parents expressed the intention to keep on using the app. In terms of social diffusion all the respondents invited some friends to join the app.

In **Kortrijk**, the use of the app was limited to the evaluation activities, during which parents tried the app. 5 parents answered the survey, 4 female and one male with an age range 33-41. Most of the respondents managed to create a group and an activity as well as to invite someone else to join. 3 out of 5 respondents expressed to have very good technological skills, no difficulties in learning to work with digital tools and a strong interest in technologies in general. 2 out of 5 parents found the app easy to use and indicated that it could facilitate the childcare organization with other parents. In terms of intention to use, 2 out of 5 parents expressed the interest to continue using the app. In terms of social diffusion, they did not invite anyone to register to the platform.

At the **Thessaloniki** City Lab, the Families Share platform was tested and used by participants during the pilot activities. A total of 10 people filled the survey: they were 3 males and 7 females, all Greek with an age range between 37 and 52 years old. All the respondents declared to have good digital skills and to learn easily to use digital technologies; they indicated to be keen to try out technologies and rather interested in them. For what concerns the Families Share application, they performed all the listed activities, apart from sending

messages (4 people did not do so). All of the participants joined at least one group in the app. They were all positive in the use of Families Share for organizing childcare activities with other parents and most of them indicated it was easy to use. Regarding their intention to use, they all would like to continue to use it and 5 of them would recommend the app to their friends while the other 5 expressed doubts about it. Finally, 9 out of 10 invited someone else to register in the app, among which, their partner, friends and other family members.

3.6 Trust and privacy

The online privacy and security represent one of the main concerns of users. This is especially relevant for the Families Share platform since also sensitive information about children are share. The perception of users about privacy and security issues was explored during **interviews, focus groups and through the survey**. In particular, special attention was paid in understanding how parents felt when sharing information about children. The evaluation activities investigated the **parents' feelings in sharing their personal data and their child/children's data with the other parents of the group**, their **awareness on privacy issues** (in particular if they were aware of the type of private information required and the reasons behind the collection of specific data) and their knowledge on how accessing and changing their privacy settings.

Also, the dimension of **trust** was explored by asking to participants a feedback with reference to **the balance between face to face meetings and online exchanges** during the pilot organization.

As concerns the survey, it included five questions on privacy and data sharing perception, asking participants to rate how comfortable (or uncomfortable) they felt in sharing information (such as their personal contacts or their child(ren)' information) with other users in the Families Share platform.

As concerns privacy policy, the platform, during the first piloting phase, included a first and basic information page on privacy and data protection⁴¹. However, the consortium has now finalized an updated version of such an informed consent sheet (M20), which is in the process of being published on the national/local instances of the Families Share app.

3.6.1 Overall Results

Among the 29 people interviewed most of them felt comfortable in sharing data and agreed with the level of details for both their own personal data and the ones of their children, with the exception of the Thessaloniki City Lab and a few parents from Győr. In both cases, indeed parents did not feel comfortable in sharing children's data and would have preferred to share less data.

Concerning the awareness related to the collection and accessibility of personal data, there were different opinions. Almost all the participants knew that they were part of a research study and therefore both group members and developers could access their data, however, someone was non totally sure of this and in some cases they reported that more transparency would be needed (especially in Trento).

The balance between face to face and online exchanges was perceived as adequate only by participants of Venice City Lab, while in the other cases, like in Bologna, parents reported that they just had face-to-face meetings or that there was no balance. Nevertheless, in every City Labs participants agreed on the importance of creating trust through in-person meetings, which are perceived as fundamental trust building precondition in order to implement Families Share activities. The online platform could be then useful only once trust between participants has already been built off line.

⁴¹ See Annex 7.

As anticipated, further than during interviews and focus groups, the matter of trust and privacy was also investigated in a question of the online survey. The results are displayed in Figure 28.

Figure 28. Results of survey's item on privacy issues

Lastly, considering differences among City Labs, the results of the survey indicate that parents, generally speaking, felt comfortable in sharing information regarding themselves (profile picture and their phone number) more than on their children. On the opposite, in Venice and Kortrijk City Labs parents were more comfortable in sharing information of their child(ren) while Budapest, Bologna and Trento City Labs' respondents seemed less willing to share their child(ren)' information, especially medical and health information. We interpret this gap with the degree of autonomy (and therefore responsibility) undertaken by parents for longer periods of time (weekly activities) in Venice and Kortrijk which increases the perceived need on the individual information on each kids to enable parents safeguarding their health and well-being. Analyzing the answers by City Lab and per type of information to be shared the following graphs are obtained.

Figure 29. Results on survey's items on privacy issues per dimension explored

3.6.2 Trust and privacy in the City Labs

At the **Bologna** City Lab trust and privacy issues were investigated during individual interviews. Most of the participants felt comfortable in sharing their own data, instead they were less comfortable about their children data. They indicated they prefer to exchange just basic information like the name, sex, and age without adding the profile picture. Half of the interviewees were aware about the reason why the platform collected their data, the others were not sure about the reason. Although being aware about the project, they reported to be not sure about who could access their data, besides the group members. Lastly, all of them reported that there was not a balance between face-to-face meetings and online exchanges, since the last ones were totally missing. Anyway they stated that online exchanges can be useful in order to save time, once the group has already had the chance to meet face-to-face.

Also, in **Trento** the trust and privacy dimension was explored only during individual interviews. In general, parents found useful and important sharing data and did not feel uncomfortable in doing so. However, most of them claimed that more transparency in the process of collecting data would be needed, since at the beginning they did not understand the reason why the information were collected and how they would have been used. Important information of children related to the activity carried out should be shared with the involved volunteers. They agreed on the fact that trust can be built only through face-to-face interactions, but the app can be a support, since, once trust is created, there is no problem in sharing personal data.

In **Venice** no relevant issues with trust and privacy emerged. Parents all felt comfortable in sharing their own data and the ones of their child/children. All of them agreed it is important that all parents involved in the activities are aware of the needs and problems of the children. Some parents were willing to share even more data, also face-to-face. In general, parents were aware on who could access the data and why info were

collected. The number of face-to-face meetings was perceived as sufficient for start trusting other parents since the group was small, even though some parents claimed that along the preparatory activities there were some variations of the number and people involved and this did not help. In case of a bigger group of parents then more meetings would have been necessary.

During the individual interviews in the **Győr** City Lab, in most cases parents felt comfortable in sharing their and their children personal data and two interviewees stated that they are willing to share more data when this can be useful (i.e. their children's school, their working hours, etc.). Only one interviewee felt uncomfortable and she claimed that the children nickname and the year of birth are enough. However, all of them felt that a trustful environment was created thanks to Families Share activities.

In **Kortrijk** the interviewed people reported that they did not have any issues in sharing their data within the group, also because they were already aware of its importance for the co-playing. They reckoned the platform can be a very useful tool where to collect all the children data and personal needs, in case some accident occurs. One interviewee suggested to better structure the section with children's data (i.e. with checkboxes, standard questions around kid needs, etc.). Another person reported that it should be possible to decide what information should be visible and what other can be hidden instead. Finally, everyone agreed on the importance of building trust first through face-to-face meetings, not only through the platform.

At the **Thessaloniki** City Lab, the matter of trust and privacy was perceived as quite problematic. Most of the parents did not feel comfortable in sharing data, especially the ones of their children and would prefer to share less information (only the age and special needs). On the other side someone observed that it would be good to have more information on the parents who are responsible for an activity in which his/her own child/children participate. A parent suggested to share contact info only once a person joins an activity, whereas another one found useful to add an "emergency contact". In general, parents were aware of the reason why such data are collected and who can access them. As concerns specifically the matter of trust some participants would have preferred to have more face-to-face meeting before the start of the piloting. None reported any conflicts/misunderstanding both online and offline arisen during the activities.

Part IV. Main strengths and challenges encountered in the digital-social innovation experiment and emerging models

The present chapter is meant at presenting the main challenges/issues encountered during the first piloting by the City Labs as well as the models that seem to emerge during the pilots. Subject of the analysis are both the acceptance of the social innovation model in its different versions, and the digital platform use, as well as their interrelation in the different contexts. We rely on data from both the evaluation and the continuous monitoring and reporting activities.

The consortium will take time to reflect on how the elements highlighted in the paragraphs below can be tackled in the continuation of WP3 and the second pilot, in WP1-WP2 in when refining the re-design of the app and in WP5, for supporting sustainability and replication.

4.1 The core strengths

The main strong point and added value perceived by parents and City Lab managers is definitely the **community building opportunity** that the Families Share social innovation model brings about: trust building for delegating other adults from your neighborhood (or your company) in taking care of your own kids and taking yourself the responsibility for it, exposes people to several concerns and resistances but when the experience is positive, it's extremely rewarding. The social bond that it creates, reflected in feelings and emotions mirrored by children being happy about it, compensate all efforts and becomes meaningful, especially in contexts and times when isolation and fear tend to become the predominant traits of social life. All the City Labs in this first piloting phase reported this was either clearly experienced in cities where co-playing activities directly and mainly managed by parents took place, or it was envisaged and expected in those cases where the approach was more gradual.

In the Families Share experience, this was coupled with the **need from families to find good quality, affordable childcare solutions** for their kids and improve their work life balance overall, whereas the combination of the two features tends to become rare.

Part 2 in particular has extensively reported on the many nuances these two aspects were featuring the 1st pilot iteration of the project solution.

4.2 Main challenges

Challenges regarded both the social model and the use of the digital platform and in some cases they were shared by more City Labs. Other issue, instead, were encountered only by one City Lab. We group them below trying to highlight how the digital and the social innovation components were intertwined, where relevant.

4.2.1 Entrusting oneself and other parents as care givers and educators: parents resistances and concerns

It was clearly reported in several City Labs how parents were reluctant to **trust** both other parents involved (most of the parents did not know each other before) and their own abilities to deal with groups of children, the latter partly linked to an initial perception that co-playing with kids for half or 1 entire day per week (as required in most of the proposed time schedules) was too demanding in terms of personal time to dedicate and needed capacities. Trust appeared to be interpreted in a variety of ways: trust of safeguarding safety and well-being, trust in other parents' educational/pedagogical approaches, etc. Such perceptions tended to be positively related to the degree of autonomy asked to parents, which lead some of the City Lab managers to adopt a more gradual approach based on either having all parents present at the same time with their own kids or by foreseeing the support of additional professional educators. Moreover, some parents proposed to receive specific training sessions on childcare-related topics (such as first-aids, activity planning, how to deal with relational issues, etc.) in order to feel more confident in providing childcare to groups of children.

Trust issues are at the core of Families_Share project, further analysis will be reported in D6.2 "Trust and safety framework Report" due in September 2019.

4.2.2 Informal vs formal care: (gendered) paradoxes and tensions of bringing childcare out of the services' market

Being the Families Share model based on parents' volunteer childcare and mutual support, it implies bringing part of the childcare needed by families out of the market, renouncing to paid professional childcare. This can generate a series of paradoxes and tensions. Childcare has traditionally been treated as unpaid

reproductive work and a women's role⁴² With the entry of women into the workforce, from the industrial revolution up to now, professional childcare as a paid service has become more and more widespread, offered by either public, and more and more often private organization, and often featuring a large share of the unregulated black economy and seeing low income, often migrant women working as nannies or babysitter to support work life balance of middle class native families. The Families Share social innovation model is implemented in such a complex scenario, and even if self-managed and volunteer childcare can potentially lead to greater recognition and re-appropriation of reproductive work for both men and women (or even new forms of negotiation between productive and reproductive time for company/organizational pilots), it risks to be perceived as subtracting competences and market's share to the existing public and private offer. This explains some of the challenges, tensions and conflicts perceived at the local level in some of the city labs, either with some stakeholders or parents, such as for example:

- NGOs or social enterprises already offering paid childcare or even parents in the process of setting up such organizations, didn't always respond positively to attempts by City Labs managers to network and collaborate, and sometimes didn't support it, even though initially thought to participate. Experimenting with mixed models where shared volunteer childcare is combined with paid care could be ways to reconnect in such cases. The initial experience within the consortium of the new Hungarian City Lab managing partner is already meaningful. This is the only organization in the consortium offering 'traditional' formal on payment childcare. They still interpret the Families Share experiment in a strategic way to complement their own existing offer. The way they are setting the pilot up shows how they are trying to handle it as complementary to their current activities: they are reaching out to different target groups of older children than the ones they are already serving, and targeting lower income parents who couldn't afford formal childcare anyway, or could afford it just for some of their kids when they have more than one.
- Childminders and/or teachers reported opinions about a supposed lack of quality in childcare provided by parents, questioning their ability to raise children in general (i.e. doubting that parents would be too much permissive and that, once back at school after holidays, children would be out of control)
- The idea that FS would lead to further Public Institutions budget cuts and decreased funding for childcare at the local level often raised by stakeholders
- The paradox that in times of economic crisis and stagnation leads an increasing number of qualified women and mothers to look at the private childcare sector as an employment opportunity while the demand for such services tends to decrease with diminished spending capacity of families, generates frustration towards requests to join social experiments where they are asked to volunteer in childcare for free.
- The number of participating fathers is still very low and their ability and willingness to re-balance the productive/reproductive time share in their lives is limited by many structural factors, a gender segregated labour market on one side, and cultural stereotypes related to care. The promising aspect here is that City Labs very positive dynamics whenever fathers took an active role.

⁴² See Federici S. (2012), *Revolution at Point Zero. Housework, Reproduction, and Feminist Struggle*, Oakland, PM Press and Ferrant G., Pesando L.M., Nowacka K (2014), *Unpaid Care Work: the missing link in the analysis of gender gaps in labour outcomes*, OECD Development Centre.

4.2.3 Regulatory issues

It is well known from literature how regulatory and legal frameworks often constitute obstacles to social (and sometimes digital) innovation processes⁴³. The Families Share social innovation model met a series of regulatory challenges mostly related to:

- **Accessing public spaces, schools and other public urban commons:** in some cases a pre-requisite set by the City authorities for accessing all spaces for free, was to set up a formal agreement between a legal entity in the form of a no-profit association and the Municipality itself, aimed at excluding the City Administration from any liabilities. The legal entity in charge should have also granted the appropriate insurance was set up to cover all participants (injury and civil liability). This implies the creation of a new association having parents as members or the involvement of an existing one whose legal form allows to have volunteers engaged. Solving regulatory issues, managing associations implies paper work that parents tend not to have time to perform or to take responsibilities which demotivate parents to participate. This points, with other elements, to the need of support that become evident once the model grows and expands, as shown by the Kortrijk City Labs.
- **Regulatory issues in company based pilots** pertain to HR management processes and protocols and might touch contractual regulations. Childcare within organizations might raise several issues, especially when employees take care of children during working hours. The engagement of employees in activities that are not directly related with their professional formal role (as for childcare) required to formally ground employees' engagement according to the logic of active participation in welfare actions and to clearly frame Families_Share initiatives as part of the organization policies on welfare and work-life balance. These internal processes asked for a strong commitment of the management and required several negotiations in order to ensure the feasibility of the pilot within the company.

4.2.4 Families with different backgrounds

Some City Labs experienced the participation to the piloting of families of different backgrounds. While in some contexts (in Venice for instance) it represented a strength, in other such heterogeneity of backgrounds created some issues, mainly related to the communication side. This is the case of the Bologna City Lab where participants (engaged by the Dadamà Association) did not speak the same language and this represented an issue both in the piloting implementation and in carrying out the evaluation activities (especially the focus group). Indeed, the group of participants belonged to families with migrant background, living close to the piloting location. These communication barriers excluded these parents to the use of the Families Share app either.

4.2.5 Various type of stakeholders resistances

When using public schools' facilities during holidays, the school personnel might not always be supportive, raising several issues (as already mentioned above), especially concerning the maintenance and cleaning of the venues. Concerns about increased workload after the Families Share pilots seems to be at stake here.

⁴³ See Alijani S., Wintjes R. (2017), Interplay between technological and social innovation, Simfact working paper, volume 2017, n. 3 and Mulgan G. (2006), The process of Social Innovation, Tagore LLC.

Involvement of local NGOs as active core players can lead to misalignment, even in cases when the commitment and engagement are very high. Communication has to be handled very carefully to make sure that both the social and the digital components of the pilot are fully understood and valued by contributing organizations. In extremely small NGOs the identity of the leader can be overwhelming and not facilitate participation and agency of parents as (child) care-givers.

4.2.6 Organizational hurdles: families last minute withdrawals

The last minute withdrawals represented a relevant issue in few City Labs and were tackled by merging two co-playing groups and by putting additional efforts to involve non parents volunteers when they were announced up to few days before the activities started. Sudden no shows during co-playing activities are more difficult to handle and need to be prevented, or a back-up solution, most often a paid educator or baby sitter, has to be set up.

4.2.7 Groups of children with different ages

In several City Labs, issues regarding the composition of the children groups in terms of age range diversity emerged, both during the preparatory activities and the piloting. Parents tackled the issue creating sub-groups of children per age range and/by adapting proposed activities for younger or older kids. During the real experience however, the age gap did not represent an issue since older children helped the younger ones during the labs and played together during the free time.

In some cases, the presence of children of different age led parents to feel they would need more volunteers to support the same activity and that they would need specific training in order to be able to properly deal with them.

Parents seem to be in need for examples of how other groups handled such issues. In this respect, sharing best practices and successful stories among volunteers seems a good way for supporting confidence and motivation among participants.

4.2.8 Children sickness

In very small groups, this can lead to the cancellation of activities for the entire group and can represent a problem.

4.2.9 Safety and insurance issues

Since Families Share deals with sharing childcare activities, the safety and insurance issues emerged from the beginning to be particularly relevant independently from the context in which the activities take place. The relevance of the issue was immediately confirmed by the Kortrijk City Lab where co-playing activities have been run already for years. Indeed, according to the Kortrijk experience, the safety of children represents the first reason of conflicts among parents. The Kortrijk community managers help parents in dealing with such conflicts and take care of the insurance contract which covers both the civil and the penal liability.

The Italian City Labs had a meeting with UnipolSAI (project advisor) where the possible insurance coverage for childcare activities were explained. As a result of the mentioned meeting, the new legal entity (NGO) set up in the Venice City Lab stipulated an ad hoc insurance contract with UnipolSAI covering both adults and children taking part to the co-playing week in case of accidents/injuries.

In Bologna and Trento, instead, no ad hoc insurance contracts were stipulated. Indeed, in the first City Lab the Dadamà Association which co-organized the pilot with the Families Share team had already an active

insurance coverage for the members of the association. In Trento, the insurance provided by FBK already covering the civil responsibility for its employees was complemented with a specific insurance policy covering potential injuries to children participating to Families Share activities.

At the Győr City Lab, the team did not have to deal with insurance issues since the activities took place in a day-care nursery and playhouse already meeting all the requirements in terms of insurance.

Finally, in Thessaloniki for the first piloting the issue of insurance was not faced since during the activities all the parents of the children were present.

Regarding the safety issues it is also important to highlight that in two City Labs first aid courses for parents taking part to co-playing activities were organized. This is the case of Bologna, where the first aid courses were organized by the Municipality and of Kortrijk, where the community management organized 3 first aid and also shared an app helping parents when something bad happens. These aspects related to trust and safety issue will be further elaborated in D6.2, exploring insurance and safety implication of Families_Share activities and investigating challenges related to trust and safety in peer-to-peer exchange, in particular when children are involved.

4.2.10 Technical issues of the platform

Typically in a piloting phase of a not yet fully optimized platform, technical issues are expected and were faced by all the City Labs in a more or less critical way. Indeed, while most of the City Labs experimented some minor issues which did not affect much the use of the platform during the organization and the implementation of the pilot, for the Győr City Labs technical issues were rather critical and did prevent parents in the use of most of the platform functionalities.

All the technical issues encountered by City Labs were described in Part III of the present document and were promptly faced and solved by the technical team.

4.2.11 Embedding and aligning social and digital innovation

The project is implemented by almost all the City Labs in such a way that the proposed social innovation based on sharing childcare time by volunteering parents, although put forward at different pace and providing parents more or less support, has been tested while at the same time co-designing a digital tool with the same groups of participants. Only for the Belgian City Lab this alignment was not featuring the 1st Families Share pilot experiment: as already explained in detail along Chapters 2 and 3, in Kortrijk a successful co-playing model featured by a high degree of autonomy and self-organization of parents is in place. A fully accepted innovation is here ingrained and facilitated by a series of supporting tools which makes the acceptance of the digital innovation component (the Families Share Platform) difficult. This was emphasized by a further misalignment between the project's timeline as far as the release of the first release of the platform was concerned, and the need and habit of Belgian parents for planning their co-playing weeks well ahead of time. Such a missed synchronicity, partly experienced in Trento as well, emphasized the perception of the Families Share app and platform as redundant, especially for supporting a practice where time is a core aspect: parents are asked (among other things) to move time from their productive life to their reproductive one and they strive doing so as this is a very limited resource; this further diminishes their availability to lose time for other additional organizational tasks and testing new time/tasks management tools. The whole dynamic is leading to a missed opportunity at the project level for using the digital tool in the context where the social innovation component is more accepted and developed. This can be read and understood by considering the role of habit and routine practices within social and organizational changes⁴⁴

⁴⁴ See Alijani S., Wintjes R. (2017), Interplay between Technological and Social Innovation, Simpac Working Paper

and the negotiations which are featuring the acceptance and appropriation of whatever technical tool by users⁴⁵ (Oudshoorn & Pinch 2003).

Overcoming this challenge will be facilitated by the fact that the new improved version of the Families Share Platform to be used during the second pilot shall be released by the end of the year, making it possible for the Belgian City Lab to ensure its broad usage for the organization of the next co-playing groups in Easter/Summer 2020. The next phase will be based on negotiating between the expected features from the Belgian parents (to incorporate functionalities of the tools already in use) and several constraints mostly in terms of:

- needs from the other City Labs (to what point the advanced functionalities would be fitting the needs from other City Labs?);
- project resources/available time for making improvements;
- technical constraints.

To conclude, the dynamics of temporal appropriation will need to be carefully monitored in view of the second pilot while at the same time leaving space for the engaged communities of parents to introduce “unexpected or unanticipated uses of technology, although it can also mean the development of novel practices organized around the specific opportunities offered by a technology” (Dourish, 1999).

4.3 Emerging models

The first piloting put the basis for the identification of the different models of sharing childcare that better suit the various contexts involved. Indeed, every City Lab has its own specificities (detailed presented in Part II of the present document) and no unique solutions can be identified. We identified some existing commonalities which are always localized with many nuances anyways, and where the key variables are:

- **time** (the amount of time required to and made available by parents on one side, and on the other side the duration/frequency of the co-playing activities);
- **level of acceptance of the social innovation component**, based on informal care, therefore articulation between **formal/informal care** (autonomy of volunteering parents in conducting the childcare activities vs received support from paid ‘professionals’);
- **level of acceptance (in situation use) of the digital tool** from the side of the digital innovation element.

The two City Labs with the highest amount of time required to parents and with the longest duration of the activities (Venice, Kortrijk), made no use of formal care support or just as a back-up (Venice - Marghera). This is interesting as one could suppose that the longest hours are requested to parents, the shortest duration would be chosen and the more formal support might be needed, but our experience shows this is not necessarily the case. The two City Labs had indeed opposite performances in terms of level of acceptance and in situation use of the platform, and we have explained this with reference to different positioning of the two City Labs at different stages of the social innovation development curve (initial steps in Venice and rapid take off in Kortrijk) and with different schedule of planning activities of parents and the actual availability of a ready to use platform. Whereas in Venice almost all parents have fully used the app for getting organized, Kortrijk experienced a misalignment between an highly developed acceptance of the socially innovative

⁴⁵ Oudshoorn, N.E.J. and T.J.Pinch (Eds.) (2003). How Users Matter: The Co-construction of Users and Technology. Massachusetts: MIT Press.

behavior sustained by already well functioning supporting tools to organized and manage them, and a resistance to switch to the platform use. Here again, the concern from potential users seem to be related to time management.

Therefore, in our experience, it looks like **promoting acceptance of a digital tool and a socially innovative behaviors at the same time, can reinforce each other**, while, **vice-versa, misalignment can generate resistance from participants/users**.

Trento had also mostly finalized the organization of their activities when the platform was ready for use, and their experience with the second experiment integrating informal childcare managed by parents into an existing summer camp, stands in between, and shows a mixed model which incorporates specificities of a work place based pilot.

The other City Labs undertook, as explained, **more gradual approaches trying to minimize both the volunteering childcare time from parents and the duration of activities**, and aiming at building trust so. This happened either making external professional support available, or like in the Greek and Hungarian case, gathering all parents together with their own kids for the co-playing activities. Bologna was a standalone case having the co-playing activities managed by informal nonpaid care from volunteer leader of the involved NGO, with parents in a supporting and unscheduled role: this model requires changes which are already undergoing in order to empowering parents and providing them with greater autonomy and a role in organizing the activities. In all such cases, the app was not really piloted “in use” but rather tested after the activities.

Some further observations can be done for each City Lab individually:

- At the Venice City Lab, the co-playing summer week was a successful experience, leading the community management to focus on the reiteration of the experience also in other periods of the year (beginning of September, Christmas Holidays, Eastern Holidays, etc.). However, other solutions will be tested (i.e. pedibus and after school activities), according to the parents’ needs, reported during the evaluation activities. The support of the Municipality, which was fundamental for the positive outcome of the first pilot, will be maintained and further exploited for the future activities. In order to carry out the future pilot activities the new NGO will be used, exploring the availability of motivated parents to undertake management by the end of the second piloting phase. At the same time, the interest from other existing NGOs in the childcare sector will be explored to pilot Families Share with mixed models to complement their already existing services.
- In Trento the mixed model featured by the presence both of parents as volunteers and of professional educators seemed to be the one appreciated at most by parents participating. Indeed, participants to the pilots agreed that a support of professional is needed for managing children dynamics, especially in case of week-long activities and of big groups of children with different age range. The pilot activity which will take place in early September 2019 will indeed be organized using the mentioned mixed model. A mixed model seems to fit a working place based pilot better, as the support from external (child)carers or educators could reassure certain concerns from parents who find themselves taking care of children of colleagues they might not necessarily get along well at work or whereas hierarchical relations at work might collide with the a flat, peer-based socially innovative behavior requested within Families Share. However, the feasibility within organizational contexts of self-organized childcare activities will be further explored in the second pilot for short activities targeting small groups of children. In Bologna the collaboration with existing association was strategic for carrying out the first pilot activities. It will be further developed with other NGOs

and together with the involvement of the Municipality of Bologna through the stipulation of a “collaboration pact” for the use of public spaces.

- In Thessaloniki the model of co-playing afternoons combined with activities for both children and parents was successful. Indeed, future activities will concern not only a sharing of time for childcare activities but also a sharing of skills among parents, in order also to meet the parents need to socialize which emerged in strong way.
- Although the piloting in Gyor was successful, the community management did not have enough time to explore the kind of model which better suits the community’s needs. Indeed, the first piloting only involved 4 families only.
- As far as the Kortrijk City Lab is concerned, the experienced co-playing weeks model keeps on involving more and more groups, having reached already 50 co-playing groups. Efforts will therefore be placed on ensuring that a substantial number of parents start using the app/platform, while the consortium will try to mediate and incorporate some additional features to the digital tool.

Part V. Scenarios of future use and requested additional features

This last chapter explores the future developments of the Families Share platform and model, based on the inputs received during the evaluation activities⁴⁶ conducted with the pilots’ participants in each City Lab, as well as through the periodic reporting. In particular, the aim of the present part is to identify possible future scenarios of Families Share platform and model usage in the various contexts and the additional features that would be needed in order to implement such scenarios.

5.1 Requested additional features

For what regards the **requested additional features** of the Families Share app, they were investigated in each City Lab, during focus groups, individual interviews as well as through periodic reporting. During evaluation activities the following questions were posed to participants:

Focus groups:

- Would you add or improve any functionalities in the platform/application? If yes, which ones? (time banking system, other)
- In particular, which aspects of the platform could be improved? (i.e. communication, coordination, activities management, information, trust and privacy, other).

Individual interview:

- Would you add or improve any functionalities in the platform/application? If yes, which ones? Would you add for example a time banking system?
- For group administrators: are there any functionalities you would like to add?

The two following tables aim at facilitating the reading and interpretation of the different feedbacks received. The first one represents the inputs and possible improvements of the app on the already existing functionalities, while the second table lists the suggested additional features to be added in the app second release. In both tables, the third column shows from which City Lab the suggestions came from.

It is important to note that each City Lab, as well as each different group of parents, has specific needs and approaches for organizing childcare and managing the activities. Therefore the platform should be flexible enough to guarantee different uses and to support users’ appropriation of the digital platform. As also

⁴⁶ Focus groups and interviews

emerged in WP1 co-design activities, one of the main challenges is to adequately support the orchestration of offline and online interactions. This orchestration is of paramount importance in order to support the development of trusted-communities but also to support communities in finding the best online or offline tools that meet their specific requirements. This implies that different features should be provided to support self-organization combining online and face-to-face interaction, for instance by extending the digital functionalities to non-digital artifacts (e.g. printed calendar, exporting critical information such as emergency numbers or health-related children information, contact numbers, etc).

Functionality	Improvements	City Lab
Notifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to tap on a given notification and the app navigates directly to the subject of the notification. - Push notifications for every new activity of the group and every change in the planning. - Possibility to schedule reminders of upcoming activities (i.e. 2 hours before its start). - Option to receive a notification at the beginning of the week with all the activities in which the parents/ children are involved the same week. 	Bologna, Győr, Trento
Chat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The chat should be better organized, by showing all the messages in temporal order, from the oldest to the newest. 	Trento, Venice, Győr
Activity export	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to export data in a well printable format. - Visualization of activity information directly in the app, before receiving it by email (as a draft). - Option to export only the calendar with the organized activities listed (without all the details). 	Venice, Kortrijk
Children information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to visualize children needs and information directly in the app. - Option to see all the children present in a group, instead of only parents (adding a section to 'members'). 	Venice, Bologna, Kortrijk
Activities in the calendar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Add an icon to indicate the typology of activity (i.e. book=homework; ball=sport). - Possibility to synchronize the Families Share calendar with Google calendar. 	Győr
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to add timeslots after an activity is created. - Adding a section where all the members that participate in an activity are listed. - Option to give a feedback on the proposed activities. - Possibility for parents to add a preference in the typology of childcare activity they prefer to carry out. 	Kortrijk, Trento, Győr

Table 21. List of requested improvements

The majority of inputs were directed to the app notification system. This is due to the fact that, according to parents' inputs, push notifications did not work properly during the first pilot. Also, parents felt overloaded with different obligations and tasks during the pilot and they perceived the need of receiving reminders for the activities they were enrolled in. The activities section also received many different feedbacks, given the priority this functionality has within the platform.

The following table shows the received inputs regarding possible useful features to be added in the app second release.

Functionality	Additional features	City Lab
Notice board of social/childcare events in the surroundings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of an app notice board where users can add links to social events organized. - Possibility to have a searching engine for local events and celebration in a selected territory. 	Bologna, Venice, Győr, Trento
Administrator roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to block users in a group. - The option for administrators to add and remove people from the calendar/ timeslots. 	Bologna, Kortrijk
External educators/ baby-sitters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When creating an activity, possibility to add the need/presence of an external educator or a baby-sitter. 	Trento, Kortrijk
Links to external files	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of a section where users can share links to external documents/files (word/excel) needed for organizational purpose. 	Venice, Kortrijk
Archive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of an archive where to store files (pics and other documents). 	Bologna
Advanced planning capabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The app should help parents to create a matrix with the dates of needs for childcare of the different users, and the dates when each parent can provide childcare him/herself. From this data then parents decide when to organize childcare and who actually will look after the children on what days / timeslots. 	Kortrijk
Space management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Add a functionality that allows stakeholders to insert in the app spaces that are available to use, permitting groups to be also informed under which conditions those places can be used (e.g. only with insurance, only in some periods, etc). - possibility to “book” or get more information on available facilities 	Venice, Trento
Time banking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Add in the app a system of time banking, that shows the balance between provided childcare and use of childcare for every user. 	Venice, Kortrijk, Thessaloniki

Table 22. List of requested additional features

Many parents expressed the desire of using the Families Share app also as notice board for social events happening in their neighborhood (both regarding children and not). This points out a spread wish of parents of finding/building a community and a group of families not only with the purpose of helping each other with childcare solutions, but also for answering their need of socialization.

As far as the time banking system is concerned, some of the parents involved expressed an interest in inserting a system which could count the hours of childcare given and received by each parent. However, they agreed that the system should be kept flexible in order to maintain the solidary approach intrinsic in the Families Share model.

5.2 Reflecting on scenarios of future use

For what concerns the **scenarios of future use**, part of the analysis is based on the feedbacks received by parents during the evaluation activities as well as on the reflections at the City Lab level that are continuing after the pilots and through ongoing discussion with stakeholders.

During the evaluation activities (both during the focus group and the individual interviews) parents suggested different possible future scenarios that would meet their needs regarding childcare. The next paragraphs will better illustrate them.

At the City Labs of Bologna, Trento and Győr, participants stated they would use the Families Share model and the platform for organizing **after-schools' activities**, in order to cover the time-gap between the end of the school and the end of parents' working hours. In particular, at the Trento City Lab, this model would be useful for Friday afternoons.

Another possible future scenario is the one identified at the Bologna, Győr, and Thessaloniki City Labs, where participants indicated the model and the app would be useful for organizing and participating in **social events**. In particular, at the Győr City Lab, parents proposed to organize a charity event for families in need, for sharing school equipment or children goods. In this sense, the Families Share model would be used by parents to create a community of mutual help, able to answer to wider social needs besides the one of childcare. In Thessaloniki, parents expressed their interest in using the Families Share model and app also during sport events and daily trips.

At the Venice City Lab, as well as in Kortrijk, the Families Share model is perceived as more useful during **school holidays**, not only in summer, but also during Christmas, Carnival, and Easter time or during weekends. Still in Venice, parents during interviews explained that the Families Share approach would be useful for covering also short time frames (for instance one hour after school) and for random situations, when families are in need. A parent expressed the desire to repeat the experience also in a working environment, in order to connect families working in a same place.

In Venice and Trento some parents reported also the possibility to use the app to organize the activity of accompanying **and picking up children** from school to different afternoon activities.

Moreover, at Bologna, Trento and Győr City Labs, parents proposed to use Families Share model for organizing **homework help** or other educational activities, where parents can put at children disposal their skills in the different subjects of study. Lastly, some parents of Venice City Lab reported that they would like to use the Families Share app to **get in contact with new parents/families**, enrolled in the app, who share and approve the same model of childcare, in order to organize activities together.

On the basis of the desirable future scenarios expressed by parents involved in the piloting, most of City Labs have already planned or are in the process of planning new activities. The next steps of each City Lab can be summarized as follow.

At the City Lab of **Bologna**, the community managers foresee to continue to promote the app of Families Share in different environments. In September 2019 they are going to participate in three neighborhood's working tables, in which they aim to promote the app among the participating parents, in order to create neighborhood's informal groups. Moreover, between October and November 2019, the City Lab will present the app during different dates of an event of support to parenthood organized in Bologna, targeting parents of children between 0-3 years old. Finally, the community managers are working to disseminate the Families Share model and platform in the city of Pescara, where they got in contact with Biblio Attack⁴⁷, a parents' association that showed to be interested in the Families Share model and platform and wishes to promote it through its channels in the city.

The community managers of the **Trento** City Lab started a collaboration with the University of Trento (UniTN) in order to implement the Families Share model and platform also in the University's context. Indeed, in September 2019 a third pilot activity is planned, in which three morning labs for children of FBK and UniTN employees will be conducted at FBK's premises by FBK volunteers, with the support of University professional

⁴⁷ For further information, visit Biblio Attack Facebook page at <https://www.facebook.com/biblioattack/>

educators. The participation of FBK employees and the organization of the activities will be managed through the Families Share platform. Community managers have also reflected on the need of finding or setting up a new legal entity for the second pilot phase.

For what concerns the **Venice** City Lab, the enthusiasm of the parents taking part to the first piloting and their willingness to repeat the experience also in other periods convinced the community managers to be on the right track, therefore in the upcoming months they will be engaged in the organization of new pilot activities to take place in other holiday periods. Furthermore, the community managers are in the process of organizing a “pedibus” activity (consisting in taking children to and back to/from school) with the collaboration of the Vecellio school in Mestre, in the mainland. a. The request of using the Families Share model and app for organizing such activity came directly from a group of parents with children attending that school, who entered in contact with the project already in April 2019. The “pedibus” will be organized by voluntary parents with the support of both the app and the community management. Some e-mail exchanges and calls already happened in the previous months, but a formal meeting with the school’s dean is expected to take place in September. Finally, also the possibility to start after-school activities in the Marghera neighborhood emerged during the preparatory meetings and it will be better explored starting from September. The new NGO established during the first pilot phase will be also used as legal entity for the next activities.

At the **Győr** City Lab, participants to the study suggested the school holidays and the activity of accompanying and picking up the children from school, as other possible contexts for using the Families Share model and platform. In addition, the community managers intend to try to engage more fathers as well, even if this is probably going to be challenging as it is not usual in Hungary to have men managing childcare. For this reason, they are considering to propose some activities during the weekend, when fathers are usually not working, and they can spend more time with their family. The community managers foresee to organize the next pilot activity in October 2019.

The **Kortrijk** City Lab will continue with the co-playing weeks for the upcoming vacations (during for instance fall and Christmas holidays) but explore other possible solutions to improve the Families Share platform and model. For instance, the community management have identified a great interest in Families Share by companies which would like to implement it in their workplace. The City Lab already involves one company, but it will open the opportunity also to other companies.

In **Thessaloniki**, different activities will take place starting from September 2019, through the use of the Families Share model and platform. In details, the following activities will be implemented:

- co-playing Friday afternoons;
- after school educational activities for children;
- activities dedicated to parents (English, computer, knitting and sewing classes, etc.), to enhance the sense of community and build trust among families;
- Saturday mornings activities for children with art and/or science classes.

In addition, from September the community managers in Thessaloniki will involve schools in the co-organization of activities targeting both parents and children.

References

- Adikari, S., McDonald, C., & Campbell, J. (2011), A design science framework for designing and assessing user experience. In International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction (pp. 25-34). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Ajzen, I. (1991), The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational behavior and human decision processes*, 50(2), 179-211.
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1977), Attitude-behavior relations: A theoretical analysis and review of empirical research. *Psychological bulletin*, 84(5), 888.
- Alijani S., Wintjes R. (2017), Interplay between technological and social innovation, Simpact working paper, volume 2017
- Amabile, T. M. (1982), Social psychology of creativity: A consensual assessment technique. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 43(5), 997.
- Arnstein, S. R. (1969), A ladder of citizen participation. *Journal of the American Institute of planners*, 35(4), 216-224.
- Besemer, S. P., & O'Quin, K. (1987), Creative product analysis: Testing a model by developing a judging instrument. *Frontiers of creativity research: Beyond the basics*, 367-389.
- Carroll, J. (2004), Completing design in use: closing the appropriation cycle, in Timo Leino; Timo Saarinen & Stefan Klein, eds., 'ECIS', pp. 337-347.
- Cavoukian, A., & Weiss, J. (2012), Privacy by Design and User Interfaces: Emerging Design Criteria—Keep It User-Centric. Information and Privacy Commissioner of Ontario.
- Davis, F. D. (1985), A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end-user information systems: Theory and results (Doctoral dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology).
- Davis, F. D. (1989), "Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology", *MIS Quarterly*, 13 (3): 319–340
- Dourish, P. (1999), Evolution in the adoption and use of collaborative technologies. In Proceedings of the ECSCW Workshop on the Evolving Use of Groupware.
- Federici S. (2012), *Revolution at Point Zero. Housework, Reproduction, and Feminist Struggle*, Oakland, PM Press.
- Ferrant G., Pesando L.M., Nowacka K (2014), *Unpaid Care Work: the missing link in the analysis of gender gaps in labour outcomes*, OECD Development Centre
- Garrett, J. J. (2010), *Elements of user experience, the: user-centered design for the web and beyond*. Pearson Education.
- Harvey, D., & Cities, R. (2012), *From the Right to the City to the Urban Revolution*. New York.
- Hilgers, D., & Ihl, C. (2010), Citizensourcing: Applying the concept of open innovation to the public sector. *International Journal of Public Participation*, 4(1).
- Iveson, K. (2011), *Publics and the City (Vol. 80)*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Jeppesen, L. B., & Molin, M. J. (2003), Consumers as co-developers: Learning and innovation outside the firm. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 15(3), 363-383.
- Karapanos, E., Zimmerman, J., Forlizzi, J., & Martens, J. B. (2010), Measuring the dynamics of remembered experience over time. *Interacting with Computers*, 22(5), 328-335.
- Kim, Y. J., Chun, J. U., & Song, J. (2009), Investigating the role of attitude in technology acceptance from an attitude strength perspective. *International Journal of Information Management*, 29(1), 67-77.

- Molich, R., & Nielsen, J. (1990), Improving a human-computer dialogue. *Communications of the ACM*, 33(3), 338-348.
- Morgan D. L. (1998), *The Focus Group Guidebook*, SAGE Publications.
- Mulgan G. (2006), *The process of Social Innovation*, Tagore LLC.
- Naumann, I., & Hogben, G. (2008), Privacy features of European eID card specifications. *Network Security*, 2008(8), 9-13.
- Nesta Foundation (2017), *Digital Social Innovation toolkit*.
- Nielsen, J. (1994), *Usability engineering*. Elsevier.
- Nielsen, J. (1994), Enhancing the explanatory power of usability heuristics. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 152-158). ACM.
- Oláh L. Sz., Kotowska I. E. and Richter R. (2018), The New Roles of Men and Women and Implications for Families and Societies, in *A Demographic Perspective on Gender, Family and Health in Europe*, pp.41-64.
- Ossewaarde, M. & W. Reijers (2017), *The illusion of the digital commons: 'False consciousness' in online alternative economies*, *Organization*, Vol. 25, Issue 25, pp. 609-628.
- Oudshoorn, N.E.J. and T.J.Pinch (Eds.) (2003), *How Users Matter: The Co-construction of Users and Technology*. Massachusetts: MIT Press.
- Rogers, E.M. (2003), *Diffusion of innovations* (5th ed.). New York: Free Press.
- Stokes M., Baeck P., Baker T. (2017), What next for digital social innovation? Realising the potential of people and technology to tackle social challenges, NESTA - Digital Social Innovation
- Suchman, L. (1993), Working relations of technology production and use. *Computer Supported Cooperative Work*, 2(1-2), 21-39.
- Surowiecki, J. (2004), *The wisdom of crowds: Why the many are smarter and how collective wisdom shapes business, economies, societies, and nations*.
- Van Helvert, J., and Fowler, C., (2003), 'Scenario based User Needs Analysis', Chimera Working Paper2003-02. Colchester: University of Essex.
- Venkatesh, V., & Davis, F. D. (2000), A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: Four longitudinal field studies. *Management science*, 46(2), 186-204.

ANNEXES

Annex 1. Heuristic Evaluation

For conducting the Heuristic Evaluation the following Google form (<https://goo.gl/forms/815fQAVmDOAnqHQW2>) was used to collect experts feedbacks:

Heuristic evaluation of Families_Share Mobile Application

With this google form you can submit any usability problem you might find in the Families_Share mobile application. For each problem, please indicate where the issue was located, describe the problem, identify the relevant usability heuristics and estimate its severity.

Screen (or section):

Login

Personal information / Child information

Manage Group

Manage Activities

Messages

Altro: _____

Describe the problem

La tua risposta

How serious is the problem?

1 = Cosmetic problem only: need not be fixed unless extra time is available on project

2 = Minor usability problem: fixing this should be given low priority

3 = Major usability problem: important to fix, so should be given high priority

4 = Usability catastrophe: imperative to fix

Heuristic(s) violated

Visibility of system status (feedback)

Match between system and the real world (speak the users' language)

User control and freedom (provide "emergency exit")

Consistency and standards

Error prevention

Minimize cognitive load (recognition rather than recall)

Flexibility and efficiency of use (accelerators - unseen by the novice user)

Aesthetic and minimalist design

Help users recognize, diagnose, and recover from errors

Help and documentation

Annex 2. Usability testing

The following protocol for reporting users observations during usability test was used. Google Drive link: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1l_JLwdtD6PUQ5wKsBnSpl0THOCcNiXE1uZedYaipbi4/edit

Usability Testing TEMPLATE					
[This Template can be used to collect feedbacks during Usability Testing session. For each participant a sheet should be completed. About 4-5 participants should be involved. See D3.1. Session 3.3. for the procedure to be used during Usability testing]					
CityLab:					
Participant ID:	Date:.....	Gender: M F		Observer:.....	Note-taker:.....
Familiarity with technology	Please, rate you familiarity with technology: No experience Beginner Average user Advanced Expert <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>				
	Task completion <i>How user completed the task? (5 point Likert)</i> 1 = Completed without struggles 5= Not completed, lot of struggles	Completion time <i>How long did it took to complete the task?</i>	Description <i>How did the task has been performed? (describe the interaction path the user followed to complete the task)</i>	Criticalities <i>Describe main issues encountered in terms of: i) understability of information/navigation flow/ UI elements, ii) trust & privacy issues, iii)</i>	Perceived difficulty (SEQ) <i>Overall, how easy did you find this task? 7 point Likert scale 1= very easy 7= very difficult</i>
Scenario 1. [Add description of the scenario]					
Task 1.1. Log-in					
Task 1.2. Insert					

Annex 3. City Labs Periodic report

WP 3 – Piloting at the Citylabs

1ST PILOT ACTION (M13 – M21) - 3rd Periodic Reporting 1st June-26th July 2019

The aim of the present template is to collect information about the preparation and the progress of the first pilot action in each City Lab. Information provided will be used by WP3 leader to elaborate D3.2

Tables require extreme synthesis and up to the point statements, but in bullet points paragraphs please try to be as exhaustive as possible. We aim at having “*Thick Descriptions*” (as ethnographers like to describe it), reports that attribute meaning to events, characters, stories, social dynamics, by making it explicit within the socio-economic and cultural context where they are placed.

Partners are asked to fill the template and upload it in the dedicated folder in GDrive – [LINK](#)

Summary

A first paragraph should present a summary of all the activities carried out in the City Lab in the target period, including preparatory activities, piloting activities implying shared childcare, and evaluation activities (interviews/focus groups).

Summary table of engaged participants

	F	M	Age range	Migrant background
Overall number or parents involved in the period				
New parents involved in the period				
Total overall number of kids				
Overall number of single parents overall				
Overall number of kids with disabilities				

Summary table of engaged stakeholders

	Type of institution/organization	Role in the activities	Number and role(s) of participating persons
Name _____			
Name _____			

Preparatory Activities

All those activities such as meetings with both parents and stakeholders or other activities related to logistics and regulatory frameworks, needed for the set up of the piloting and child-care sharing activities, they might have taken place either before piloting or during

Summary of preparatory activities by typology

Type	Overall number	Short description /title	Number and role(s) of participating persons/institutions
Meetings with parents			
Meetings with institutions/organizations/networks			
Agreements prepared and/or signed			
Set up of new organizations			
Other			

Meeting with parents

1st FIRST MEETING: DATE (duplicate for more meetings)

- 1) Place-neighbourhood
- 2) Overall number of involved adults (and children, if any)
- 3) Institutional representatives/ stakeholders with legal entity and their roles/contribution
- 4) **Socio-demographic profile of participants and emerging needs** (*gender, age range, different socio-economic status, type of job, ethnicity, if single parents families are represented, if same sex families are represented etc.*)----
In case of many participants describe some 'typical' profiles, not each participant individually.
- 5) Discussed issues
- 6) Emerging needs and motivations
- 7) Emerging perceptions and expectations about Families Share (including negative/critical aspects)
- 8) Technology mediation for community's engagement and for relations within the communities, if any (e-mails, whatsApp/social media, others) please specify
- 9) Communication tools/media channels used to disseminate externally the actions (links welcome)
- 10) Any other issues related to the action in view of the piloting of shared-childcare

Meetings with stakeholders

1st FIRST MEETING: DATE (duplicate for more meetings)

- 1) Place-neighbourhood
- 2) Involved Institution(s)/organization(s)/network(s) including a brief description
- 3) Overall number of involved adults (and children, if any)
- 4) Institutional representatives/ stakeholders with legal entity and their roles/contribution
- 5) Discussed issues
- 6) Envisaged and/or set up collaborations in the framework or in view of the pilot
- 7) Emerging perceptions and expectations about Families Share (including negative/critical aspects)
- 8) Any other issues related to the activity in view of the piloting of shared-childcare activities

Other preparatory activities

Activity 1

Description including involved organizations, goals in the pilot preparation, outcomes.

Activity 2

Activity 3

Child Care Sharing and co-playing piloting actions

SUMMARY OF all PILOTING ACTIONS CARRIED OUT AT THE CITY LAB

Actions are composed/aggregates different activities which are the sub-units within each action, as they are categorized on the app. For example, the action named "Summer co-playing week in Giudecca" is composed of 2 activities per each one of the 5 days

	Number of involved parents and M/F ratio	Number of other involved adults (non parents volunteers, educators, coordinators etc)	Number of involved children	Age (divided in the 2 groups 3-6/7-11) and sex of the children	Duration	Type of Activity
Action 1 – Title						
Action 2- Title						

PILOTING ACTION 1- TITLE (i.e. CO-PLAYING WEEK CANNAREGIO_VENICE)

(To be described per group. In case the same group of parents has carried out more than one action, the section below shall be duplicated)

SUMMARY OF THE ACTION

Please write here a descriptive paragraph describing the overall piloting action capturing its main elements/contents in terms of participation, educational content, type of usage which was made of the app/platform:

TABLE Real Experience and Platform Use

When filling the table below, please consider the following: we aim at understanding the pilot action features in real life contexts and the use of the platform in that context, so the relation between the social and digital aspects of the experiment, the offline-online dynamics and the extent to what the platform/app was an effective tool to make shared childcaring possible. In the column titled real experience, please describe the information related to how in the real field experience the action was carried out. The column “platform should report on the information made available in the platform and the use of the platform on that particular aspect, when relevant. The column titled “Interpretative notes” can be used to clarify reasons and/or hypothesis behind the observed gaps between the real social innovation/childcare sharing experience and the platform usage.

TITLE (i.e. Co-Playing Week Venice Cannaregio) specify if routine/holiday/workshop or other	Real experience	Information on the platform/use of the platform	Interpretative notes
The group	N° of adults and children (M/F)	Out of the participating parents and children how many were registered on the platform? And how many other people not taking part to the actions registered and used the platform?	
Use of the app/web platform	Not relevant	How many parents used the mobile app and how many the web platform?	
Sociodemographic profile of participants (parents and others)		Not relevant	
N° of activities		Out of the activities carried out, how many were registered on the platform	
Content of the activities	What was put in practice in reality was it as described on the platform in terms of contents?	At what level of details did the activities were described on the platform?	
Duration of each activity	Was the duration reported on the app same as real duration?		
Parent/children ratio during each activity			
Average time made available by each parent and each		Not relevant	

family and time sharing principle (equal, flexible, time banking other)			
Other shared resources (beyond time)		Was the message section of the app used or the description within each activity? What other technologies?	
On line/offline information sharing/communication among parents	Type of information shared and average frequency of exchanges during the piloting, both on line and off line, related to the organization of the action itself and beyond for socialization purposes. Which media/technologies were used and how.	Was the platform used for information sharing? To what extent and how?	
Community management	Role/task/responsibilities	Use of the platform	
Group administrator	Role/task/responsibilities and who took the role	Use of the platform. The group administrators in the platform were the same people covering the role in the real experience	
Other group's roles	Describe	How were these roles performed on the platform? (how people with such roles did use the platform to such goals?)	

Other information

1. **Overall considerations on the piloting experience from a social innovation perspective in terms of meeting parents' expectations, quality of relations and trust among parents and with children**
2. **Did any misunderstandings/ tensions or conflicts occur during the pilot? Where they originated from on line or off line exchanges? How were they handled?**
3. **Overall considerations on the piloting experience on the platform/app and its role in the experience, its strengths and weaknesses**
4. **What additional functionalities of the app/platform would you suggest implementing in view of the second pilot?**
5. **Insurance and safety issues (how did you tackle insurance and safety issues? did any accidents/injuries happen during the pilot? How was it tackled?)**

Annex 4. Interviews

Template for the results of the semi-structured interviews

Dimensions	Questions
<p><i>Overall experience evaluation</i></p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Age/Job-employment</i> 2. <i>How and why did you join the Families_Share pilot activity? (explore, if not known yet, the way the person joined Families_Share)</i> 3. <i>In general, how do you evaluate your experience with the "Families_Share model"?</i> 4. <i>Are you happy about how the experience (or the week) was structured and its duration?</i> 5. <i>Can you name three positive aspects (if any) and three negative/critical aspects (if any) of the experience? (In case of negative experience, explore the reasons)</i> 6. <i>Did the experience allow you to create a community with new families?</i> 7. <i>Did you feel you could trust the other parents involved?</i> 8. <i>Did any conflicts arise during the experience? If yes, how did you react and eventually solve them?</i> 9. <i>Did you cover any group-role during the experience? (group administrator/in charge of overseeing cleaning or other)</i> 10. <i>How was your children's experience in the activities?</i> 11. <i>Would you repeat the experience?</i> 12. <i>In which other kind of situation would you use the "Families_Share model" (i.e. after school activities, christmas holidays, routines etc.)?</i> 13. <i>Overall, do you think the on line platform/app was useful as tool to facilitate the Families Share experience?</i>
<p><i>Usability</i> Issues encountered in terms of usability of the platform: Strategies to cope with criticalities</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Did you use the mobile app or the web platform?</i> 2. <i>In general, how do evaluate your experience in the use of the platform/application? (positive or negative?)</i> 3. <i>In general, would you define the platform/application easy/intuitive to use?</i> 4. <i>Please give a rate from 1 to 7 (1 not easy at all, 7 extremely easy)</i> 5. <i>Did you encounter any issues in the use of the platform/application?</i> 6. <i>If yes, in which functionality(ies)?</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Account creation</i> - <i>Group creation</i> - <i>Parent invitation</i> - <i>Activity creation</i> - <i>Calendar functioning</i> - <i>Other</i> 7. <i>Did you play the group administrator role? If yes, did you encounter any issues because of this role?</i> <hr/> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. <i>In case you encountered any criticalities in the use of the platform/application, how did you cope with them?</i> 9. <i>Did you report them to the community manager?</i> 10. <i>Did you receive timely and useful support?</i>

<p><i>Usefulness</i> (How the platform supported parents in : i) creating connections with other parents, ii) socializing childcare, iii) coordinating activities with other parents, iv) manage childcare activities)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>In general, did you find the platform/application useful?</i> 2. <i>Give a rate between 1 to 7 (1 not useful at all, extremely useful)</i> 3. <i>Did the platform/application help you to create new connections for co-organizing childcare with other parents?</i> 4. <i>How many parents you didn't know before did you get connected with through during the first pilot?</i> 5. <i>How many groups/activities you were involved into?</i> 6. <i>Was the co-organization of childcare activities with other parents through the platform successful?</i> 7. <i>In %, how much the organization of the childcare activities did happen through the platform/application and how much outside it (through other applications/by phone/offline)?</i>
<p><i>Trust and privacy</i> (awareness of privacy aspects related to sharing data within groups; needs related to trust and safety in online environment; understanding of privacy setting functions)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Did you feel comfortable in sharing your personal data and data of your child/children with the other parents of groups you joined?</i> 2. <i>Do you feel it would have been useful/better to share more/less data? Which data?</i> 3. <i>Do you know how to access your data and the data of your children and how to modify them?</i>
<p><i>Improvements for the 2nd release</i> Additional functionalities users would like to have related to: i) communication, ii) visualisation communication, iii) coordination, iv) activities management, v) information, vi) trust and privacy. Additional functionalities that Community managers and Group Administrators would like to have</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. <i>Are you aware of the reason why the platform/application collects your personal data and the ones of your children?</i> 5. <i>Is it clear who can access your data and the data of your child/children?</i> 6. <i>In the process of organizing the Families Share experience, do you think the balance between face to face meetings and on line exchanges overall was appropriate to create and sustain trust?</i> 7. <i>If not, why? How could it be improved?</i> 8. <i>Did any on line/off line conflicts or misunderstandings arise during the activities?</i>
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Would you add or improve any functionalities in the platform/application?</i> 2. <i>If yes, which ones? Would you add for example a time banking system?</i> 3. <i>In particular, which aspect can be better improved? (Communication, coordination, activities management, information, trust and privacy).</i>
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. <i>For group administrators: are there any functionalities you would like to add?</i>

Annex 5. Focus group

Template for the results of focus groups

Dimensions	Description and questions for focus groups
<p>Overall experience evaluation (minimum 10 minutes)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Did you already know each other? How many of you did already know each other? 2. In general, how do you evaluate your experience with the “Families_Share model”? 3. Can you name three positive aspects (if any) and three negative/critical aspects (if any) of the experience? case of negative experience, explore the reasons) 4. How about the different roles covered during the experience? (group administrator or other) / anyone encounter any trouble in covering his/her role? Was it good/appropriate to identify different roles during the experience? Were the roles too demanding in terms of responsibility and/or time? 5. How was children’s experience?
<p>Usability (minimum 10 minutes) Issues encountered in terms of usability; strategies to cope with criticalities</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Did you use the mobile app or the web platform? 2. In general, how do evaluate your experience in the use of the platform/application? In general, would you define the platform/application easy/intuitive to use? 3. Did you encounter any issue in the use of the platform/application? If yes, in which functionality did you encounter criticalities? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Account creation - Group creation - Parent invitation - Activity creation - Calendar functioning - other 4. How did you perceive the role of the group administrator? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do you think the role of group administrator is clear and well settled in the platform? - Did you rely on the group administrator for any issue? 5. In case you encountered any criticalities in the use of the platform/application, how did you cope with them?
<p>Usefulness (minimum 10 minutes) How the platform supported parents in : i) creating connections with other parents, ii) socializing childcare, iii) coordinating activities with other parents, iv) manage childcare activities</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In general, did you find the platform/application useful to the group activities? 2. Was the co-organization of the childcare activities with other parents through the platform successful? 3. In general, do you think the co-organization of childcare activities with other parents through the platform helped you to save time and efforts or was the use of the platform/application time/efforts consuming?
<p>Improvements for the 2nd release (minimum 10 min) Additional functionalities users would like to have related to: i) communication, ii) communication, iii) coordination, iv) activities management, v) information, vi) trust and privacy, vii) self-reflection tools (Open Data Analytics)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Would you add or improve any functionalities in the platform/application? If yes, which ones? (time banking system, other) 2. In particular, which aspects of the platform could be improved? (i.e. communication, coordination, activities management, information, trust and privacy, other). 3. In which other kind of situation would the “Families_Share model” be useful (i.e. after school activities, christmas holidays, etc.)?

Annex 6. Survey

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) questionnaire items

Dimensions	Items
Perceived Usefulness (PU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To what extent do you rate the following statements about the Families-Share app? (possible answers: Strongly disagree/ Somewhat disagree/ Neither disagree nor agree/ Somewhat agree/ Strongly agree) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Using the app makes it easier to organize childcare arrangements with other parents
Perceived Ease of Use (PE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To what extent do you rate the following statements about the Families-Share app? (possible answers: Strongly disagree/ Somewhat disagree/ Neither disagree nor agree/ Somewhat agree/ Strongly agree) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The application is easy to use
Attitude Toward Using (AT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For each of the activities below, did you perform this activity in the Families-Share application or not? (possible answers: Yes/ No/ I don't know or Not applicable) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ I created a group ○ I created an activity ○ I have sent a message in the group ○ I checked the proposed activities ○ I have added my availabilities through the app ● How many groups did you join as a member on the Families-Share application? (possible answers: one/ two-four/ I don't know) ● How good or bad would you describe your digital skills? (possible answers: Very bad/ Rather bad/ Neither good nor bad/ Rather good/ Very good) ● To what extent do you agree about the following statements about the usage of digital technologies (possible answers: Strongly disagree/ Somewhat disagree/ Neither disagree nor agree/ Somewhat agree/ Strongly agree) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Learning how to work with digital technologies is easy for me ○ I'm keen in trying out digital technologies ○ In general, I'm not so interested in digital technologies

Intention to Use (IN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To what extent do you rate the following statements about the Families-Share app? (possible answers: Strongly disagree/ Somewhat disagree/ Neither disagree nor agree/ Somewhat agree/ Strongly agree) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ I would like to continue to use the app ○ I recommended the Families-Share application among friends and family members
Social diffusion (SD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For each of the activities below, did you perform this activity in the Families-Share application or not? (possible answers: Yes/ No/ I don't know or Not applicable) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ I invited someone else to register to the app ● For each of the persons below, did you invite this person/these persons to register for the Families-Share app? (possible answers: Yes/ No) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ My partner ○ Grandmother / grandfather ○ Older siblings ○ Other family members ○ Colleagues ○ Friends (e.g. parents from my child's school)

Annex 7. Privacy and data protection

The information below on privacy and data protection were included in the first platform prototype, used during the first piloting.

What is Families_Share?

Please read the information below carefully before you decide to register to this platform. Please feel free to ask any questions you might have. If you are happy to proceed and participate, you will be asked to sign a consent form. Your participation is completely voluntary.

What is Families Share about? Families_Share aims to offer a bottom-up solution and a co-designed platform supporting families with sharing time and tasks related to childcare, parenting, after-school and leisure activities and other household tasks—with a particular focus on low-income families. The project also aspires to engage with the elderly by involving them in childcare activities and by offering them support in shopping and administrative tasks, but also by involving them in socialisation family events. To achieve this objective, the project will build on current practices that are already leveraging on mutual help and support among families, such as Time Banks, Social Streets and self-organizing networks of parents active at the neighbourhood level, and seek to harness the potential of ICT networks and mobile technologies to increase the effectiveness of participatory innovation.

Which information will be collected? In Families_Share platform will be collected information about parents, children, and childcare groups.

- About parents: name, family name, phone number, facebook account, address, email, picture/avatar and other information (About me).
- About children: name, birth date, gender, picture/avatar and other information specified by parents (allergies, diseases, specific diet, special need etc.).
- About childcare groups: the group name, group bio, childcare location, childcare periods and the messages in the group feed (text & picture).

The platform and the process which permits user to access data are compliant with 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR) and European Parliament Directive 2002/58/EC.

Are there any risks for my personal information? Data will be stored at the central protected storage facility of a cloud service provider in Greece, administered by a responsible person from VILABS (partner

in charge of the platform's technical development) and certified data protection officer from The Cloud service provider and following the best practices and standards available. Data storage and protection procedures are compliant with 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR) and European Parliament Directive 2002/58/EC. For the platform, the consent form will provide an email address to ask for access, rectification and removal. For the platform, the tool will provide a mechanism to access and rectify the personal data as well as the possibility of unregistering and removing all the personal data. For what concerns the portability of the data (art. 20), the platform will provide a mechanism to export machine-readable version of the personal information of a registered user. A strict security standard for children's photos and pics is ensured for the storage in particular taking into consideration the possibility of a cyber attack for sexual reasons.

Will my data be confidential? None of the collected personal information will be shared with 3rd parties.

Who is responsible for security information? The responsible of the data managed within the Platform is Apostolos Vontas (Vilabs). The responsible of (non-personally identifiable) data managed at Consortium level is Massimo Zancanaro (FBK). The responsible of quality assurance and policy compliance is Agostino Cortesi (UNIVE).

What happens if something goes wrong? Should you have any concern or complaint, contact us at cortesi@unive.it (project coordinator). We will attend to your enquiry within five (5) working days.